

**CULTURE ORTHODOXY IN SELECTED
NOVELS OF YORÙBÁ EXPRESSION**

FỌLÁKÉMI SHAKIRAT SHEHU

B.A. ED (Lagos), M.ED, M.A. (Ìbàdàn)

Matric No. : 73084

**A Thesis in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages
submitted to the Faculty of Arts in partial fulfilment of the
requirements for the degree of**

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

of the

UNIVERSITY OF ÌBÀDÀN

NOVEMBER, 2010

DEDICATION

To the glory of Almighty Allah, from whom all knowledge emanates
and
for my children: Olámipòsi and Opémipòsi

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by
Folákémi Shakirat SHEHU
of the Department of Linguistics and African Languages
University of Ìbàdàn, Ìbàdàn, Nigeria, under my supervision

 24/02/11
Supervisor

Durotoye A. Adélékè, Ph.D. (Ìbàdàn)
Department of Linguistics and African Languages
University of Ìbàdàn, Ìbàdàn.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I cannot enumerate the number of people who have, in various ways, partaken in the successful completion of this study. I am greatly indebted to all those whom I cannot mention by name, but who have contributed to the success of the work.

I will be an ingrate, if I fail to express my sincere gratitude and appreciation to my supervisor, Dr. D.A. Adélékè, of the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ìbàdàn, Ìbàdàn, who nurtured this work from its crude form to the elegant piece it now is. I wholeheartedly say a big "Thank you", for the encouragement he gave me, since the days of my "National Youth Service Corps" in 1992, when I had the privilege of meeting him at the Federal College of Education, Òsìlè, Abèòkúta, where he was a lecturer in the Yorùbá Department. I appreciate you for the encouragement you gave me to pursue the M.A. programme in the first instance, and the encouragement, brotherly advice, guidance, and "tongue lashing", especially, each time I was at my low-ebb, and almost giving up the zeal to continue the work. "Thank you" for the interest you have taken in my academic career, since the past seventeen years. I wish to remark that, if it were not for you that God used, this thesis would not have attained this successful stage. May the Lord God, who has lifted you up, never let you down. May you continue to abide under His Shadow and Grace; may the goodness and mercy of the Lord continue to follow you, and all that is yours, all the days of your life (Amen).

I am also grateful to my former supervisor, Retired Ven. Professor, O.O. Olátúnjí. May you continue to reap the fruits of your labour (Amen). I will also like to express my sincere gratitude to the Head of Linguistics and African Languages Department, Professor, P.A. Ògúndèjì, for his interest and encouragement, most especially, for ensuring that I proceeded immediately to the Ph.D programme, after my M.A., and that I did not abandon the programme. May the Lord God bless all the fruits of your labour, and may you reap the sweat of your labour (Amen).

To Dr. (Mrs.) A.G. Adéjùmò, I am greatly indebted. 'Sister', as I call her, always had a word of encouragement and advice for me, each time she saw me. Your words of wisdom and chastity played no small role in the success of this work. Thank you, ma, for all the "tongue lashing", and the "warm embrace thereafter". Sweet sister, words are not enough to express my gratitude to you. May the Lord God continue to bless you abundantly (Amen). I am equally indebted to my lecturers in the department: Dr. M.O.A. Olátéjú deserves a "thank you", for his words of encouragement; so does Professor D.K.O. Owólabí. I also acknowledge and appreciate the efforts of Dr. E.O. Olúkòjú, who, before his retirement from the services of the University of Ìbàdàn, exposed me to 'prose', as a course of study. May the Lord God grant you long life, good health and prosperity, to enjoy the fruits of your labour. I thank Dr. Herbert Igboanusi, for his constant encouragement towards the completion of this programme.

I equally appreciate the constant encouragement and gearing up of my dear friend, Dr. (Mrs.) Adénikeé Akínjobí, of the Department of English. You are, indeed, a friend. May God bless all that is yours (Amen). My very big "thank you" goes to my colleagues in the Department of Yorùbá, School of Languages, Federal College of Education, Òṣìṣẹ̀, Abéòkúta. I thank you all for the love which you continually extend to me. I shall be an ingrate if I end this acknowledgement without giving kudos to Dr. Adésojí Adérémi Fájényò, who has contributed in no small measure to the success of this work, I am indeed, grateful. Dáòdù, you are indeed, a true first-born child. And to Mr. P.K. Írókòtòlá (Ègbón), I thank you for your support and encouragement. I appreciate the Deputy Provost of Federal College of Education, Òṣìṣẹ̀, Abéòkúta, Mr. Nurudeen Oláńrewájú Oládiméji Sódipè, who was my lecturer in my days as a student at the college. He advised me to study "relevant courses"; thank you for giving me 'close markings'. May the river of your knowledge and wisdom never run dry (Amen). I also appreciate Miss Omówunmí Àdisá (Àbúrò), may all your hopes, dreams and aspirations come true.

I am grateful to my colleagues and friends, who showed interest and encouraged me to go on, in spite of all odds. I am particularly grateful to Dr. R.A. Sòyèlé, Mr. Kólá Òjéládé, Dr. G.A.K. Omóyínmí, Dr. Y.A.A. Jimoh, Mr. Dàda-Kóredé, Mr. T.A. Edokpayi, Dr. A.A. Àjàyí, Mrs. S.I.C. Iwuagwu, Alhaji D.A. Hameed, Dr. Barhi Adétúnjí, Mr. R.A. Éégúnjobí, Engineer Adèbèṣin, Mrs. A.A. Adésidà. I am also indebted to my late colleague, friend and confidant, Dr. Ameen Akínpèlú Hassan. May his soul continue to rest in perfect peace (Amen).

To all members of my family, I am grateful, especially to my husband and children, including Tèmitópé Táiwò, who endured and paid the price for my inability to attend to some domestic chores as a wife and a mother while this work was going on. Thank you for your endurance and understanding. I am grateful to the following friends also, for their support and encouragement, Mr. and Mrs. H.I. Kúyè, Mr. and Mrs. A. Àjàyí, Mr. and Mrs. Oṣinyemí, Mr. and Mrs. Fálòde, Mr. and Mrs. Akínbò, Mr. and Mrs. Adéléyè, Mr. and Mrs. Fábáyò, Mr. and Mrs. Mákíndé. And to Mr. M.N. Ibrahim and family, I say a big "thank you" for your encouragement, prayers and moral support, may everything you touch, 'turn to gold', Amen.

The painstaking efforts of Miss Kabirah Adébóyè, Messrs Kelim Olenloa, Adédayò Sóbàjò and Dr. A.B Sunday are highly appreciated. Thank you for making this work a success story.

I thank my darling husband, Oyètúndé, Mákànjúolá SÓLÀJÀ. I just want to remind you once more that I appreciate 'all that you mean to me, my Soulmate'.

Finally, I return all glory and honour to Almighty Allah, the King of the Universe, the master of the day of judgement, the one who has neither beginning nor end. Thank you, Sir, for doing it once more.

ABSTRACT

Previous studies on Yoruba novels mostly centres on the explication and critique of their thematic, stylistic and ideological preferences. Adequate scholarly attention has not been devoted to analyzing aspects of the cultural orthodoxy of the novels. For instance, the extent to which many novels written in the Yoruba language portray indigenous worldview of the people remains largely unknown. This study, therefore, investigated the representation of the Yoruba orthodoxy in selected novels, with a view to determining the level of cultural continuity amidst the effects of modernism and globalization.

The study adopted the sociology of literature as perspective that prioritises the nexus between literature and society, and post-colonial theory as frameworks. Thirty-four novels of prominent Yoruba writers such as Fagunwa, Odunjo, Olabimtan and Delano were purposively selected for analysis. The selected texts were further categorized into pre- and post-independence novels. Data were subjected to content analysis.

The selected novels reflected and refracted Yoruba culture and tradition through institutions such as marriage, religion, politics and economy, which were widely represented. Elements of culture contact featured prominently in the pre-independence texts of Fagunwa, Ogunjo, and Olabimtan who had approached marriage from a pure Christian perspective with their inclination toward monogamy. However, Johnson's work depicted extensively, traditional marriage and its processes, accentuating the chastity of the would-be bride and the payment of bride-wealth. Some of the texts emphasized the monotheistic stance of the Yoruba traditional religion. Fagunwa's works, for instance, stressed the belief in a Supreme Being as the commonality in the orientation of Yoruba indigenous religion, Christianity, and Islam, and, therefore, deplored all forms of religious intolerance. The selected works also mirrored the Yoruba traditional political institution, which was considered participatory, stable and well organized. Politics in traditional Yoruba settings was perceived to be a blissful competitive exchange devoid of violence. Furthermore, Yoruba agrarian lifestyle featured adequately in all the novels. Olabimtan, Fagunwa, Odunjo and Oladipupo, particularly associated the emphasis on agriculture with the Yoruba philosophical standpoint that food alleviates poverty. All the above themes were well represented in the post-independence novels other aspects of contemporary realities such as military dictatorship, electoral malpractices, and official corruption were reflected in the works of Akintade and Owolabi.

Finally, all the novels acknowledged the influence of modernism and globalization on the Yoruba way of life, especially the incursion of neo-colonial vices, which Delano devoted much attention to in his works. Olabimtan, particularly, decried these vices and suggested that Yoruba metaphysics be deployed in combating them.

The "Yorubanness" of the texts dwelt in the writers' representation of many indigenous and cultural values as ideals, which are necessary for maintaining societal equilibrium. The negritude orientation of the writers, however, conflicted with the post-colonial values entrenched by modernism and globalization, hence the vociferous criticism directed at neo-colonial practices. Above all, the extent of cultural products and images contained in all the novels certainly established Yoruba novels as veritable tools for cultural preservation.

Key words: Yoruba novels, Cultural orthodoxy, Modernisation, Tradition

Word count: 483

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Dedication	ii
Abstract	iii
Certification	iv
Acknowledgements	v
Table of Contents	vii

CHAPTER ONE: BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

1.0	Introduction	1
1.1	Purpose of the study	1
1.2	Scope of the study	1
1.3	Significance of the study	2
1.4	Research questions	2
1.5	Classification of novels selected for the study	2

CHAPTER TWO: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.0	Introduction	4
2.1	Theoretical framework	4
2.1.2	Post colonialism	6
2.2	Literature Review	9
2.2.1	Forms of prose	9
2.2.1.i.	Oral Tradition	9
2.2.1.ii.	Written prose	16
2.2.2	Cultural orthodoxy	19
2.2.3	Characteristics of culture	22
2.4	Multiculturalism	22
2.4.1	Conservation multiculturalism	23
2.4.2	Liberal multiculturalism	24
2.5	Globalization	25

CHAPTER THREE: CULTURE AND TRADITION IN FAMILY INSTITUTION

3.0	Introduction	29
3.1	The concept of family	29
3.2	The family as a miniature political organization	30
3.2.1	The roles of extended family	39
3.2.2	Co-wife rivalry in the family system	43

3.2.3	Ethics and values	48
3.2.4	Ethics within family organization	51
3.3	Courtesy	54
3.4	Yorùbá traditional dressing	60
3.5	The marriage institution	62
3.5.1	Types of marriage	66
3.5.1.i	Monogamy	66
3.5.1.ii	Polygamy	67
3.5.1.iii	Polyandry	67
3.5.2	Culture orthodoxy in marriage	68
3.5.2	Seeking a partner	69
3.5.3	Acquaintance of parents	70
3.5.4	Chastity	72
3.5.5	Orthodoxy wedding as reflected in Yorùbá novels	74
3.5.6	Royal marriage	82
3.5.7	Marriage through abduction of the girl	83
3.6	Modern marriage	85
3.6.1	Court marriage	85
3.6.2	Christian marriage	85
3.6.3	Muslim marriage	85
3.7	Divorce	87

CHAPTER FOUR: CULTURE ORTHODOXY IN POLITICAL INSTITUTION

4.0	Introduction	90
4.1	Governance and the Yorùbá society	90
4.2	Kingship	91
4.3	Monarchical governance with absolute power	93
4.4	Erosion of power	96
4.5	Erosion of power in traditional Yoruba society	97
4.6	Democratic dispensation	98
4.7	Military governance	107

CHAPTER FIVE: RELIGION AND ECONOMY

5.0	Introduction	111
5.1	Religion	111
5.1.1	African traditional religion	113
5.1.1.1	Sacrifice	122
5.1.1.2	Metaphysics	127
5.1.2	Christianity	136
5.1.3	Islam	142
5.2	Economy and culture	146
5.2.1	Cash crops farming	150
5.2.2	Food crops	151
5.2.3	Livestock keeping	152
5.2.4	Pastoral farming	154
5.2.5	Medicine and pharmacy	155
5.2.6	Hunting and fishing	155
5.2.7	Other professions	157
5.3	Women and economy	159
5.4	White collar job	164

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION

6.0	Introduction	166
6.1	Summary	166
6.2	Implication of the findings	168
6.3	Recommendations	169
6.4	Limitations of the study and suggestions for future study	173
	SELECTED NOVELS	174
	REFERENCES	176
	GLOSSARY OF TERMS	187

CHAPTER ONE

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

1.0. Introduction

The thrust of this study is culture orthodoxy as it is portrayed in Yorùbá novels. In the background to the study, the purpose, scope and significance of the study are highlighted. The methodology adopted in carrying out the study is also presented. As the theme reflects that culture is the bedrock of any society, the theoretical approach employed for the study encompasses sociology and postcolonialism. These approaches enhance the focus on the relationship that exists between culture and tradition on one hand, and society and the world of Yorùbá fiction on the other, vis - à - vis the Yorùbá world view.

1.1. Purpose of the study

This study examined trends and issues in culture orthodoxy as contained in Yorùbá novels and, by extension, Yorùbá society. The work examined the cultural practices and tradition of the Yorùbá as x-rayed in Yorùbá novels. The work also attempted finding out the level to which the contents of Yorùbá novels truly reflect Yorùbá culture orthodoxy. The ultimate aim is to find out whether these novels truly present what is obtainable in the society in the past and contemporary time.

1.2. Scope of the study

In this study, cultural issues are treated in relation to family, marriage, political, religious, and economic institutions. Therefore, novels that discuss the mentioned institutions were purposively sampled. The data were drawn from the selected novels and then subjected to content analysis. Altogether, thirty-four novels were studied. They were read repeatedly and issues arising from them were discussed. To ensure reliability, similar issues were studied as they are presented by different novelists. These novels were then subjected to content analysis. Some of the issues examined recur in some other novels. Thus, the findings from the selected texts are representative of Yorùbá culture and tradition.

1.3. Significance of the study

Many critical works on Yorùbá literature in general abound. Earlier studies on Yorùbá novels have focused on the rise and development of the genre. Ògúnshínà (1987 and 1992), for instance, traces the development of Yorùbá novels up to 1975. Ìsòlá (1978) attempts an examination of the writer's art in Yorùbá novels up to 1978, while Adébòwálé (1994) highlights the style in Yorùbá crime fictions. However, there is no work on Yorùbá culture orthodoxy in Yorùbá novels. This study tries to fill this gap. Besides, the study gives some insight into Yorùbá cultural norms, which will be useful to sociologists and anthropologists.

1.4 Research questions

Based on the focus of this study, it becomes necessary to provide answers to the following research questions:

- (a) Does the culture orthodoxy of the Yorùbá reflect in Yorùbá novels? If so, to what extent are they reflected?
- (b) How is Yorùbá culture orthodoxy depicted in Yorùbá novels?
- (c) Does the culture orthodoxy depicted in Yorùbá novels really reflect the Yorùbá world-view?
- (d) Are there significant influences in the way(s) the Yorùbá culture orthodoxy are practised in the past compared to how they are practised today?
- (e) Do Yorùbá novelists do justice to the preservation of Yorùbá culture orthodoxy and, can we say the novelists are true custodians of the culture orthodoxy of the people and their society as reflected in their novels?

1.5. Classification of the novels selected for the study

The novels considered for this study cover various aspects of Yorùbá culture and tradition. They include: *Eégún Alàré*, *Ogún Qmòdé*, *Kékéré Èkùn*, *Àyànmá*, *Aiyé D'aiyé Òyìnbó*, *Ó Le Kù*, *Ìyábò I*, *Ìyábò II*, *Atótó Arére*, *Ògbójú Qdẹ̀ Nínú Ighó Irínmalẹ̀*, *Ighó Olódùmarẹ̀*, *Ìrèké Onibùdò*, *Ìrìnkèrìndò nínú Ighó Eléghèje*, *Àdùití Olódùmarẹ̀*, *Ibú-Olókun*, *Àjékú L'ayé*, *Qmò Olókùn Èşin*, *Qmò Òkú Òrun*, *Kini Mo Şe?*, *Ìghì Aiyé N' Yí*, *Qìtè N'ìbò*, *Şìngbà Fọ́*, *Filà L'obìnrin*, *L'ójó Qjọ un*, *Ogun Àwítélẹ̀*, *Jé Ng Lò 'gha Tèmi*, *Ménumó*, *Ìjànbá Şelú*, *Kúyẹ̀*, *Kádàrá Àtì Ègbọ̀n Rẹ̀*, *Bàbá Rere*, *Orílawẹ̀ Àdìgún*, *Orúko ló Yàtò*, *Gbòbaniyì* and *Olówólayémò*.

Of all the novels, *Òghójú Qdẹ Nínú Igbó Irínmalẹ́*, *Igbó Olódumarẹ́*, *Ìrìnkèrindò nímú Igbó Elégbèje*, and *Ìrèké Onibùdó* belong to the Fágúnwà tradition. *L'ójó Qjó un*, *Ìgbì Aiyé N' Yí*, *Aiyé D' aiyé Òyinhó*, *Qmọ Olókùn Eşin*, are historical novels while the rest are social novels.

In conclusion, having discussed issues that are paramount to narrative prose in their different forms, it is necessary to examine the theoretical issues needed in this study. This shall prepare the ground for our analysis.

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the theoretical framework for the study. It also gives a detailed literature review of Yoruba novels and culture orthodoxy. In the course of this, theories of sociology of literature and postcolonialism are examined.

2.1 Theoretical framework

2.1.1. Sociology of literature

Sociology is a study of people and society. Society is an assemblage of people who share a similar cultural background and live in specific geographical areas. Hence, each society has a social structure, a network of interrelationships among individuals and groups. Different relationships exist in societies. The desire to determine its effects on the overall function of the society has necessitated the need to study society. Sociology, therefore, is the study of the individuals, groups and institutions that make up human society.

The field of sociology, according to Kuper and Kuper (1996:62), covers an extremely broad range that includes every aspect of human social conditions. They opine that, most sociological studies deal with the predominant attitudes, behaviour and types of relationships within a society. According to Emenyonu (1978), the term 'sociology' is a hybrid of the Latin word "socius" which means society, and the Greek word "Logos", which means "science". This is why sociology is seen as the science of the society. The term cuts across different human endeavours, including Education, Religion, Medicine, Sciences, Literature, et cetera.

Sociology of literature is a term that was created by Taine 1882-1893 (In *The World Book Encyclopedia*, 1992). The need for an empirical form of research for literature and art led to the establishment of this field of literary study. There are well developed sociologies of religion, education, politics, sports, knowledge and language. But it is not until recently that sociology of literature began to gain any serious attention (Ògúnṣínà, 1987:17).

The term "sociology of literature" combines two areas of study, 'sociology' and 'literature'. Sociology is the study of social relationships and the outcome of such relationships for on-going social systems and the process of social change (Moore 1965:207-209). Sociology concerns itself with all that happens to human beings as a result of their relationship with one another in the society (Barber, 1978:7). Literature deals with man and his society. It is an art composed of words, which entertains, enlightens and relaxes. In other words, literature showcases the experience and behaviour of man in the society (*The World Book Encyclopedia*, 1992:464). Sociology, according to formal and orthodox sociologists, has been defined as an essentially scientific and objective study of man in the society, the study of social institutions and of social processes (see Laurenson and Swingewood 1977). These groups of sociologists submit that sociology answers the questions of how the society functions and how it persists. Sociology examines social institutions of economic, religious and political structures, which form the social structures.

Literature is a discipline that involves man and the social world of man; it is also a field that is obviously affected by man's social world, his adaptation to it, and his desire to change same. Therefore, according to Professor Olátúndé Olátúnjì in his personal discussion with the researcher in his office on the 10th of September, 2002, "writings of any literary genre cannot be detached from the writer's experiences and culture, since literature itself is a mirror through which the society is reflected".

It is not a surprise that Ebewo (1991:60) posits that the society produces and influences a writer who in turn influences the society through his work. He further submits that literature is a product of the writer's environment. Every work of art centres on people and everything about them. Every action in a literary work transpires within the environment of a particular culture.

It is apparent from the above that the field of literature and sociology concerns the study of the society. This area of common interest is what culminated into a study area of sociology of literature. In his own view, Bámidélé (2000:4) considers sociology and literature as being the best of friends in spite of the discrepancies between their methods of discussing society. However, the conservative formalist school of critics considers sociology as an extraneous tool in comprehending literature, and as such, immaterial as a critical yardstick. Their consideration is based

on the artistic tendency of literature as an art. But, the structuralist Marxist school observes literature in its literariness and posits that it is defective in its style of studying literature without considering the social values and context of the text. This school's consideration is based on the social nature and importance of literature.

Gregor and Nickolas (1962) note that novel and drama are basically concerned with the moral and the story. The scholars reveal that novel shows the relationship between the author and the society, while drama deals with the author's relationship with the art. This shows that all novels and plays reveal the social life of a people. The social life of a people cannot be discussed in isolation: the culture of a people reflects in their social life. This is why Ìsòlá (1998:3) says "any critic who disregards the local conditions surrounding a work of art cannot establish what is universal about such work". He then recommends that any critic that will study modern Yorùbá novels objectively must be well grounded in the various outcome of the culture.

The above reveals that a novel cannot be studied effectively without considering its cultural background. This is because culture is the bedrock of the society of which the writer writes.

2.1.2. Postcolonialism:

Postcolonialism, also known as Neo-colonialism or Postmodernism, is described by Encarta (2008) as the philosophy of examining nature, meaning and knowing. It claims that postmodernists question the validity of the faith in science and the rationalism that originated during the enlightenment era and that became associated with the philosophy known as modernism. Osborne (in Encarta 2008) describes colonial rule as:

that which dominated the African continent from 1895 until the second half of the twentieth century. Not until 1990 did the last dependency, Namibia achieve independence. Years of intense and primarily European rule spread Western culture, government, industry, religion and medicine, across the continent. The relatively recent exodus of Western powers left the continent with artificially constructed nations and alien forms of government, still dominated by remote economic powers.

The Encarta expounds that all knowledge is necessarily shaped by culture. Also, Nkrumah cited in Offiong (1980:123) views Neo-colonialism as "the

process of handing independence over to the African people with one hand, only to take it away with the other hand". Nkrumah further defines neo-colonialism as:

Clientele sovereignty, or fake independence, namely, the practice of granting a sort of independence by the metropolitan power, with the concealed intention of making the liberated country a client-state and controlling it effectively by means other than political ones.

With the contact of the Europeans with the Africans under different guises, Nigerians travelled abroad in order to receive Western education. During the process of accomplishing this feat, they completely abandoned their traditional ways of doing things, including worship and religion, for foreign religion(s). This attitude makes such Nigerians and their 'Tòkunbò' children speak through their noses like the Westerners, after returning from their sojourn overseas. Sad enough, some Yorùbá who have received one form of Western education or the other, in an attempt to "belong" to the elitist group, use code-switching and code-mixing when speaking. This is a caricature of the "anglicized" Yorùbá man (Ìsòlá, 1998:120).

Mazrui (cited in Ìsòlá 1998) refers to these people as "Afro Saxon". These are the Yorùbá educated elite who take pride in speaking adulterated Yorùbá. Ìsòlá remarks that the fact that the educated Yorùbá take pride in this ludicrous and inelegant language use is annoying. The admixture of Yorùbá and English words is a frequent form of expression (Ògúnṣìnà, 1992:125). The situation today is that the Yorùbá elite cannot speak pure unadulterated Yorùbá for three to five minutes. This attitude is retrogressive. No wonder, Makward, quoted in Emenyonu (1978:103), aptly writes:

The African experiences in the 'Whiteman's country' and its effects on his behaviour among his own people 'Quandary of the Been-To', the evocation of the African past are more or less critical references to traditional customs and philosophies are the condemnation of the colonial abuses.

This prompts Bámbóṣé (2001) to ask the question of the kind of Nigerian citizens we are producing in our schools, homes, and community, whether they are the type that are more at home with American slang and pop culture than the Nigerian cultural and linguistic scene.

The situation where the cherished heritage of verbal art and oral renditions is not accorded its rightful place by the present generation, whose new religions teach that such oral traditional renditions are associated with paganism, is disheartening. The present generation which ought to pass this heritage down to the next generation is mostly prejudiced by its practice. With this situation, what will be left for posterity? Africa has very rich cultures, as noted by Achebe Chinua in Offiong(1980):

African people did not hear of culture for the first time from the Europeans: that their societies were not mindless but frequently had philosophy of great depth and value and beauty that they had poetry and, above all, they had dignity. It is this dignity that many African peoples all but lost in the colonial period, and it is this that they must now regain. The writer's duty is to help them regain it by showing them in human terms, what happened to them, what they lost. There is a saying in Igbo that a man who cannot tell where the rain began to beat him cannot know where he dried his body.

The writer can tell the people where the rain began to beat them. This work does not set out to condemn postcolonialism experiences outright. Rather, we intend to bring to the fore the various changes in the traditional Yorùbá society brought about by colonialism. Ògúnṣínà (1992:165) compares the pre-colonial life of the Yorùbá with the modern life:

Yorùbá pre-colonial life is portrayed as pleasant, peaceful and comfortable; it advocates and cherishes honesty and chastity. Modern life, though characterized by sophistication and physical attractions, is hypocritical, corrupt and immoral.

Ògúnṣínà is of the opinion that this outlook of the pre-colonial and modern Yorùbá life is biased as a result of a narrow assessment of the effect of colonialism on Yorùbá life. One then agrees with Ògúnṣínà's view that, despite the ills that emanate as a fall out of colonialism, it has brought about significant changes, progress and development into Yorùbá life. Examples of these abound in the areas of sophisticated cosmopolitanism, education, religion and industrialization observable in the society. Nkrumah (1965:239) observes that the greatest danger,

at present, facing Africa is Neo-colonialism and its major instrument is balkanization and recommends that:

In order to halt foreign interference in the affairs of the developing countries, it is necessary to study, understand, expose and actively convert neo-colonialism in whatever guise it may appear. For the methods of neo-colonialists are subtle and varied. They operate not only in the economic field, but also in the political, ideological and cultural spheres.

The neo-colonialists activities are portrayed in some of the novels studied through the institutions of marriage, economy, religion, politics and economy. The neo-colonialists activities do serve as means of preserving colonial ideas and ways of life in Yoruba modern society.

2.2 Literature Review

2.2.1. Forms of prose

Prose is the universal language of the novel (Íşòlá, 1978:3). It is the language employed for use in speech delivery and writing letters, newspapers and magazines, articles, biographies, histories and novels. Prose is the broad term used to describe all forms of discourse, spoken or written, which are not patterned into the recurrent metric units we call verse (Abrams, 1981:147). It is the language of everyday speech and writing. Before the advent of Western education, there was no written form of Yorùbá prose; all we had were oral forms (Obiechina, 1975:4). There are two forms of prose, namely oral and written.

2.2.1. i. Oral Tradition:

The oral form precedes the written and is rendered by words of mouth from generation to generation. In it, characters are unveiled through conversations and such conversations divulge the interaction among characters. Prose forms are also all forms of writing, written in prose style. These include stories, biographies, histories, letters, newspapers, magazines and articles. This kind of write-up differs from the other genres of literature; they lack rhymes, unlike poetry which is written in verse and stanzas; and they usually lack dialogue, which is peculiar to drama.

at present, facing Africa is Neo-colonialism and its major instrument is balkanization and recommends that:

In order to halt foreign interference in the affairs of the developing countries, it is necessary to study, understand, expose and actively convert neo-colonialism in whatever guise it may appear. For the methods of neo-colonialists are subtle and varied. They operate not only in the economic field, but also in the political, ideological and cultural spheres.

The neo-colonialists activities are portrayed in some of the novels studied through the institutions of marriage, economy, religion, politics and economy. The neo-colonialists activities do serve as means of preserving colonial ideas and ways of life in Yoruba modern society.

2.2 Literature Review

2.2.1. Forms of prose

Prose is the universal language of the novel (Ìsòlá, 1978:3). It is the language employed for use in speech delivery and writing letters, newspapers and magazines, articles, biographies, histories and novels. Prose is the broad term used to describe all forms of discourse, spoken or written, which are not patterned into the recurrent metric units we call verse (Abrams, 1981:147). It is the language of everyday speech and writing. Before the advent of Western education, there was no written form of Yorùbá prose; all we had were oral forms (Obiechina, 1975:4). There are two forms of prose, namely oral and written.

2.2.1. i. Oral Tradition:

The oral form precedes the written and is rendered by words of mouth from generation to generation. In it, characters are unveiled through conversations and such conversations divulge the interaction among characters. Prose forms are also all forms of writing, written in prose style. These include stories, biographies, histories, letters, newspapers, magazines and articles. This kind of write-up differs from the other genres of literature; they lack rhymes, unlike poetry which is written in verse and stanzas; and they usually lack dialogue, which is peculiar to drama.

The oral tradition also relies largely on human memory for preservation as well as transmission of the cultural repertoire. Iwara (cited in Dasylva, 1999:2) assesses oral narratives and observes that they are the imaginative use of language. Iwara views oral narratives as not just being story telling; they are the telling of a life experience : and adds that prose itself include oral forms of myths, legends, folklore, and historical narratives. Myths offer reasons and causes of certain phenomena in which past events are manoeuvred in order to explain, justify and comprehend events of the past and those of the present (Adéléké, 1998:186).

The oral form of Yorùbá prose began with folktales, myths and legends. The elders used to gather children together late in the evening, to teach morals and entertain the younger ones in their leisure time. Unfortunately today, with the availability of electricity and electrical gadgets, families now spend the time hitherto spent to present oral literature in front of television sets; others spend the time in going out to cinemas; while others prefer to watch home-videos. Few people read novels and other story-books. Worse affected are the highly educated elite, who spend time on the computer systems and in cyber cafes. Some younger ones are not excluded either. This newly imbibed culture is not without its shortcomings. In the name of modernization and technological innovations, violence, and sexual perversions are displayed and exhibited on the Internet and in porn magazines. Now children and teenagers are exposed to adult and x-rated materials, which are readily available through the Internet.

Moreover, the imported idea of monogamy, which results into individualism rather than communal polygamous life that was earlier practised by the Yorùbá, is gradually going into total extinction. The practice of such communal living gave opportunities to all the extended family members to have closely knit relationship, which enabled them to interact effectively, especially during the rendition of oral literature in the moonlight. Today, most families live away from the larger family and practise the nuclear family system, whereby father, mother and children live in self-contained apartments. Extended family members are rarely welcomed; the buildings they live in are fenced round in order to deter unwelcome visitors and intruders. This practice contributes in no small measure to the extinction of the traditional system of communal living and association. What is obtainable today is

the situation whereby children and probably adults who are next-door neighbours neither know one another nor relate socially. These days, everybody is preoccupied with his/her own business. This to some extent is responsible for the gradual extinction of oral traditions of the Yorùbá culture.

Another important factor in this regard is education and literacy. Parents would rather have their children at home in the evenings either reading or studying in preparation for various examinations. More often, children of school age use the evening time to do their various home assignments given by teachers in schools. Brothers used to be one another's keepers. This is rapidly disappearing in Yorùbá society, leaving instead the imported idea of "me and my family". This practice has come to stay, most especially, in the urban centres and among the educated elite. With the advent of literacy in Yorùbá society, written prose began with collection of folktales and local histories. This development gradually led to original compositions. This made people to lay claim to authorship. Fágúnwà toed this line, which was soon followed by other novelists in the Fágúnwà tradition.

According to Olúkòjù (1999), prose could also be classified as descriptive or explanatory. In descriptive prose, people are described by giving information about them. Actions, places, events and incidents are also described. In explanatory prose, all subjects, like politics, economics, history, philosophy, theology and the sciences, are explained. He further explains that a myth is a story that is believed to be true by a particular cultural group which also explains the reasons and whys of a particular natural phenomenon.

Oral prose is one of the folklores which refer to the culture, beliefs and tradition of a people, which are passed on from generation to generation. Fájényò (2003:86) sees it as an aspect of folklore. Dorson (1972:2) asserts that verbal lore is an oral aspect of 'folk behaviour'. It is the people's tradition and knowledge handed down by words of mouth. The common idea present in all folklore is that of tradition, which is something handed down from one person to another and preserved either by memory or practice rather than by written record (Thomson, 1974).

Finnegan (1979:38-39) builds on the assertion above, when she claims that oral or unwritten literature is a way of saying 'folk literature'. She identifies two

characteristics of oral literature² to be its traditional quality and verbal performance. The level of performance varies in line with the type of literature. Drama and poetry involve performance more than oral prose. Verbal lore is an expressive literature that is based on lexical sound. This means that it is learnt, perpetuated and transmitted orally in performance (Akinyemi, 1996:34). As a result of this, verbal lore is dependent on specific occasions: without performance, verbal art has no import of existence. Oral lore illuminates 'people's cultural values, beliefs and practices' (Olúkòjù, 1978:30), and it is the most significant aspect of any human culture (Ọlátúnjí, 1993:7). Verbal lore, as Goody and Watt (1968:28), (cited in Fájényò 2003:87-88) assert:

Channeled through words and reside in the particular range of meaning and attitudes which members of any society attach to their verbal symbols.

Şódípè (1991:8) hints that 'verbal lore is a foundation of the past which points out the rules and ethics of the society and also enacts the 'musical idioms'. It performs the functions of entertainment, information, instruction and guidance to the people from generation to generation. Bascom (1943:129-130) identifies the two categories of narratives in Yorùbá oral traditions to be myths, which he considers to be superior to and of more importance than the second category, folktale. He rates the former as being more realistic than the latter, which he takes to be fantasy and meant for entertainment. Bascom locates myths and folktales in the recital of Ifá verses and contends that the two categories be considered as analytical concepts which can meaningfully be applied cross-culturally.

This categorization is said to be overgeneralized and unsubstantiated. Dasyva (1999) contends that, while certain myths and folktales originate from Ifá verses, other myths and folktales came about by the sociological peculiarity of a people or society whose present settlement may not be traced to the Ifá verses. Bascom's criteria for classification of Yorùbá oral narratives are divinatory rituals, on the one hand and truth and fiction, on the other hand.

The quest for a more suitable classification of African oral literature is thus necessary, since existing Western classificatory criteria have been found inadequate led to the search for truly African critical standard for traditional and modern

African literature. The critics of these criteria according to Dasylyva (1999:15-16), are Yai (1972), Olábimtán (1975 and 1982), Amos (1976), Sekoni (1979, 1982, 1983a, 1983b), Chinweizu et al (1983), Olátúnjí (1984), Ògúnpòlú (1986 and 1990), Irele (1990) and Okpewho (1992).

The search led to the emergence of 'alter-Native theory'. This theory recognizes African loric traditions as culture-bound and takes cognizance of sociological factors, thus making classification to vary from culture to culture. It values and promotes cultural harmony. Ògúnpòlú (1990) uses performance 'spectrum' approach for his classification. He sub-categorizes the Yorùbá verbal arts as "ìtàn" (prose) and "Ewí" (Poetry). He sub-categorizes "Ìtàn" into four: "Ìtàn Fèyikógbón" (moral lessons); "Ìtàn Yèhùwò" (divinatory stories); "Ìtàn Orisun" (this includes stories of origin, legend, mythology); and "Ìtàn Àmúsagbára" (incantatory stories). He says that the social context which informs the performance of each story differs from one story to another. He cites the example of "Yèhùwò" divination narrative which only the "Babaláwo" (a diviner) can perform, whereas he cannot perform in the context of "Ìtàn Fèyí-kógbón". One agrees that this classification is a delightful improvement on earlier efforts by critics.

Dasylyva categorizes African oral narratives as comprising verbal and non-verbal aspects which are realizable only in actual performance and which may be referred to as 'whole text'. Therefore, classification of the oral narrative must consider the cultural imperatives which foreground it, because it is impossible to ignore cultural values to which the tale, and African oral literature, is bound. We rely on the "alter-native taxonomy" of the oral narrative, as proposed by Dasylyva (1999:37-38), because it recognizes African oral traditions and thus views lyrics as culture bound, including intrinsic and extrinsic taxonomic imperatives. The literature of a people cannot be detached from such people's culture and tradition. Earlier, Obiechina (1975:28) has noted that:

The traditional material of folktale, myth and legend is so intimately connected with the life of Africa that some knowledge of it is necessary to an intelligent understanding of certain areas of African creative writing... Writers of today must be influenced consciously or otherwise by the work of traditional artists like story tellers and praise-singers.

Oral literature must have formed the basis for the written literature in the pre-literature society, Africa inclusive. Folktales, according to *Microsoft Student Encarta* (2008) are fictional stories which are based on animals or human beings. The settings of the tales are not any particular place or time. They usually begin in a certain way. For instance:

<i>A-pa ààlọ:</i>	<i>Ààlọ o</i>
<i>Ìdáhùn:</i>	<i>Ààlọ</i>
<i>A-pa ààlọ:</i>	<i>Ní Ojọ kan</i>
<i>Ìdáhùn:</i>	<i>Ojọ kan kii tán láyé</i>
<i>A-pa ààlọ:</i>	<i>Ní ìgbà kan</i>
<i>Ìdáhùn:</i>	<i>Ìgbà kan n lọ Ìgbà kan m̀hò</i>
	<i>Ojọ n gori ojọ</i>

Story teller:	Story, Story
Response:	Story
Story teller:	Once upon a time
Response:	Days come, days go
Story teller:	Once upon a time
Response:	One period comes after another

And they usually end with the protagonist becoming victorious over the antagonist. Folktales reflect the attitudes and idea of a society. Bámgbósé (2007:14) captures this vividly:

The world of the folktales is a moral world, where wickedness does not go unpunished and the moral of the story is often pointed to at the end of such stories.

In essence, folktale is a traditional story or legend story that is passed down orally from one generation to the next and becomes a part of a community's tradition. Thompson (1965:178) sees the search for the original meaning of any folk as the search for the origin of that story. According to him, for both quests, adequate data are missing, and one is either left with a choice of making a guess according to our own predictions or of saying that we do not know. It is preferable to say that we do not know.

Coffin (2007) says folktales are a genuine term for the various kinds of narrative literature found in the oral traditions of the world in which some of their

many forms of folktales are heard and remembered; they are also subjected to various alterations in the course of re-telling. As they are diffused and transmitted through a culture, some folktales may pass in and out of written literature and some stories of literary origin may cross over into oral tradition. The principal kinds of folklore are myths, legends and folktales: In common usage, these terms are interchangeable: they refer to any highly imaginative concept that usually carries an implication of falsehood and incredibility. To folklorists, however, each of the three represents a distinct form of folklore.

Legend according to *Microsoft Student Encarta* (2008) is a traditional narrative or collection of a related narrative, popularly regarded as historically factual but actually a mixture of fact and fiction. The etymology of the word is the Medieval Latin word "Legenda", which means "things for reading". Scholars seem to be in agreement as to what is and what not legend is. Na' Allah and Ôgúnjímí (1991:46) claim that 'legends are always associated with events such as wars, rules (dynasties), migration and settlements'. Legends tell about recognizable people, places and events.

According to the *World Book Encyclopedia* (1992:452), these events are of more recent times. Some legends are said to contain imaginary characters. The heroes of legends possess qualities that their society considers admirable. The difference between myths and legends is that myths are told as though they were true while legends are set in the real world and in relatively recent times. Legends are associated with famous people who have died and whose names are immortalized. Some become gods, as they are deified. While a legend is set in a specific time, the subject is often a heroic historical personage, according to *Microsoft Student* (2008) DVD. A legend differs from a myth, in that legend portrays a human hero rather than a god. Legends are originally oral literary masterpieces.

Thomson (1974:173) avers that myths have to do with the gods and their actions, with creation, and with the general nature of the universe and of the earth. According to him, there seems to be a consensus that stories about the gods and their activities in general are myth. However, Wheelwright (1979:154) views myth as a complex of stories in which some are facts and others are fantasy, which for

various reasons human beings regard as demonstrations the inner meaning of the universe and of human life. The submission of Bidney (1965:11) is that myth is a stage in the development of the culture. It is a mode of thought based on the confusion of the symbolic ideal and the existential real which manifest historically at a given stage of cultural evolution. Myth is a necessity in the preservation of oral tradition of a people.

Barthes (1976:109-111) views myth as "a type of speech". Myth is taken as a system of communication; it is a message which has a historical foundation. It is a type of speech chosen by history. He opines that everything can be a myth provided it is conveyed by a discourse. He adds that every object in the world can pass from a close, silent existence to an oral state which is open to appropriation by a society, for there is no law, whether natural or not, which forbids talking about things. He further says that this kind of speech is not confined to oral speech. It can also be presented in the written mode.

Barthes also identifies in myth the three-dimensional pattern which he describes as the signifier, the signified and the sign. He constructs this from a semiological system, that which is a sign or concept of an image. The first system becomes a signifier in the second while the material of the signified is speech. In concluding this subsection, it is note worthy to agree with Adéléké (2004:2) that myths influence the present as well as the future. Thus, its sphere of influence is limitless.

2.2.1. ii. Written prose

The basic difference between oral prose and written narratives is in the method of transmission. This is clearly seen in the origin of the written prose. It began with translation of collected folktales and local history. From this, it developed into original compositions with people laying claim to authorship. It further paved way for such early authors as Fágúnwà, who wrote the Fágúnwà series of novels, and other early novelists, like Ògúndélé, who wrote in direct imitation of Fágúnwà and others who belong to the Fágúnwà tradition (Ògúnsínà, 1992:76-90). These days, there are numerous novels which are available for reading to Yorùbá and non-Yorùbá speakers. Hence, Ògúnsínà classifies the modern

Yorùbá novels and sub-classifies novels of the Fágúnwà tradition into four, namely: novels in direct imitation of Fágúnwà, the middle course novels and the mythological novels. He also identifies three sub-categories of the modern novel by their contents: historical novels, social novels and crime novels.

The novels classified as novels in direct imitation of Fágúnwà include those written by Ògúndélé, whom Ògúnṣínà (1992) says is the oldest and the most popularly read. According to him, Ògúndélé uses materials from Fágúnwà, who was undoubtedly his source of inspiration. Ògúndélé's novels include *Èjìgbèdè Lónà Ìsàlú Ọrun* (1956) and *Ibú Olókun* (1956), which is said to be a much better novel and more popularly read in schools, according to Ògúnṣínà.

Novels of the Fágúnwà Tradition include novels written by Fágúnwà himself, viz; *Ògbójú Ọde Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè* (1938), *Igbó Olódùmarè* (1949) and *Ìrìnkèrindò Nínú Igbó Elégbèje* (1954), which Ògúnṣínà refers to as a trilogy, while *Ìrèké Onihùdò* (1949) and *Àdìitú Olódùmarè* (1961) complete the set of novels written by the prolific writer. Ògúnṣínà identifies remarkable similarities in the setting, mode of adventure and moral purpose of the five novels. He comments that they give an impression of "if you have read one, you have read all".

Ògúnṣínà (1992:76) opines that "the five novels were highly successful and famous in the schools and among the general public". As a matter of fact, no novelist has been able to surpass the works of this legendary novelist, whose works are masterpieces, and whom many other writers imitate directly. Ògúnṣínà describes some novels as middle course novels. These are novels that deviate from Fágúnwà's pattern mainly in setting and characterization. In this group of novels, an attempt is made to place the setting in the 'real world' and 'real human society', rather than the forests and habitant of spirits trolls, gnomes and fairies (Bámgbòsé 2007:10), for example Oyèdélé's *Aiyè rẹẹ* (1973), *Ìwọ Ni* (1970). Oyèdélé's pre-occupation seems to be the dissemination of moral lessons, but, his works are not so popular (Ògúnṣínà, 1992:94). In this group also is Ọdúnjọ's *Kiyyé* (1964) and *Kádàrá àti Èghon rẹ* (co-authored with Ọládípúpò) (1971).

There is also what can be described as mythological novels. According to Ògúnṣínà, the high incidence of mythical materials and mythological motifs in these novels justifies this categorization. They are an offshoot of Fágúnwà's

tradition; the background materials of these novels are Yorùbá myths and legends. Examples of novels in this category are Ògúnníran's *Eégún Alaré*, Šóbándé's *Rìgímò Ohínrín Kò Ẹ é tí*, and Adéoyè's *Èdà Omò Oòduà* (1971).

Ògúńşínà (1992) also describes modern novels as a departure from the older novels and the subsequent emergence of what he has named the modern novels. Ògúńşínà (1992) identifies the historical novels, social novels and crime novels. These, he observes, came on course as a result of changes in technique, setting, point of view and structural pattern of the new class of novels. The modern Yorùbá novels he notes, is a result of a conscious effort to deviate from the general pattern of the Fágúnwà tradition. The historical novels, according to him, are Délànò's *Aiyé D'aiyé Òyínbó* (1955), *Lójó Ojójún* (1963) and Fálétí's *Omò Olókùn Eşin* (1969). According to Olúkòjú (1978), historical novels are a mixture of fictional materials and historical events.

The social novels, as categorized by Ògúńşínà (1992), are Thomas' *Ìtàn Èmi Sègìlólá* (1930), Jébođà's *Olówólayémò* (1964), Odúnjò's *Omò Òkú Òrun* (1964), Olábímtán's *Kékéré Èkùn* (1969) and *Àyànmó* (1973), Ládélé's *Jé Ng lò 'Gbà Tèmi* (1971), Yémitán's *Ghòbaníyì* (1972), Awóniyì's *Ayé Kòótó* (1973) and Ìşòlá's *Ó le kú* (1974). With regard to the crime novels, Ògúńşínà says, these include Omóyájowó's *Ìtàn Adégbésan* (1961) Òkédíjì's *Àjà ló Lẹrù* (1971) and *Àgbàlagbà Akàn* (1971), and Akinlàdè's *Ta ló pa Omò Oba* (1971), *Qwó tẹ Amòòkùn Şikà* (1971) and *Alòsì Ológo* (1974).

Ìşòlá (1978:124) further classifies Yorùbá detective novel as the tender and the tough. The tender, he observes, does not emphasis violence, but hinges on the intellect of the detectives. The tough novels discuss hardened criminals who are armed and desperate in their escapades and unmindful of the dangers involved. Oládèjò Òkédíjì, he claims, writes the tough type of stories, while Kólá Akínlàdè writes the tender type, which are 'really detective' in form and in tone; he views Òkédíjì's novels as "proper crime thrillers whose emphasis is on the chase".

2.2.2. Culture orthodoxy

Culture as described by Adéyemí (2005:3) is used to justify the dominations and oppressions of the “uncultured” group by the “cultured” group. This means that culture refers to the philosophy that distinguishes civilised people from the uncivilised. Thompson (1991:17) posits that culture originates from the Latin word ‘*cultura*’. It is a universal human trait, which is generally seen as a way of life. It embraces values, attitudes, beliefs and norms. Bámgbósé (2001:5) also explains that culture is expressed in customs, religion, language, literature, music, art, dance, drama, etc. In a plain language, culture can be said to be a complete way of life and it is in this light that the social scientists use the term culture. It is posited that every human society has culture which includes such society’s arts, beliefs, customs, institutions, inventions, language, technology and values.

Culture may be divided into material and non-material culture. Material culture includes all the things that are made by the members of a society, and are a product of human knowledge. Non-material cultures are the ideal cultures. According to Àjàlá 2002, the non-physical examples of culture include language, norms, beliefs, religion, philosophy, magic and witchcraft. (Dr. Ajala, A. is a lecturer in the Department of Archaeology and Anthropology, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ìbàdàn. He said this in an interview with him in his office on 11 – 06 – 02, in the Faculty of Social Sciences). The non-material culture is used to maintain and sustain the material culture. This means that some cultures are resilient and do not die; they continue to live. Examples of such culture are language, tribal marks, dressing, hair-style, diet and religion. The polytheist nature of the Yorùbá illustrates the fact that cultures are resilient.

Orthodoxy refers to tradition. The word ‘*tradition*’ is derived from the Latin noun ‘*tradittio*’ which connotes ‘handing over’. ‘*Tradittio*’ also emanated from the verb ‘*trader*’, which translates into ‘handing over’ or deposit (*Encyclopedia of Religion* 1995:1). It may then be inferred that ‘*tradittio*’ means teaching or instructing the inherited heritage of doing things, thinking, and feeling, which is orally transmitted from one generation to the other (see also Ajeleti, 2002:16).

Such heritages include cultural practices, religion, beliefs, philosophy and principles of a people which are preserved and which originate from the past. By

implication, culture and tradition are one and the same; because the culture of a people in a society means the way they do their things from generation past, which also makes it their tradition. The Lactic Law Library's Lexicon on tradition simply observes that tradition is the act by which a thing is delivered by one or more persons to some or more others. Thompson (1991:23) also views tradition as including aspects of the past which live on in the present, even if in changing form and with somewhat modified meanings. These changes do occur because culture is not static. Any static culture is a dead culture.

According to the *World Book Encyclopedia* (p. 491). "Culture is passed from generation to generation chiefly through language which is learnt through the process of enculturation". Children take on the language in which they are brought up. Hence, an Igbo girl brought up in a Yorùbá-speaking society will speak the Yorùbá language fluently, if she is communicated with in this language like any Yorùbá national, because she was born and raised in that culture. That is, no one is born with a culture. Children also acquire language through imitation and learning. They learn culture by observation of what their society considers right or wrong. Hence, culture is learnt and not inherited biologically.

A culture is based on symbols. Symbols represent one thing or the other, for example, skull and crossbones stands for danger; this is universal. Whereas in Yorùbá culture, 'Eja' (fish) stands for negativity while 'Akàn' (crab) connotes positivity in a discourse. A type of symbolic message known as 'Arokò' exists in Yorùbá. A mourner adorns a black outfit; red cloth signifies danger; while white stands for peace, purity and cleanliness. All human societies adopt the use of symbols to create and maintain culture.

Basically, the functions of culture are ascribed to humans. Kroeber, an anthropologist (cited in Angulu 1975:4) remarks that some societies exist without culture but that culture is what differentiates human from animal societies. Also, Kroeber holds the view that human's culture directs the kind of life they human beings lead. Kroeber actually opposes the truism in the study of man that "No culture, no society; no society, no culture" (cited in Angulu, p 5). He stresses the solitary uniqueness of human society in contrast to that of other animal species.

Anthropologists differ in their opinions on culture and society as concepts in the field of social sciences. Hence, three main groups exist among them. The first group defines culture as all embracing, including society. Malinowski champions this view. The second group is that which differentiates between culture and society. Among the proponents of this is Radcliff - Brown. The third group takes the middle course by subscribing to the fact that society and culture are two aspects of social realities viewed from different points of view of relationship and grouping and those of action and behaviour.

There is no wonder then that Makgoba et al (cited in Bámgbósé, 2001:16) asserts that language is culture and language expresses identity and culture. Bámgbósé, 2001 avers that man is the only living specie that has culture. He defines culture as the ability to originate and bestow meaning upon a thing and ability to grasp and appreciate such meaning. This is further buttressed by Andah, as cited in Molóyè (2004:378):

Culture embraces all the materials and non-material expression of a people as well as the processes with which the expressions are communicated. It has to do with all the social, ethical, intellectual, scientific, artistic and technological expressions and processes of a people usually ethnically or nationally or supranationally related, and usually living in a geographically continuous area: what they pass on to their successors and how these are passed on.

This shows that culture has to do with the totality of well being that makes the lifestyle of a people in a society which is passed down from one generation to the other. *The World Book Encyclopedia* (1992:490) says civilization is similar to culture, but that it refers mostly to cultures that have complex economic, governmental and social systems. A civilization, it says, is technologically more advanced than other cultures of its time. Hence, culture is way of life, be it simple or complex, advanced or not advanced.

Meanwhile, William and Walker de Felix (1992:20) define acculturation as a process of 'acquiring' a second culture and the gradual adaptation to the target culture without necessarily forsaking one's native language identity. For instance, a student learning a second language resides at the spot where the target language is

spoken for a period of time and tries to integrate himself into the culture and language of the host community. Hence, second language learning can also be second culture learning (Brown 1992:33).

From the foregoing discussion, it can be deduced that scholars in literature, sociology and anthropology agree to the fact that culture is a distinctive way of life which includes all aspects of human endeavour.

2.2.2 Characteristics of culture

There are several important characteristics of culture. *The World Book Encyclopedia* (1992:491) identifies the main ones as:

- A culture satisfies human needs in particular ways.
- A culture is acquired through learning
- A culture is based on the use of symbols
- A culture consists of individual traits and groups of traits called patterns.

Meanwhile, from sociologists' point of view, Kroehler and Zarden (1996:37-43) have earlier characterized culture into norms and values. Human needs are satisfied through culture. All cultures, thus, serve to meet the basic needs of man. For example, every man needs food to survive, as such, culture has methods of obtaining food, by cultivating lands, planting, hunting and fishing. The tools used to obtain the food depend on the culture of the people concerned. For instance, in most African countries, Yorùbá society in particular, the manual farm implements such as cutlass, hoes, diggers, and baskets are still used for food production. Conversely, in Western culture, mechanized farming is used in all farming activities from planting to harvesting and processing of agricultural products. In some other cultures, animals are still used to plough and carry out their farming activities, particularly in the Middle-East.

2.4 Multiculturalism

Multiculturalism is the co-occurrence of various cultures in the same society. It is not a new idea, but an idea that is borne out of coming together of peoples as a result of migration, commerce, displacement and conquest (Jusdanis,

1996:100). According to Adéyemi (2005:2), it was an official policy of Empires like Hellenistic Empire, the Holy Roman Empire or the Hapsburg Empire to tolerate diversity of cultures, languages and ethnicities. The American society, for instance, is faced with an upsurge of minority groups requesting acknowledgement of their identities and accommodation of their cultural differences. This challenge is called multiculturalism.

McLaren (1994:47) identifies three forms of multiculturalism as:

- (a) Conservative or corporate multiculturalism,
- (b) Liberal multiculturalism and
- (c) Left liberal multiculturalism.

2.4.1. Conservative multiculturalism:

This can be tracked down to the views of African – Americans whose perception as slaves, servants and entertainers is entrenched in the self-serving congratulatory and profoundly imperialist attitude of Europe and North America. Such an attitude depicted Africa as a savage and barbaric continent populated by the lowliest of creatures that were deprived of the most saving graces of Western civilization. It can also be located in evolutionary theories which supported United States manifest destiny, imperial largesse and Christian imperialism. It is also a direct result of the legacy of doctrines of white supremacy which conceived of Africans as “creatures” by equating them with the earliest stages of human development. Thus, Africans were likened to savage beast or merry-hearted singing and dancing children.

McLaren (1995:47) alludes to a former stereotype. A ten-year old black boy named Joseph and his mother were led to be exhibited at the Antwerp Zoo at the turn of the century. Also, he claims that, in a not too remote distant past, a “pygmy” boy was exhibited in 1906 at the monkey house in the Bronx Zoo as an “African homunculus” and as the “missing link” and was encouraged by zoo keepers to charge the bars of his cage with his mouth open and teeth bared. McLaren also points out that “America historically has been the “white man’s country” in which institutional and ideological patterns of men over women supplemented and reinforced one another” (p 48).

Conservative multiculturalists have scarcely removed themselves from the colonialist legacy of white supremacy. Although they would officially like to distance themselves from racist ideologies, conservative multiculturalists pay only lip service to the cognitive equality of all races and charge unsuccessful minorities with having "culturally deprived backgrounds" and a "lack of strong-family oriented values" (p 48).

McLaren opines that one particular project of conservative or corporate multiculturalism is to construct a common culture – a seamless web of textuality – bent on annulling the concept of the "border" through "the delegitimization of foreign languages and regional and ethnic dialect". It holds the position of common culture and bilingual education (p 48). The power of conservative multiculturalism lays claims to its constituents by conferring a space for the reception of its discourses. It does this by sanctioning empiricism as the fulcrum for weighing the "truth" of culture.

2.4.2. Liberal multiculturalism

Liberal multiculturalism is of the view that a natural equality exists among whites, African-Americans, Latinos, Asians and other racial population. This perspective is based on the intellectual "sameness" among the races on their cognitive equivalence or the rationality imminent in all races that permits them to compete equally in a capitalist society. However, from the point of view of liberal multiculturalism, though equality is absent in the United States society, it is not because of black Latino cultural deprivation, but because equal social and educational opportunities are not given to everyone to compete equally in the capitalist marketplace. They believe that existing cultural, social and economic constraints can be modified or "reformed" in order for relative equality to be realized.

Meanwhile, left liberal multiculturalism emphasizes cultural differences and suggests that the stress on the equality of races smothers those important cultural differences between races that are responsible for different behaviours, values, attitudes, cognitive styles and social practices. Left liberal multiculturalists believe that main stream approaches to multiculturalism includes characteristics and

differences related to race, class, gender and sexuality. Wallace (1995:261) is somewhat skeptical about the import of multiculturalism, stressing that:

By now I suppose everybody knows on the right, left and in the middle that, multiculturalism is not the promised land.

However, we want to add that with so much prejudice position held by the whites against the blacks and Africans, we subscribe to the principle of multiculturalism that projects equality of all cultures. This is in opposition to Hume's statement (cited in Adéyemí 2005:4) that:

I am apt to suspect the Negroes and in general all species of man (for there are four or five different kinds) to be naturally inferior to the white. There was never a civilized nation of any complexion than white, no arts, no sciences, such as... uniform and constant difference could not happen in some many countries and ages if nature had not made our original distinction between these breeds of men.

This study is opposed to the belief of white supremacists who are of the opinion that some people could not be fellow human beings because they differ in either colour, sex or culture. If the Almighty had wanted all human beings to be of the same colour, sex and culture, God could have created them as such; but as variety is the spice of life, the earth has been spiced up with multi-people, multi-colours, multi-sex and multi-cultures. However, this study does not aim at demolishing the preponderant Western-European cultures; rather, it advocates reciprocal recognition of other cultures, among which is Yorùbá, in the global community.

2.5 Globalization

The term globalization is fallout of colonization. Globalization, Awónúsi (2004:86) explains, is the umbrella term for appearance of a global society, in which economic, technological, and political environment as well as cultural aftermath of events in one area of the world will rapidly affect people around the world positively or negatively and will also have some consequence for people in the rest of the world. Instances of these abound in recent times. Global warming and

the global food shortage are good examples. Fólájin (2007:37) notes that globalization removes the limitations of distance and time. Awónúsi (2004:86) (cited in Fájényò 2007:3) view the concept thus:

Globalization may be regarded as transformation of our world "a process by which different regions of the world are pulled together through an expanding network of exchanges of peoples and culture as well as goods and services across the globe.

From the above, it is clear that the list of what can be globalized is endless, most especially people, culture, environment and agriculture. Global issues, as *The New Thesaurus* describe it, is so persuasive and all inclusive, as to exist in, or affect the whole world. Globalization occurs as an aftermath of advances in communication, information technology and transportation. It also describes the growing economic, political, cultural and technological linkages that connect individuals, businesses, governments and communities around the world. Whereas people live as individuals and nationals of a particular country, they are also linked culturally, psychologically, physically, emotionally and materially. People in different parts of the world are affected by the lives and livelihood of people in other parts of the world.

In recent times, global economic recession and economic meltdown have been affecting the whole world. The election and subsequent inauguration of President Barak Obama as the first Black President of the United States of America is another instance of a global event that affects all the people of the world, either directly or indirectly. However, globalization avails the world such opportunities as sharing of basic knowledge, investment opportunities, technological advancement, resources and ethical values.

Stager (2003), cited in Fájényò (2007), recognizes the characteristics of globalization as follows:

- i. Globalization involves the creation of news and multiplication of existing social networking and activities that increasingly overcome traditional, political, economic and geographical boundaries.

- ii. Globalization is reflected in the expansion and the stretching of social relations activities and interdependencies.
- iii. It involves the intensification and acceleration of social exchange and activities.

The above reveals that globalization encompasses a multidimensional set of social processes that cannot be restricted to a single theoretical framework. However, while discussing globalization and the search for cultural philosophy in contemporary Africa, Ukpokolo (2004:285) recommends, among others, that:

Africa in contemporary times should consider certain ideals, values and institutions: ideals such as considerations for the integral human person, integrity of life and self, considerations for the integral human person, respect for the institutions of family and marriage and any other capacities that can enhance the common good.

These recommendations of mutual love and respect for all cultures is borne in mind when the issues of culture, as they are reflected in Yorùbá institutions, are discussed, since globalization affects all nations. Egbokhare (2007), comments on the relationship between globalization and language thus:

The current form of globalization does not lead to language or culture contact in the traditional sense of the term... Languages do not of themselves come in contact, but people do. When cultures and languages flow with the aid of artificial vectors, such as technology, they are like weapons of destruction. Technology delivers language and culture with deadly and destructive consequences.

However, globalization eradicates individualism and leads to cultural identity. Since the world is indeed a global village, mutual respect for each culture and love of humanity is desirable, if the world must live in harmony. Moreover, since no man is an island, and none can exist in isolation of the rest of the world, the world would be a much better place to live in, if everybody accepts the fact that everyone should contribute his/her quota for the upliftment of the world, so that all would exist in a much better world.

Moreover, rapid changes in technology in recent times have altered the nature of culture and cultural exchange. People around the world can transmit

information to one another instantly, through the use of computers and satellite communications. Industrialized societies continue to develop new technologies, in order to produce products and energy en masse (Scholtes, 2004:37). Technology is employed to reduce the number of people environment can support. This according to Scholtes (2004:17) includes:

- Manufacture of birth control measures
- Ways of thinking, such as the ideal family size that is used to check population explosion and to avoid running out of natural resources.

This trend is contrary to the Yorùbá orthodox belief of having numerous children. Thus, this chapter has given its theoretical review of literature with the review of sociology of literature and post-colonialism. It has also given a review of relevant literature to the study which includes the review of concepts such as multiculturalism and globalization.

CHAPTER THREE

CULTURE ORTHODOXY IN FAMILY INSTITUTION

3.0 Introduction

Social institutions are essential parts of the whole which constitute culture. Hence, it is important to pay attention to various issues inherent in culture. These are institutions such as family, marriage and their structures. The ways these are depicted in Yorùbá novels are discussed in this chapter.

3.1. The concept of family

The Western ideology of the family emphasizes personal fulfillment as the reason for maintaining family relationship and love as the basis for marriage (Theodorson, 1965, cited in Henslin, 1980:415). Most people in the Western society thus get married in expectation of what that ideology promises. But then, they find themselves having to organize their family life along other dimensions of family responsibilities of choosing between having children or not, where to live and so on, whereas most people view the family as an emotional unit which is meant to cater for the well-being of its members. The family is also expected to stabilize interpersonal relationships which offer support, sharing and intimate communication among members (Baum, 1971, cited in Henslin, 1980:417).

The family in traditional Yoruba culture is communal in nature as it extends beyond the nuclear family system of the British culture. In it the concept of family (*Ebî*) comes to play. This is buttressed by Fadipe (1970) that family system encompasses kith and kin, that is, aunts, uncles, cousins, nephews, nieces, grand parents, brothers and sisters. Hence, the exclusive family life was impossible in the orthodox Yoruba society.

However, the British rulership which ended in 1960 exerted a lot of impact that altered much of the traditional Yorùbá culture today. The influence of the British colonisation was strongly felt during the almost fifty years of postcolonial rulership in Nigeria and Yorùbáland. Postulations about the family are integrated to the cultural ideology which affects all organizations in the society. As long as the family alone is believed to care for and promote people's well-being, formal

organizations can be based on principles which ignore or conflict with that well-being.

The *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English* (2008) defines family as a 'group of parents and children'. This definition is quite alien to what family is in Yorùbá society. It is an evidence of the concept of individualism, brought about by modernism. Fámílúsi (1998:16) claims that, basically, the family unit comprises the father, the wife or wives, mother(s) and the children. But the family system in Yorùbá community is more complex and exceeds the nuclear family only (Fádípè, 1970:99; Oyèdípè, 2004:247; Dòpámú and Alana, 2004:166). Thus, family system in Yorùbá society encompasses kith and kin, that is all those who are related by blood and by marriage. These include uncles, aunts, cousins, (whether first, second or third), nephews and nieces, step-fathers and step children, foster children, grand-fathers, grand-mothers, sometimes, great-grand-fathers and great-grand-mothers are inclusive.

Fadipe 1970 holds that the Yorùbá hold the family (*Èbí*) sacred and they are always conscious that the *Okìn Èbí* (family ties) is not severed by them, so that they are not punished by their *Alájòbí* (progenitors). Every member of the family has the interest of the rest of the family members at heart and there exists deep concern for the welfare, fortune and misfortune, joy and pain of the whole family. The close bond of the family in traditional Yorùbá society makes it almost impossible for the exclusive nuclear family life which exists in Western culture. This extended family system seems to be going into oblivion with the tendency towards the nuclear family in Yorùbá community, which is alien to Yorùbá society and a result of sophistication, civilization and culture contact. This is most commonly practised by the educated elite.

3.2. The family as a miniature political organization

In traditional Yoruba society, the family represents the smallest political organization, where the father is supposed to provide for all the material needs of the members of his household. As the breadwinner, and protector of the family and chief security officer, he caters for and cares for the family as the head of the family. The mother is believed to be innately capable of understanding and

ministering to the domestic chores and the emotional needs of the family. Mothers achieve fulfilment through caring for their husbands; bearing, nurturing and caring for their children and others who are by circumstance members of their household at any given time; and by contributing to the family income. Thus, they are deputy heads of families. The children are lieutenants or ministers who run errands and assist the parents in various ways. Each member has a role to play and every member works together to accomplish the purpose of the family.

Aiyé D'aiyé Òyìnbó depicts life in a polygamous setting. It is full of strife and envy among co-wives and children. The roles women play in child bearing and child welfare are brought to the fore in the novel. For instance, when Àṣàbí takes ill, her mother becomes anxious and disturbed. Àṣàbí is also worried about her husband's travails over the issue of executing authority in his domain. This is seen in her response to the punishment her husband (Baálé) inflicted on Adánójà (a resident of Ojúsàngó) who usurps an indigene's wife. She gives her unwavering loyalty and total support to her husband like a good wife should, when she says:

Ìṣe baba re lo se, Iwà baba re lo hu, Òyìnbó ni ó ṣiṣe... Bàba wa ló ni ilẹ̀yìí, kí Òyìnbó jáwó nínú ọ̀rọ̀ wa... (o. i. 39).

You are carrying out your father's deeds, you are behaving like your father, it is the whiteman that is wrong... This is our father's land, the whiteman should hand off our matter...

Essentially, the Yorùbá society is a patriarchal society, as captured in the Yorùbá adage: *Òkè òkú lòkú ñrè, baba ọmọ ló lọmọ* (the dead go to their abode, the father owns the child). Àgbégbémí upholds this saying in *Kádàrá àti Ègbọn rẹ*, when, in spite of his mother's love and affection for Kádàrá and the knowledge that mothers usually hold the last-born child very dear to their hearts, Àgbégbémí still exhibits his authority over Kádàrá and his mother. When Kádàrá refuses to choose farming as a profession, but prefers animal husbandry instead, his father is challenged. He uses all the apparatuses in his power as a father to make him change his mind. When Àgbégbémí finds out that Kádàrá had procured some animals to begin his pastoral profession, he becomes angrier and denies him food.

Bí nwón bá je onje kan kù, dípò kí nwón je kí Kádàrá je é. ajá ni nwón yóò ghé e fún, wón sì n sọ iyá rẹ lówó àti lésé

ki ó má ba à rí àyè fún ọmọ náà ní ọńjẹ rárá nínú èyí tí òun pàápàá ńjẹ. (o. i. 20)

If they had some leftover food, instead of allowing Kádàrá to eat it, they gave it to the dog. They kept watching his mother to ensure that she did not give him any food to eat out of her own portion.

Rather than give the leftover pounded yam to Kádàrá to eat, Àkóbí serves their mother's pounded yam with the exact portion she can finish and reserves the leftover till the following day, so that he can give it to the fowls and ducks to eat. This indicates that in the orthodox Yoruba society, a child is usually made to comply with the dictates of his parents particularly, the father. Though it was possible for him to seek survival elsewhere, yet he had to adhere to his father's instructions.

Ohun tí ó ẹ ni pé, lẹhin tí Àkóbí ti kọ iyán tí òun pèlú bàbú rẹ yíò jẹ tún, ó bu iwónba tí ó mò pé iyá wọn yíò lè jẹtán. sinù ãwo kan fún un, ó sì kọ iyán tí ó kù sínú igbá àdému kan, ó lọ gbé e pamọ di ọjọ kejì, kí nwón lè fi bó àwọn adìe àti pépéiye wọn bí wón bá ti oko dé. (o. i. 26)

What happened was that, after Àkóbí had served his and his father's pounded yam, he served the exact portion his mother could finish in a plate. He also put the remaining pounded yam in a calabash with a cover, and kept it till the next morning, so that it could be given to their fowls and ducks when they returned from the farm.

Kádàrá goes hungry and, needless to say, his mother becomes unhappy and offers him her food, but the love ties and affection between Kádàrá and his mother make him reject the food. He says, he would rather starve to death than watch his mother go hungry for his sake.

Nígbà tí iyá Kádàrá ti ọjà tí ó lọ dé, Àkóbí gbé ọńjẹ tírẹ fún un. Iyá náà ẹ àkíyèsí pé Kádàrá kò ì jẹ nńkankan rárá, ó sì pe ọmọ náà sí iyára gégé bí àsa rẹ. ó hẹé pé kí ó gba iwónha iyán tí mwón fi silẹ fún òun, kí ó sì jẹ é. Sùgbón Kádàrá kò jálẹ pátápátá. ó ní ó sàń kí òun kú ju kí iyá òun fi ebi sùn nítorí ti òun lọ. (o. i. 26)

When Kádàrá's mother returned from the market, Àkóbí served her food. The mother observed that Kádàrá had not eaten any-

thing all day long. She called Kádàrá into her room as it was customary to her, and begged him to eat the little pounded yam that was left for her to eat. But Kádàrá refused, and said; he would rather die than see his mother go hungry for his sake.

The action of Àgbégbèmi runs contrary to the Yorùbá proverb that says “*Omọ oníyàá kò mọ ebi*”, (A child that has a mother does not go hungry). This is because the father’s instruction that he should not be fed, has to be upheld by the family members. To further prove the patriarchal nature of the Yorùbá society, it is not only Àgbégbèmi that condemns Kádàrá’s choice of profession but the entire paternal members of his family.

*Bí enípé gbogbo ebi ni ó sẹ ni nípa ti isẹ àgbè tí ó kò láti ẹ
yí; nítorípé kí í ẹ bàbá rẹ nikan ni ó da ẹhìn kọ ó láti ìgbà
nàà lọ. Gbogbo ebi l’ómọdẹ l’ágbà ni nwón kò fẹ bá a ẹ
ohunkóhun pọ mọ, àfi iyá rẹ nikan tí ó dúró tí í.*

(o. i. 15)

It was as if he had offended his entire paternal family members by choosing the pastoral farming profession; because, it was not only his father that was against him since then. The entire family members, both young and old turned their back on him. They didn’t want to have anything to do with him, except his mother, who stood by him.

This confirms the Yorùbá adage that: “*Omọ tó bá dára ti bàbá ẹ ni, ẹyí tí kò dára ni ti iyá ẹ*”, (A good child belongs to the father while a bad one belongs to his mother).

Characters in Yorùbá fiction are essentially stereo-types. Ìsòlá (1998:51) remarks that they represent certain groups, ideas or traits in the real society. The presentation of characters in the novels mirrors the pattern of allocated roles in the society. Hence, characters are depicted in terms of their positions in the family. The world of the Yorùbá novels is the world view of the Yorùbá. The Yorùbá novels reflect Yorùbá life in all its ramifications; in them are intrinsic traditional traits that are exclusive to the Yorùbá family.

In the traditional Yorùbá system, husband, wife/wives and their children all live together in the compound of the husband’s extended family (Fádípẹ, 1970:98). The families of the husband and the wife were not neglected by the newly wedded couple; rather they all become one large extended family. This connotes that uncles,

aunties, nieces, grandparents, and, sometimes, great grandparents and great-great-grandparents all lived together in the same compound. This is what the Yorùbá called “*Ehí*” (extended family). That means, all those that were related by blood lived together in the same compound. Then, the idea was “*omo wa ní*” that is, ‘he/she is our child’. Everyone was his brother’s keeper, as such, they ate together, shared affection among themselves, felt their pains and shared their joy and had the same interest of the family at heart. The whole family members took care of the discipline of the young ones while the elders took care and settled issues and disputes among the older members of the family. Every member admonished erring members appropriately.

In *Éégún Aláré*, Dáṣofúnjọ portrays a very deep sense of family responsibility and commitment to his family, when his bosom friend, Lárinnàkà, approaches him that they should go on a performance exercise. He declines, saying he has some family problems which should not be left unattended to:

*Dáṣofúnjọ so fún un pé òun kò ní í lè lọ, nítorípé idiwó ilé
tí ènià kò gbọdọ fi sílẹ̀ lọ s’ájò pọ̀jù foun.*

(o. i. 28)

Dáṣofúnjọ told him that he would not be able to go with him because of some family problems he had, which should not be left unattended to and embark on a journey.

Lárinnàkà then entrusts the care of his wife and yet-to-be-born baby to his friend. During the long absence of Lárinnàkà, his extended family members fulfilled their obligation and responsibility to Ọ̀jélàdé (Lárinnàkà’s son that was born in his absence while he went on performance tour) by enrolling him for apprenticeship with his father’s friend, Dáṣofúnjọ, to learn magic performance:

*Àwọn mọ̀lẹ̀hi Ọ̀jẹ̀ Lárinnàkà mú Ọ̀jélàdé wá sí ọ̀dọ̀ Dáṣofúnjọ
pé kí ó múa kọ̀ọ̀ ní iṣẹ̀ idán pípá nítorípé esè bàba rẹ̀ ló tọ̀ wáiyé.*

(o. i. 10)

Ọ̀jẹ̀ Lárinnàkà’s extended family members took Ọ̀jélàdé to Dáṣofúnjọ in order for him to teach him the act of magic performing, as his destiny conformed with that of his father.

The extended family members also take the full responsibility on his graduation day. They play the role of a father to him, in the absence of his father.

Nìgbàtí ò dí ojù ọdún méta gbáko tí wón tí fa ọmọ náà fún Dásofúnjò, ní ó rǎnsé sí àwọn móléhí bàbá ọmọ náà, ó sì sọ fún wọn wípé ọmọ wọn Ọjélàdé tí yege isé tí ò ń kó. Ó sì mọ isé náà dárádára, ó ní kí wón ẹ̀tò kí òun ẹ̀ àdúrà fún un, kí ó lè máa bá ọ̀nà tírẹ̀ lẹ.

(o. i. 10 – 11)

After three full years that Ọjélàdé had been under the apprenticeship of Dásofúnjò, he sent a message to Ọjélàdé's extended family, that their son Ọjélàdé had completed his apprenticeship, and had learnt the act very well. He asked them to make an arrangement so that he could formally perform a graduation ceremony for him to become independent in the field.

The extended family quickly rises to the occasion in the absence of Ọjélàdé's father, who had gone on magic performance trip.

Ní ọjó kejì ní àwọn móléhí bàbá rẹ̀ ẹ̀tò àdúrà náà. Àwọn egbé éégún aláré sì wá ẹ̀dúrà fún un.

(o. i. 11)

On the following day, the extended family members organized the graduation ceremony, and the guild of *éégún aláré* came to pray for him.

In *Ó le kú*, the novelist presents foster parenthood in Àṣàké and his uncle, who is her foster father. Àṣàké calls him Bàbá Kékeré (Junior Daddy) and accords him the full respect one would give to one's father. Bàbá Kékeré also treats her like his own biological daughter, as he is often very worried and disturbed whenever Àṣàké keeps late night or fails to sleep at home as she did on an occasion, when she keeps a date with Àjàní. Bàbá Kékeré asks Àṣàké's mother:

"Ọmọ rẹ̀ ò mà sunlé yì lánà! Sọ o mọ?"

(o. i. 10)

Your daughter didn't sleep at home last night!
Do you know?

He eventually chastises her when she returns:

*E mọ káàhọ, ẹ káàhọ náà, kín lẹ wa ń dé sí?
È bá máa gbé-bé. E jówó níbo lẹ sùn o jàre?*

(o. i. 10)

You are indeed welcome, you are actually welcome,
why did you return? You should have stayed there.
May I know where you slept?

*Dáké nibè, àwọn egbé rẹ wà ní yunifásítì. Èyí tí n lẹ sílúú
Òyìnbó n lẹ, òun n jìjò ẹlẹyà kírì, Eni iyà, ojú rẹ ó já a. Ìwò
máa wòò.*

(o. i. 10)

Shut up there, your mates are in the university. Those of them who venture to travel abroad, do go, you are dancing - about, useless girl, you will regret it, you wait and see.

It is obvious from these utterances of Bàbá Kékeré that he wants Àṣáké to be successful and become a graduate. He does not want her to derail and become half-educated. He could not have done more for his biological daughter.

In the same text, the picture of commitment to the welfare of other members of such a family is vividly painted. A good example is when Bòdé, Àjàní's brother, is trying to help Àjàní solve the problem of choosing a life partner through religious means. Àjàní takes the problem as if it were his own and solves it through religious means, because a Yorùbá adage says "Àlòbìnrin kò Ẹ é dáké, ghogho ayé ni i bá ni í gbọ". (Not having a wife at the right time calls for action, hence, everybody is involved).

Another example of family commitment to the problems affecting individual members is seen in *Ọmọ Olókùn Ẹṣin*. In it, Àjàyí escapes from Òtu to Ìgbòho after he has challenged the authority of Olúmokò by seizing the working tools on the fields, as protest, so that his people would be freed from the political bondage of Olúmokò. The Alááfin strips Olókùn-Ẹṣin, who is Àjàyí's father, of Olókùn-Ẹṣin title. On hearing this in exile, Àjàyí becomes sad, because he has caused his family so much pain, even though he himself has had to leave home in order to escape the consequence of his action. Àjàyí converses with Àyówí:

"Njé o gbọ nkan tó n Ẹlẹl' Òtu?"

Ẹni kínní ló n bí ẹkejì rẹ lèrè báun.

"Kín ló n Ẹlẹ o?"

Hà! Wón mà tí yọ Olókùn-Ẹṣin lóyè. Àbó ọ mọ?"

"Hàn-ín! Ọmọ rẹ mà da ilú rí tán.

Olórún nì kò mà da ilú rí.

Ẹni kan tó tí Òtu dé lánà-án ló n ròyín fún mí."

"Kín ló wá dé gan-an?"

*"O Ẹun. Wón ní ọmọ Olókùn-ẹṣin sọ pé òun kò sìn
Olúmokò mó.*

(o. i. 32)

“Have you heard about the latest development in Òtu?”
 The first person is asking the second person.
 “What is happening?”
 Hah! Olókùn-Èṣin has been stripped of his title.
 So you haven’t heard?” “True! His Son had almost caused a civil strife.
 It’s only God that put the situation under control.
 Somebody that returned from Òtu brought the news to me.”
 What actually happened?”
 “Thank you. I heard that Olókùn-Èṣin’s son said, he would
 no longer be a serf under Olúmokò’s serfdom.

In spite of the difficulties and untold hardship he faces in exile, Àjàyí’s concern for his father and family is touching. This is a typical example of what family commitment and concern means to the Yorùbá; the family is paramount in their consideration.

Still on family, the need for a close relationship and sense of belonging within family members, whether the member is alive or dead, is treated in some Yorùbá novels. The Yorùbá take care of their dead and the belongings of the deceased. This is captured in the saying “*Adiẹ kii kú, ká da eyin rẹ ni*”. (You don’t dispose of a dead hen’s eggs). This is aptly demonstrated in *Ìyábò 1*, where the novelist discusses the death of Ìyábò’s Uncle, Bòḍá Eréko. Though he dies young, his extended family members take good care of his widow, the pregnancy and even the baby. After the child is born, Ìyábò asks her mother who is to be Èkúndayò’s foster father. She responds thus:

‘Babá kú, babá kù, bàbá Èkúndayò ti kú ni tòótọ, sùgbọ́n, ó sì ní bàbá púpọ́ láyẹ. Bàbá rẹ, bàbá rẹ ni, Bàbá Olówógbowó, bàbá rẹ ni. Bàbá Ìta-Àkànní, bàbá rẹ ni, tíí kan Bùròdá Ajégúnlẹ àti Bàbá-Òtá tí a n rí lẹ́ẹkan lódún. Kii ẹ eni tí ó bá bímọ nikan ni ó ni omọ... Bàbá mi rán an lọ sí ilé-ìwé, ó sì ẹ itọ́jú rẹ lórí sírísí ọ̀nà. Bàbá mi tilẹ̀ ni Èkúndayò pàápàá ńpe bàbá mi, tí ó fi jẹ pé àwọn ọ̀rẹ wa miiran ẹ hí bàbá mi ni ó bí.

(o. i. 45)

If one’s father dies, there are other fathers. Though Èkúndayò’s father is no more, he still has many fathers. Your father is his father, Bàbá Olówógbowó is his father, Bàbá Ìta-Àkànní is his father, brother Ajégúnlẹ is also his father, as well as Bàbá-Òtá, even though we see him once in a year, it is not only one’s biological father that is one’s father... My father sent him to school, he also took good care of him in various ways. Èkúndayò calls him ‘My father’, to the extent that some of our friends think my father is his biological father.

In the excerpt above, the practice of extended family and family members' commitment to their kinsmen are brought to the fore as the culture of the Yoruba. Whether such family member is alive or dead, the family still sees him as one of their own and, as such, takes charge and responsibility of looking after his widow and children. In *Iyábò II*, the novelist highlights what constitutes a family in Yorùbá culture. When he is being espoused to Olúfẹ́mi, on reading the letter of proposal, Iyábò comments as follows:

...Íwé yìí kii se tí bàbá àti iyá mi nìkan so so, tí gbogbo ebi ni, nitoripé ní ilẹ̀ Yorùbá ní ibi tí àwá ti wá, ebi kii se bàbá, iyá àti omọ nìkan bíi tí àwọn Òyìnbó. Ítumọ̀ ebi tíwa ghòòrò, ó bèrè láti bàbá bàbá, bàbá iyá, iyá bàbá, iyá iyá, ègbón, bàbá bàbá, àbúrò bàbá bàbá, àbúrò bàbá iyá, ègbón bàbá iyá, iyá iyá iyá, ègbón iyá iyá, àbúrò iyá iyá, ègbón iyá bàbá, bàbá bàbá, ègbón bàbá, àbúrò bàbá, ègbón iyá, àbúrò iyá àti béé béé lọ. Ènikan kii je àwádé! Se bí èniyàn bá yó ayé je dandan ni kí Olúwa rẹ̀ yó iyá je! (o. i. 25).

This letter is not meant for my parents only, it is meant for the whole family, because, in Yorùbá land, where we come from, the family does not constitute the father, mother and the children alone, like that of the Europeans. Our own family system transcends that, it begins with the paternal grand father, paternal grand mother, paternal great uncles, maternal great uncles, maternal great-great uncles, maternal great grand uncles, paternal great-grand uncles, paternal grand uncles, maternal grand uncles, maternal uncles, paternal uncles, et cetera. No single person constitutes a group of people! If a person enjoys the goodness of life alone, he is sure to suffer alone when the tides change!

This is what family among the Yorùbá is made up of: it includes all those who are related by blood in the extended family. The trend in family system among the Yorùbá in recent times tends towards the nuclear family system, especially among the elite. This is alien to the Yoruba orthodox culture and it is as a result of civilization and foreign education.

In *Ogún Omódé*, Ísòlá portrays a nuclear family structure, which depicts Bàba Délódún, Iya Délódún, Àyòkà, their daughter, and Délódún, their son. Délódún's grandmother lives away from Délódún's nuclear family, but they all live within the same village; however, the novelist also features Dọ́lápọ̀, who is

Délódún's cousin. Each member of the nuclear family lives separately in different houses. This might have been influenced by Christianity and the monogamous family system embraced by the new converts at that time. Délódún's father plays his role as a good father who has his daughter's best interest and happiness at heart. He displays this when the Catechist called to ask for Àyòkà's hand in marriage to a church member whose family he claims to know quite well. Bàba Délódún is reluctant to give his approval: rather, he enquires:

*'E dákun, e jé ká ro ọ̀rò yíí ire. Àwa kii sọ̀nìjẹkújẹ, kó tóó
dípé Ọ̀mọ̀dẹ̀kùnrin náà yóò gbé àna wá, mo fẹ́ kí tìyá tọ̀mọ
yín ròó dáadáa o. (o. i. 28).*

Please, let us consider this issue well. We are not gluttons.
before we accept any bride-price from this youngman, I want both
of you, mother and daughter to think about it properly.

In the past, parents would always dictate whom their children of marriageable age would marry, but the situation has changed. Today, mature male and female children bring home their would-be-husbands and wives to the parents. This is a sharp contrast and an imbibed ideology which found its way into our culture in post colonial days. Àyòkà plays her role well as the only daughter in the family; she cooks for her family as well as carry out other domestic chores. Délódún, though with youthful exuberance and pranks playing, also fetches fire wood and runs errands for his family.

In orthodox Yoruba community, the father is expected to be responsible not only to his immediate family members but to other members of the extended family and friends. This is displayed in *Kékeré Èkùn*. Bádéjọ, the head of his family, plays his role as a responsible father and a dutiful husband well. Bádéjọ, a cocoa farmer with yearly harvest yields, also plants vegetables and fruits round the year, so that he could have some for his immediate family, and friends' consumption throughout the year.

3.2.1. The roles of extended family

Ogún Ọ̀mọ̀dẹ̀ and *Kékeré Èkùn* depict that the Yorùbá society is a communal society where individualism is a farce. The Yorùbá society is a society in

which people feel concerned about one another's problems. This accounts for the concern of Bádéjò's family about his having an only child by his wife Àyàwó. He is told that he needs another wife to give him more children. He eventually takes one who almost annihilates his family.

Also, in *Àyànmọ*, Àlàbí begins to lose interest in Jòké, his uncultured wife, when she is rude to his family. She is neither pregnant nor raising a child; this is what Africans and the Yorùbá consider as the reason for contracting a marriage. A childless woman is considered an incomplete woman. Whereas having many wives is a proof of a man's virility, having many children is a proof of a woman's fertility. The Yorùbá have a saying that, "death has a remedy, and the remedy of death is proginety", ("*Ìkú lóògùn: òògùn ikú ni omọ*"). This means that one who dies, and is survived by children has not died, because he has left a part of himself behind – his offsprings. Hence, the proverb;

Bí iná bá kú, á fì éérú bojú
Bí ògèdè bá kú, á fì omọ rè rópò

If fire is extinguished it leaves behind ashes
If banana tree dies, it replaces itself with its suckers.

It also shows in such sayings as "*Olómọ ló layé*" (one who has children possesses the world). When a man dies, the Yorùbá also say:

Òkú Olówó, iyẹn á gba ọdún kan
Òkú Òtòṣì, iyẹn á gba ọṣù méfà
Òkú Olómọ, àṣẹ̀èṣẹ̀tán.

The burial ceremony of the rich lasts a year
The burial ceremony of the poor lasts six months
The burial ceremony of one who has many children is endless.

The thought behind this philosophy is that the demise of a man who has many children is celebrated gloriously and intermittently. The children may periodically choose to remember him and celebrate his lifetime, this is called '*yíyí ègbé òkú padù*' (remembrance of the dead). In the recent past, most couples preferred to have three or four children. But today, couples opt for one, two or three children at most. The reason is not difficult to find. It could be as a result of the

harsh economic situation of today, which has made having many children, a luxury. Besides, civilization and liberation have opened the eyes and ways of reasoning of couples to see that the fewer the number of children in a family the merrier and the more prosperous the family is likely to be. Provisions will be able to go round the few members of the family, based on the meager income of most couples. The issue of maintaining good and healthy living by the few members of the family is also a factor.

Àyànmó, a sequel to *Kékeré Èkùn*, equally portrays Yorùbá culture and its beauty. It reflects the interference of the family in the affairs of young couples. A couple cannot live their life in isolation of the extended family. A Yorùbá couple cannot live in solitude, an idea derived from Euro-Christian culture. The extended family intervenes and sees the marital problems of their children, even though married, as their own.

Àyànmó stresses the Yorùbá belief that a typical traditional Yorùbá society believes in having many children. In fact, the more children a man had the wealthier and more prestigious he was. In *Àyànmó*, Àyàwó has only Àlàbí. This culminated into Bádéjò's action of taking Àdùfẹ as a second wife, so that she could bear him more children. This action leads to the death of Àdùfẹ's child, who mistakenly swallows the poisoned food his mother prepared for Àlàbí. Here, the author portrays polygamy as being devilish and deadly, presenting it in a negative way.

The traditional communal effort at raising well-disciplined children and the notion that all adults are responsible for proper upbringing of children is portrayed in *Ogún Omode*. In this novel, Bábá Délódún chastises Fọlá for failing to pick up a cane to beat Délódún when he misbehaved.

Njé bí irú omode yìi bá sè ó, kò ha yẹ kí o lè baa wi fúnra rẹ ndan? Kín ló ẹ tí o kò ti mọré láti àná náà, kóo ti fín in bí ẹnì fíngbá, ká wá máa wẹni tí yóò sọ pé o kò ẹe re ...

(o. i. 15)

So, if this little child had offended you, shouldn't you have punished him yourself? Why didn't you pick a cane to beat him since yesterday. Why didn't you beat him mercilessly and let's see if anyone would say you've not done well.

This family closeness and collective responsibility enables children to grow up well-disciplined. Unfortunately today, civilization makes parents question even teachers and authorities concerned when they discipline their children and wards. They also challenge other adults who may want to correct or discipline an errant child.

Ọlábímtán opposes this practice in *Kékeré Ekùn*, when Àlábí is erroneously accused of stealing his teacher's book containing already set questions. Àlábí's father goes to Àlábí's school to challenge the headmaster, and meets the clergyman there, who counsels thus:

*Ohun kan sí ti mo fẹ sọ fún Bádéjọ ní pé, ọ̀rọ̀ àghà ni ọ̀gá ilé-
iwé sọ nígbà tí ó sọ pé "òtùn wẹ ọ̀sì, ọ̀sì wẹ ọ̀tùn mà l'owó
fi òmó". B'ọ̀rọ̀ ẹ̀kọ̀ ọ̀mọ̀ tí rí gan niyẹn. Ẹ̀kọ̀ ilé ọ̀rọ̀, ẹ̀kọ̀ ita ni ó tẹ̀lẹ̀,
sùgbón àpapọ̀ méjèjì l'ó nís'ọ̀mọ̀ di ọ̀lọ̀ghón, olóye àti onímọ̀.
Ẹ̀nikéni tí ó bá sì ní àwọn wònyí, ọ̀lólá ni. Ẹ̀kọ̀ ilé jé isẹ̀ ọ̀hí àti ẹ̀bí,
sùgbón ẹ̀kọ̀ ita ni isẹ̀ ilú. àti ti ijọba...
Nitorí èyí ni gbogbo èni tó bá fi ọ̀mọ̀ sí ilé-iwé gbódò máa fi ẹ̀kọ̀
ilé bó ọ̀mọ̀ wọn bí ọ̀njẹ, kí nwón sì máa sowópò pèlú tísà láti ríi pé
ọ̀mọ̀ wọn gba ẹ̀kọ̀ tí ita kún l'ilé kí ọ̀mọ̀ wọn ba lè di ọ̀jọ̀ghón, olóye
àti onímọ̀... (o. i. 36-37).*

One thing I want to tell Bádéjọ is that, the advice given him by the headmaster is the wise counsel of the elders, when he says "if the right hand washes the left hand, and the left hand washes the right hand, is what makes the hands clean". This is exactly what the education of the child is like. Home training comes first, followed by formal education, the combination is what makes the child a wise person. Education within is the responsibility of the parents and the responsibility of the extended family members, while education without is the responsibility of the public and government... Because of this, everyone who sends his child to school must compliment it with home training, just like food, the home must also cooperate with the teachers to ensure that the child receives formal education in addition to "home training", so that their children may become well trained, well-educated and wise.

The novelist therefore advocates collective and collaborative efforts of the home and the school in bringing up, well educated and well behaved children.

With the incursion of the Western culture, families now live in separate apartments and flats. The communal living that was part of the traditional practice is fast disappearing, except in the rural areas. The popular saying "Èni kan níí bímọ̀,

gbogbo ayé ní háa tó ọ (it's only one person that gives birth to a child but everybody helps to train him) is no longer obtainable. Such was the living pattern of the Yorúbá before the Western culture was imbibed and the "me and my immediate family" syndrome took its place. Today, everyone minds his/her own business and cares less about what happens to the next person, as long as all is well with him/her. You dare not beat somebody else's child otherwise you incur his/her wrath.

3.2.2. Co-wife rivalry in the family system

Jealousy has been the bane of polygamy and Ọlábímtán authenticates it in *Kékeré Èkùn*. Ọlábímtán writes about the rivalry between iyá Àlàbí and Àdùfẹ; both are Bádẹjọ's wives. In the course of their rivalry, Àdùfẹ, the younger wife, makes several attempts to send Àlàbí, the son of her co-wife, to the world beyond. But each attempt is foiled. She remains undaunted until she pays dearly for her evil machinations. Àdùfẹ plans to kill Àlàbí by poisoning his food when she goes to pay Àlàbí a visit at Ìlòkò after a quarrel with iyá Àlàbí:

Àlàbí ni: 'Nígbàtí iyàwó wá sódó mi ní Ìlòkò, ará fu mí, mo tú àpò rẹ mo há àdó yí, mo sì mú u pamó. Kí ng tó tú àpò yí ní àsàlẹ ọjó náà, ó ní, òn ni ó gbọdò se ọúnjẹ mi ng kò sì kò fún u. Sùgbón nígbàtí a jẹun tán mo rí i pé inú rẹ kò dùn mọ, ó sì bérésí bá mi jà títí ó fi wá s'ílẹ. Lẹhìn tí ó kúrò ní Ìlòkò mo ra adìẹ kan mo sì fi diẹ nínú ẹtù inú àdó náà sí ọúnjẹ adìẹ yí. mo fún u jẹ. Kò pé lẹhìn náà adìẹ náà kú, ẹrù sì bà mí.'

(o. i. 118)

Àlàbí says: 'When the new wife came to visit me at Ìlòkò, I was suspicious, so I searched her luggage only to find this little gourd, I hid it. Before I searched her bag that evening, she insisted on preparing my dinner and I did not decline. But, after dinner, I observed that she was no longer cheerful, and she began to quarrel with me until she returned home. After she left Ìlòkò, I procured a fowl and I added a little of the powdery substance in the tiny gourd to its food. Shortly after, the fowl died, and I was scared.

A tún rí bí Àdùfẹ ẹ lọ sí ọdọ Ràìmì láti ẹ ọ̀ògùn lẹhìn ìgbà tí onísẹ̀gùn rẹ kú. Ó bẹ Ràìmì kí ó ẹ egbòògì tí òn yìò fi fa ọkàn Bádẹjọ mọra àti ẹyí tí òn yìò fi pa Àlàbí.

(o. i. 130)

We also had an occasion, when Àdùfẹ went to Ràìmì the herbalist to prepare some charms for her, after the death of her former herbalist. She begged him to prepare a charm for her that would make Bádẹjọ have passion for her and another charm that she would use to eliminate Àlàbí.

Àdùfẹ wants Àlàbí dead by all means because she sees him as a threat to her relationship with Bádẹjọ. She also wants to hit back at Ìyá Àlàbí, so that Bádẹjọ will be left with only Àjàyí, her toddler son. However, all the attempts made by Àdùfẹ to kill Àlàbí proved abortive, and later boomeranged. In another attempt to eliminate Àlàbí, Olábímtán writes:

Sìgbón nígbàtí ilẹ̀ ojó sátidé mó, gégé bí eto, egbògi náà sí sẹ́, sìgbón kì ísẹ̀ Àlàbí l'ó mú, ẹ̀lòmíran ní ó mú lọ. Bádẹjọ àtí Àdùfẹ̀ jókòó síwájú ilẹ̀, nwón ònsòrò l'òrísírísí, nwón ònsíré, àtí àbúrò Àdùfẹ̀ tí ó wá kí wọn. Ní àkókò yí, Àjàyí tí ònrákò, ó sì ò rá káákírí inú ilẹ̀. Lẹ́hìn hí isẹ́jú méwǎ tí o tí rá kúrò lódò wọn, ó rá padà, gbogbo ẹnu rẹ̀ sí dídú fún etú. Òkèèrè ní àbúrò Àdùfẹ̀ tí rí ẹnu Àjàyí tí ó sì kígbẹ̀ pé 'kíní omọ̀ yí fí sẹnu?' Bì Ìyá rẹ̀ tí rí ò, ó sáré dídẹ̀, o gbá guuru mó o, ó gbé e, ó wo ẹnu rẹ̀, ó sì kígbẹ̀ tòò, ó ní 'Mo gbé o! Yèèpà! Omọ̀ yí p'ara rẹ̀!' Ó tún jù ú silẹ̀, ó sáré jáde, ó sì doríkọ̀ ilẹ̀ Ràìmì bóyá yìò ní ẹ̀rò. Ó tí gbàgbé pé èyí tí kò ní ẹ̀rò ní ọ̀n ẹ.

(o. i. 140-42)

On Saturday morning, the medicine worked as planned, but it did not kill Àlàbí, but someone else. Bádẹjọ and Àdùfẹ were seated in the front of the house, they were discussing various issues, including Àdùfẹ's sibling, who had come to visit them. Àjàyí had started to crawl at this time, and he crawled around the house. After about ten minutes that he had left their vicinity, he crawled back, and his mouth was full of a black powdery substance. Àdùfẹ's sibling observed this from afar and raised alarm thus 'What has this child put in his mouth?' As his mother saw it, she quickly carried him, looked at his mouth and shouted. She cried out: 'I am in a precarious situation! Yeh! This child has killed himself!' She put him down and ran out to Ràìmì's house in anticipation that she would get its antidote. She had forgotten that she requested for medicine that would have no antidote.

Perhaps, the havoc being perpetrated in polygamy is responsible for why Christianity flourished among the Yorùbá, to the detriment of traditional religions. Christianity does not encourage polygamy; it is 'one man, one wife'. Co-wives rivalry was so rampant, and co-wives tried to outwit one another in their evil deeds. In *Ìrèké Oníbùdò*, Ifẹpínyà practises her wickedness against her co-wife.

Ó ghé ògùn yī wá sí ilé lójó tí ó ǵ é, ní irèti àti lọ bù ú sí iyá Ìfèpàdè lára nìghàti onìòhùn bá sùn. Ó ghé ògùn yī sí pèpè lókè àjà, ó fì èhin lé ilé kò sí mọ pé òn lè sùn lọ. Bí ó ti fì èhin lé ilé tán ó sùn lọ. Nìghàti ó dì òru, ológhò tí ó ñsá kiri òkè aja kọlu igò ògùn nā, ó yī lulè, ghogbo ògùn inú rẹ sí dà lè e lóri, nìghàti ilé fì mā mọ. obìnrin nā dì adètè, ìka ọwó rẹ sí ti hère sí gé. (o. i. 100-107).

She brought the medicinal concoction home the day it was prepared for her in anticipation of pouring it on Ìfèpàdè's mother in her sleep. She placed the concoction on a shelf in the ceiling. She laid down, oblivious of the fact that she could fall asleep. As she laid down, she fell asleep. In the dead of the night, a cat that was moving around the ceiling hit the bottle in which the concoction was, the bottle fell down and its contents poured on her. Before dawn, the woman had become a leper, her fingers had also sbegun to fall off.

Such is the wickedness that co-wives mete out to one another. It is hard to find a mother who would wholeheartedly give her consent for her daughter to marry into a polygamous home, nor for her son to marry more than a wife. This is because peace eludes this type of family, while confusion, trouble and suspicion are the norm.

In the same novel, Ìfèpàdè's mother chastises Ìrèké-Oníbùdó, when he pays her a visit to meet her acquaintance.

Ìyá Ìfèpàdè pè àkiyèsì Ìrèké Oníbùdó sí ọrọ̀ yìi nìghà tí ó ñ gbèrò láti fì Ìfèpàdè ǵ aya. Ó lọ bá yìi: "Sugbón kiní kan ni mo fé sọ fún ọ kí ó tó di pé ọràn nā bèrè, nkò fé kí o ní obìnrin mīràn pèlú ọmọ mi o, nítorí bí èmi pāpā ti wà nínú ilé yī pèlú, mo mọ ñkan tí ọjú mi ñrí lówó àwọn orogún, bí kò bá sí àwọn ọmọ mi tí mo dúró tí ni, ñbá ti kọ bàbá wọn silẹ. Nítorínà, fì eléyī sí ọkàn o, òn ni àkòhí mi. Bí orogún bá ñfì ọjú rérīn, oró ejò mbe ni òkàn àiyà wọn". (o. i. 85).

Ìfèpàdè's mother called the attention of Ìrèké-Oníbùdó to this issue, when he proposed to take Ìfèpàdè as a wife. She says: "But, there is one thing I intend to say to you before the relationship begins in earnest. I don't want you to have another woman with my daughter, because as I am married into this family, I know the kind of things I experience from my co-wives. If not for the sake of my children, for whom I remain in the marriage, I would have left their father. So, bear this in mind, she is my first born child. If co-wives smile at you, there is venom in their hearts.

Ifẹ̀pàdẹ̀' s mother speaks out of experience: co-wives can be deadly. In an attempt to compete for the favour and attention of the husband, co-wives go to any length, so as to become the husband's favourite. This rivalry is also extended to the children, as co-wives, in a bid to outwit one another also wish that their children should be the favourite of their father and also for them to excel and be the most successful among all the children of their father. This rivalry sometimes leads to the death of the children, co-wives and at times, their husband. In *Ògbójú Ode ninú Ighó Irúnmalẹ̀*, Fágúnwà writes about co-wives rivalry:

Ní àkókò igbàkan, omọ mės̄ān ni bàbá mi bí, èmi sì ni àgbà gbogbo wọ̀n: Ìyàwó mērin ni ó ní pẹ̀lú, iyá mi sì ni iyálé gbogbo wọ̀n. Ọ̀n bí omọ mērin, iyàwó tí ó tẹ̀lẹ̀ e bí mēta, èkẹta bí méjì, èkẹrin kò tilẹ̀ bí rárá. Ó ẹ̀ ní ojó kan, iyá mi àti òkan nínú àwọ̀n iyàwó wọ̀nyi jà nwọ̀n sì kó ejó nǎ lọ sí ọ̀dọ̀ bàbá mi, ọ̀n sì dá iyá mi lẹ̀bi, èyítí ó mú kí iyá mi binú púpọ̀, ó sì pinnu láti gbẹ̀san. Ó bẹ̀rẹ̀sí ihu iwà àjé rẹ̀ tóbè lí ó pa omọ méjọ nínú àwọ̀n omọ bàbá mi, ó sì pa iyàwó mēta kí ọ̀dún nǎ tó parí. Ó wá jẹ̀ pé ó ku èmi nìkan gégé bí omọ, ó sì ku ọ̀n nìkan gégé bí iyàwó. (o. i. 2)

A little while ago, my father had nine children, and I was the eldest of them all: He had four wives and my mother was the first wife, she had four children, his second wife had three children, the third wife had two children while the fourth (last) wife had no children. One day, my mother and one of the wives had a quarrel. They reported the incident to my father, who blamed my mother. My mother was very angry and she decided to revenge. She began to practise her witchcraft to the extent that she killed eight of my father's children. She also killed three of my father's wives before the end of that year, thus leaving only her, as my father's wife, and me, as my father's only child.

This confirms the claim of Ifá that "*Òrìsà jẹ̀ n pé méjì ohìnrin kò démí*". (A woman's wish to have a co-wife is nothing but hypocrisy). After the co-wives' evil plans to bring Ìrèké-Oníbùdó into disrepute before Ifẹ̀pàdẹ̀' s father is aborted. Ìrèké sends for Ifẹ̀pàdẹ̀ to tell his own side of the story, but the co-wives do not allow the messenger to see Ifẹ̀pàdẹ̀. Among the havocs that are caused by rivalry is the backwardness that Ìrèké-Oníbùdó experiences in his frantic effort to see Ifẹ̀pàdẹ̀ which her mother's co-wives thwart.

Mo ránsé sí i ní ojó kẹta pé kí ó wá, sùgbón àwọ̀n orogún

iyá rẹ̀ tó wà ní idí gbogbo ríkísí nā kò jẹ́kí ẹ̀nítí mo rán rí í.

(o. i. 89)

I sent for her on the third day, but her mother's co-wives that were behind the conspiracy prevented my messenger from seeing her.

Ìrèké-Oníbùdó later laments:

Ìwọ ọ̀rẹ̀ mi, inú àwọn orogún dúdú ju ẹ̀dú, ó sọ̀kùnkùn bí ọ̀gànjọ̀ ọ̀ru, igèdegèle ní m̀bẹ̀ ní inú wọ̀n...

(o. i. 100)

My friend, the thought of co-wives is blacker than the charcoal, it is darker than midnight, there is plenty of dregs inside them...

In *Omọ̀ Òkú Ọ̀run*, Ọ̀dúnjọ̀ captures the brutality of co-rivals. Though Àdió, who is bàbá Wálé, is not legally married to Àbèké, who is iyá Wálé's friend, Àbèké takes over her friend's home including her bed. During the process, she ill-treats Wálé:

'Wálé! Wálé!! Wálé!!!' Omọ̀ orogún rẹ̀ ní ó ń pè yẹ̀n... 'Ma-a-a', Wálé ní ó ń dàhùn bẹ̀è láti ẹ̀hìnkùlẹ̀, ó sì ń sàré hò lésè kan nàà sínù pàlò ní ibi tí Àbèké gbé wà. 'Mà-à ma-a ẹ̀nu rẹ̀. Níbo ní olórí burúkú rẹ̀ tí ghà lẹ̀ láti ọ̀nì tí mo tí ń pè ẹ̀ tí ó kò dàhùn? Oníranù omọ̀!' Àbèké ní ó ń fì ibinù bú Wálé hẹ̀è... ẹ̀mi ní yí mà-à, ata tí ẹ̀ ní kí ng lẹ̀ sílẹ̀ ní mo ń lẹ̀ ní ẹ̀hìnkùlẹ̀ mà-à...

Ata kọ, ata ni! Ẹ wo ẹ̀yí tí mo tí ń pè látòní tí ọ̀nì ata ní ọ̀n òn lẹ̀. Oníranù omọ̀! Kí ẹ̀ni tí ó pe ara rẹ̀ ní bàbá fún ẹ̀ sàù dé. Ẹ̀mi kò ní gha gbogho pàlapàla tí ó ń sẹ̀ wọ̀nyẹ̀n fún ẹ̀ mó. Ẹ̀mi sá kọ̀ ní mo ní kí iyá tó bí ẹ̀ kú kẹ̀... gbogho ẹ̀yí tí ẹ̀ni ń pe ara rẹ̀ ní iyá fún ẹ̀ tí ń sẹ̀ wọ̀nyẹ̀n, àkókò tó nísinsìnyí tí màá gbèsan lára rẹ̀...

(o. i. 1-2).

'Wálé! Wálé!! Wálé!!!' She called out to her co-wife's daughter... 'Ma-a-a', Wálé responded from the backyard and she ran into the parlour where Àbèké was. 'Ma-ma', damn you. 'Where have you, unfortunate child, been, since I have been calling you, and you refused to respond? Useless girl!' Àbèké angrily abuses Wálé... 'Here I am, ma, I am grinding the pepper that you asked me to grind at the backyard ma-aa'. What pepper! See somebody I have been calling long ago, who said she had been grinding pepper. You loafer! Let the one who calls himself your father arrive. I will not tolerate all this nonsense from you any longer. After all, I am not the one who asked your mother to die... all the things that your mother had done, it is now time that I will take my revenge from you...

This is a clear case of child abuse and child labour. Àbèkè visits her wrath and anger on Wálé. She does this to take her own pound of flesh from Wálé, the daughter of ìyá Wálé. The co-wife visits her anger on an innocent child who is not part of the rivalry. Such is the treatment meted out to children by step-mothers. Rivalry wrecks a lot of havoc on the family. Considering this, one is tempted to pronounce polygamy as a curse, rather than a blessing, to the family.

3.2.3. Ethics and values

Dòpámú and Alana (2004:155) define ethics and values as “the science of morality of human acts. It is the science which deals with morals, moral rules or principles of behaviour that govern people or society”. Noonan (cited in Dòpámú and Alana 2004) says “Morality itself is the goodness or the badness, the rightness or the wrongness of human acts”.

Another negative effect of postcolonialism is change in social values. In pre-colonial days, the Yorùbá valued and cherished self respect, honour and integrity. In contemporary days, the status-quo has changed. People are now assessed based on material wealth, the number of houses he has built, the number of automobiles in his fleet of cars, and, perhaps, the more expensive and flashy the car he rides. This is misplacement of priority, because how fat a man’s bank account is should not be a yardstick for assessing him in the society. Rather, a man’s integrity, honour, values and dignity, especially, his contribution to the progress, development and advancement of his society and humanity, in general, should be the yardstick with which his success and accomplishment is measured.

Before the period under discussion, the Yorùbá used to ask questions about the source of wealth of their people. Hence, the proverb “*Ọmọ yín kò ghà àgbàfọ, ó n kó aṣọ wálé, ẹ rí ojú olè, ẹ kò mú un*” (your child is not a launderer, yet he brings clothes home, you have seen a thief but you refuse to apprehend him). The practice of making enquiries about the source of a man’s wealth is no longer in vogue. Rather, the trend now is “*Ọmọ tó mú owó wá ilé nì òbí rẹ má a yín*”, (it is the child who brings money home that the parent will praise). Due to this, the youths of

today are involved in various kinds of criminal activities, including the "get-rich-quickly syndrome", that is, they do anything in order to get rich. Dòpámú and Alana (2004:179) hold the view that:

Today, many people are in haste. They want to get rich quickly. Such impatience is condemned by the Yorùbá. Since impatience ultimately leads to disappointment.

Dòpámú and Alana also explain that there is every likelihood that people who are impatient, who anticipate events, and who wish to achieve the good things of life in haste will always engage in endless and fruitless struggles to achieve the impossible. They further says:

They may engage in actions that border on indiscipline such as guile, deceitfulness, craftiness (*àrékérekè*) hypocrisy, dishonesty, trickery (*ogbónkògbón*) etcetera.

(p 171)

These negative practices include stealing, armed-robbery and, most recently, Internet fraud, popularly known as "yahoo-yahoo" in the youth parlance. This practice has further dented the image of the country in the global community. If every parent had stuck to the traditional ways of bringing up children, by giving children thorough monitoring, a lot of fraudulent activities and involvement in the "get-rich-quickly" syndrome and advanced free fraud would have been checked.

Today, teenagers want to ride exotic cars; they want to wear the most expensive and sophisticated clothes; they want to go on holidays abroad, live in an expensive and exotic apartment, the type their parents and grandparents have never dreamt of. This fast-lane life is alien to our cultural practices. The youths are not alone in this practice: adults too are involved. The act of kidnapping of people, especially children, for money rituals has become so rampant in the society. These acts thrive because people no longer ask questions as to the source of wealth of their family members. All they are interested in is to celebrate their son's arrival into the millionaire fold. Although money is essential for acquisition of other needed things, money on its own cannot add value to life. It is a means to an end and not an end in itself. In *Ìrèkè Oníbùdó*, Fágúnwà writes:

*Lójó kejì, níghà tí mo jí ebi ñ pa mí, ògèdè kò sí wù mí í je,
ojó nàà ní mo mò pé iyí owó wà lótò, iyí oúnjẹ sí wà lótò*

*pélú. Mo ghé owó lè orí, sùghón n kò rí ñkan fì rà, hée ni
n kò lè sọ owó di oinje... (o. i. 72)*

When I woke up the next day, I was hungry. banana did not appeal to me. That was the day I realized that money has its own value while food also has its own value. I put money on my head but I did not find anything to buy with the money, and I could not turn money to food...

In *Ìrìnkèrindò Níní Igbó Elégbèje*, during Ìrèké's dream of a sojourn into the world beyond, he is made to witness an event that occurs as a result of money. The event depicts the evil that may come as a result of the love of money among men. The excerpt below captures this:

Kò pé púpò tí mo ñwò ilẹ̀ bá yí tí mo rí okùnrin arúgbó kan tí ó wá láti wé létí odò nā, ó ghé àpò owó kan lówó. Nighàtí ó wé tán, ó lọ. ó gbàgbé àpò owó nā silẹ̀... Ibití ó sì tí ñwé ní ẹnítí ó kọ́ gbé owó nā wá tí ó gbàgbé rẹ̀ dé pé lú ihon, ó rí arúgbó tí ó tí ó ñwé, ó bèrè owó lówó rẹ̀. onítòhún sì wí fún un pé òn kò rí ñkan tí ó jé owó nighàtí òn dé odò. Okùnrin yí kò gbàá gbó. óní irọ́ ni, wéré ó yìnhon lù ú, ó bá tirè lọ... (o. i. 9)

It was not long after I had started looking at the ground that I saw an old man, who came to bathe in the stream, he carried a bag of money in his hand. After his bathe, he left and forgot the bag of money behind... As he was bathing, the one who initially brought the money and forgot it arrived with a gun, he saw the old man bathing, asked him for the money, and the old man replied that he didn't see anything like money when he got to the stream. This man didn't believe him, and said it was a lie, quickly, he shot him and went on his way...

This portrays that the love of money is the root of all evil as it has led to the murder of the man in the above instance. This is a common trend in the post-colonial era. Also, in *Ìrìnkèrindò Níní Igbó Elégbèje*, Fágúnwà takes his readers on a trip to *Ọ̀run Àpádi* (Hell fire), where the devil himself heads his government. The hunters are taken to the devil, which takes them on a tour round his palace and shows them *Pàkúté èsù*, (the devil's trap).

Ìgbàtí a dé Pàkúté èsù yí ñkan tí ó kọ́ fì hàn á ni owó gòlù tí ó pọ́ tí ó pupa dé dé tí ó n dán yinrin yinrin. Nwón kó owó nā sínú ibìkan bá yí tí ó dàbí ilẹ̀ tí ènià kàn fún ẹ̀yẹ, sùghón lẹ̀hìn owó nāà ni a rí ẹ̀jò ọkà tí ó ká jọ tí ó ghé ẹnu sókè hàrìhà. Èsù

*tóka sí, ó wípé. 'ìghàtí mo bá wá sí aiyé tí mo fì omọ ènià mí
owó olówó, tí kii ṣe tiwon, mwon kò nmò pé ejò oká ni àwọn tí
owó bọ lẹnu'...* (o. i. 67).

When we got to the devil's trap, the first thing he showed us was golden coins which were enormous, shining red, and also glittering. They put the money in a place that looked like a house built for birds, behind the money was a cobra that folded itself in a ring and opened its mouth wide opened. The devil pointed to it and said, 'when I come to the world and tempt men to steal money which does not belong to them, they are ignorant of the fact that they are dipping their hands into the mouth of a cobra'...

In the extract above, Fágúnwà likens the love of money and stealing of money to dipping one's hands into the mouth of a cobra. This spells doom and death for the culprit. The devil himself admits that he tempts people to steal money. This is a big moral lesson for humanity. Man should avoid the love of money. Money is good but it can also be a source of evil. It is disheartening that more people care about money and material wealth acquisition today more than ever before. The society no longer cherishes societal norms, values and cultural heritage. What is obtainable today is unsaturated acquisition of money, to the detriment of moral standards. People seem to care less about how they make wealth.

3.2.4. Ethics within the family organization

In *Àyànmọ*, we see modernity being bastardized in Jọké (the woman Àlàbí married abroad). She is used to smoking cigarettes, whereas the most an old woman will do is to snuff tobacco powder that is, "ááṣì" or "tábà". Jọké, as ostentatious as she is, adorns the most seductive outfits. She does not kneel to greet anyone. These actions are unheard of among the Yorùbá; in fact, they are taboos.

The issue of a traditional Yorùbá woman calling her husband by name is a result of civilization and sophistication brought about by the association of the Yorùbá with the Westerners. This is contrary to orthodox Yoruba practice as wives are expected to use pet names in addressing their husbands or husband's family members. According to one of our informants, a bride used to call her groom "Bùràdà" or refers to him by saying "È égbṛ" that is (listen to me), "Olówó orí mí"

(one who owns me) or "*Baálé mí*" (my husband). Much later, when the woman had spent many years in her matrimonial home, she would call her husband "*Baále mí*" (my husband), or "*Bàba wa*" (our father). This is to show respect and courtesy to the husband so it was absurd that a woman should call her husband by name. This also extended even to the baby born about an hour before the new bride is married into the family. The bride would not call him by name. Jòkè's failure to do this is responsible for why Àlàbí's parents do not like her.

Dòpámú and Alana (2004:155) remark that younger ones must not call their elders by name, as a wife must not call her husband by name. A wife even dare not call the younger brothers and sisters of her husband born before her marriage into the family by their names. This idea is borne out of the fact that children born before her marriage are regarded as being seniors to her. She may give male children such names as "*Èniáfé*", "*Oríolówó*", "*Fáàrípò*", "*Akòwé*", "*Bòdá Iléewé*", "*Eyínáfé*", "*Oko Ìyàwó*", "*Awoşomáròde*", "*Mánjã*" while the female members of the family may be given such names as "*Èjíníwúrã*", "*Èjìwùmí*", "*Ayalóyà*", "*Sisi Iléewé*", "*Olójúarédè*", "*Òwúrúbútú*", "*Ìdílèkè*", "*Ayílukò*", "*Ìbàdiàrán*", "*Gèlèòdùn*". But Jòkè openly calls Àlàbí by his name. This does not go down well with his parents, who see her as an uncultured and ill-mannered lady (*Àyànmo*, p 106-108). This is further reflected in some Yorùbá pithy sayings:

Ọyájú obìnrin tí ñ pe oko lóókò

An arrogant woman who calls her husband by name...

Aşa obìnrin tí ñ pe oko lóókò

A rude woman who calls her husband by name...

The idea of husband name-calling, which is a fallout of postcolonialism and a Western concept, has become a very common practice among the educated metropolitan female elites today.

Another fallout of postcolonialism is the incursion of foreign religions, that is, Christianity and Islam, into the Yorùbá nation. As a result of these foreign religions and cultures, religious titles have become a common phenomenon. Titles such as Pastor, Alfa, Reverend, Alhaji, J.P, Elder, Deacon, Apostle, et cetera,

become common prefixes to traditional Yorùbá names. As a result of this, some women address their husband with the above mentioned titles.

Similarly, postcolonialism reflects in political institution, where the political titles of "Excellency" is employed to address the president and state governors; "chairman" to address local government chairmen. "Honourable", for House of Representative and State Assembly Members. These titles are used by the wives of such political officers to address them. The craze for chieftaincy titles, both traditional and honorary, also afforded wives of such title holders the opportunity to address their husbands as Chief.

Children are not left out of this practice. They refer to their mothers as "mummy", "mumsie", "mum" and to their fathers as "daddy", "popsie", "old-man" and so on. An instance is found in *Ọmọ Ọkú Ọrun*, where Adùn's mother (Ìyá Adùn) refers to Kúnlé's mother (Màmá Kúnlé) as *Mámì wa*; (a word which is derived from the English name for mother "mummy"). Even though they are friends, she chooses to use the name children use to refer to mother. Children also acknowledge their parents' call and reply by the word "sir" (*sa-a-a*) or "ma" (*ma-a*). In *Ọmọ Ọkú Ọrun*, Wálé answers her father's call with "sir" (*sa-a-a*).

Married women are also fond of referring to one another as "mrs" (*mìsìsì*) as found in *Ọmọ Ọkú Ọrun*, where Kúnlé's mother (Màmá Kúnlé) refers to Adùn's mother (Ìyá Adùn) as such. In the same text, the court clerk tells the audience that:

...*Obìnrin ni ó n jé mìsìsì, kábíyèsí.* (o. i. 36)

...It is a woman that is referred to as Mrs, my lord.

In *Jé ng lò'gba tẹmi*, *Kẹkeré Ekùn* and *Àyànmọ*, the clergymen in the texts are addressed as *Àlùfáà*. In *Àyànmọ*, Jọké is addressed as 'Lawyer' (*Lóyà*) her professional name. In the same text, *Àlàbí* is referred to as 'Doctor' (*Dókítà*) his professional name. In *Ìjámhá Sílú*, *Àjùwòn* uses the title 'Doctor' (*Dókítà*) as the nomenclature of the medical personnel who is to conduct a medical test on him.

As a result of civilization, Christianity, Islam and sophistication, some women today address their husbands as "love", "mine", "honey", "my dear", "darling", "angel", "my husband", "sweetheart", "soulmate" and so on. All these

are strange to the orthodox Yorùbá culture. The most that the older women in Yorùbá society would do is to call their husband by their child's name, for example, Bàba Qláyíwọlá, Bàba Qmótóyòsí, Bàba Tóyìn, Bàba Jídé, and so forth.

3.3. Courtesy

Roget's II, *The New Thesaurus* defines courtesy as a well mannered behaviour toward others, courteous acts are the acts that contribute to the smoothness and ease in dealings, and social relationships. Actions like exchange of pleasantries, politeness and acts of generosity show courtesy. The Yorùbá are a highly respectful and courteous people. In Yorùbá culture, younger people express respect to the older members of the society. The younger ones greet the older members first and respectfully too. The female kneels down to greet older members while the male prostrates himself. The plural form of pronoun is used to refer to an older person in conversation. Hence, the use of *Eyin* (plural 'You') and *Won* (they, third person plural form) to refer to an elder person. (See Dopamu and Alana 2004).

The younger one offers his seat to an elder person regardless of relationships between them. In a bus or a social gathering, a younger person vacates his seat for elderly person, even in a social gathering. It is a sign of disrespect on the part of a younger person to walk without any load, while an elderly person carries a load. The Yorùbá show appreciation for favours rendered to them as well. Similarly, they generously entertain visitors, host guests and welcome strangers in their folds and homes and extend a hand of love and friendship to people. Dòpámú and Alana (2004:165) succinctly capture this:

It is the duty of the young to first greet the elder. Children are not expected to utter a word in self defence, when they are reprimanded or blamed by elders for wrong doing. Such reprimands are meant to serve as corrections which would change the life of such erring children for the better. The elders take this responsibility with all seriousness...

The Yorùbá has greetings for sundry occasion (sic), time of the actions, work, circumstance, season etc. There is hardly any human endeavour that the Yorùbá does (sic) not have a greeting for.

The younger Yorùbá looks up to the elderly ones for advice and counsel. In *Ó Le Kú*, Àjàní seeks Bòdé's, his elder brother's, counsel concerning his choice of wife.

*Nìghà tó di alé ojó kàn: Àjàní lo sí ilé wọn, ó bú èghón rẹ
'Bòdè nílẹ̀. 'Bòdè jù ù lọ púpọ̀. ó sì máa n' gba ọ̀pẹ̀lọ̀pọ̀
imọ̀ràn l'awó rẹ̀.*

(o. i. 37)

That evening, Àjàní went to their house. He met his elder brother, 'Bòdè at home. ' Bòdè is much older than he is. He usually seeks his counsel.

The fact that Ajani goes to seek his elder brother's counsel reveal that he holds him in high esteem and respect his counsel as a way of showing courtesy to one's elder. The Yorùbá in the post-colonial times use 'àntí' to refer to an elder sister and 'bùròdá' to refer to an elder brother, hitherto, the word 'egbón mí' was used to indicate respect to the elderly. In *Ogún Omodé*, Isòlá uses Fọlá to illustrate this:

Fọlá dàgbà jù wá lọ púpọ̀ púpọ̀, bùròdá ní a sì máa n' pè é...

(o. i. 3)

Fọlá is much older than us, so we usually call him brother...

In *Ó Le Kú*, when Àjàní visits Àsàké in her house, he sends Àsàké's housemaid to buy him two bottles of stout. The girl shows courtesy and respect in referring to Àjàní, when Àsàké asks the housegirl; *Ta ló rán ọ l'ótí?* (Who sent you to buy drink?). The housegirl replies; *Àwọn bùròdá ní* (It is brother). Àsàké asks again: *Bùròdá wo?* (Which brother?) and the girl responds: *Wón wà ní pálo* (He is in the parlour). (p 44). The housegirl did not mention Àjàní's name out of respect and courtesy. It is a sign of disrespect and lack of home training for a younger one to mention or call an older person by name. Also in *Ó Le Kú*, Lọlá expresses courtesy to 'Dòtun by introducing Dòtun and Àjàní to each other when he visits her in her room and meets Àjàní with.

*Lọlá kò tilẹ̀ mira, ó kí Dòtun káàbọ̀. Dòtun sì dá a lóhùn gán-
ín, Lọlá sì fì Àjàní àti 'Dòtun han ara wọn. Ó ní, 'Àjàní nìyí,
Dòtun nìyẹn'. Àjàní dídè ó nawó sí Dòtun, ... Ó bọwó náà. (o. i. 29-30)*

Lọlá did not move, she welcomed Dòtun. Dòtun replied her sharply, while Lọlá introduced Àjàní and 'Dòtun. She said 'This is Àjàní, that is Dòtun'. Àjàní got up and extended his hand to Dòtun... Dòtun shook him.

Àjàní and Dòtun greeted each other this way because they are age-mates and contemporaries, if they were not age-mates the younger out of the two would have prostrated to the other in the traditional Yoruba society. The act of prostrating as a means of showing courtesy is portrayed when Àjàní goes to meet Ọgbéni Àjàsá. Bàbá Kékeré's friend who is to solicit for him concerning his relationship with Àsàké, what happens is described below:

*Bi Àjàní àti Àsàké ti wólé, wón kí bàbá. Àjàní dọhálẹ̀ tán
ghalaja... Àsàké náù kúnlẹ̀ húrúhúrú. bàbá kí wón dáadáa.
Wón jòkòò lóri àga, wón se, jẹ́... (o. i. 87).*

As Àjàní and Àsàké came in, they greeted father. Àjàní prostrated himself fully... Àsàké also knelt down humbly. Father greeted them warmly. They sat on chairs, and were calm...

Courtesy is shown by Ajani to Mr. Àjàsá. Bàbá Kékeré's friend as a mark of respect that is associated with traditional Yoruba culture. When Şadé invites Àjàní to her house for a dinner to mark her twenty-first birthday, Şadé's family receives and welcomes him warmly.

*...Wón kii tifétifé, tọyàyà-tọyàyà. Àsè tí à n wí yii ga. Kò sí
orísirísi oúnjẹ tí kò pé síhè tán. (o. i. 106).*

They greeted him with love and cheerfulness. The entertainment was excellent. There was no delicacy that was not served there.

In *Ogún Omódé*, Ìsòlá depicts respect for the elderly and contentment on the part of children so invited to join in a meal by their declining and expressing appreciation rather than behaving like gluttonous children:

*A bá Dọlápọ̀ àti bàbá rẹ̀ tí wón n jẹun lówó. Bàbá rẹ̀ ní kí
a wáá jẹun, gbogbo wa, sí sọ pé, a ti yó. (o. i. 1).*

Dọlápọ̀ and his father were eating then. His father invited us to join them in the meal. We all replied that we were already full.

On an occasion, after 'Délódún has played one of his pranks, he runs to his grandmother's place to avoid being beaten.

*Mo di mó iyá àgbà, mo sì n sunkún èké. Iyá àgbà gha ọré
lówó iyá mi, ó ní kí n múa báa lọ sílé àti pé kò gbọdọ̀ nà mí.
(o. i. 9)*

I entwined myself to grandmother and cried falsely, grandmother seized the cane my mother held, and asked me to go back home, and that she must not beat me.

It is a way of showing courtesy to the elders in Yorùbáland, that once a child runs for refuge to an elderly person's place and hugs him or her, his mother, father or whoever pursues the child must not beat the child in the grip of the elder. Moreover, once an elder has chastised an erring child and asked the one who pursues him to pardon this child; nothing must be done to such a child.

A younger one shows respect to the elder in the way he/she answers the call of the elder. For example, when Àbèké calls Wálé, in *Omọ̀ Òkú Ọ̀run*, saying Wálé! Wálé!! Wálé!!!, Wálé responds by saying Ma-a-a! Ma-a-a' is equivalent of the 'ma' in English, when a female elder calls, and 'saa' is the same with the lexical item 'sir' in English. When Àdió calls Wálé, Wálé replies him this way:

Sa-a-a! Wálé ni ó n dá bàbá rẹ̀ lóhùn bẹ̀ẹ̀ láti èhìn òde, ó sì sáré wọ̀ ilé, ó kó ọ̀wọ̀ sẹ̀hìn bí ó ti dúró níwájú bàbá rẹ̀
(o. i. 29)

Sir! Wálé replied her father thus from the backyard, as she ran into the house, she put her arms behind her as she stood before her father.

Wálé's posture is meant to show ultimate respect to her father. The use of 'sir' and 'ma' though borrowed from the English language and culture, is synonymous with courtesy and respect in contemporary Yoruba society, whereas in the orthodox Yoruba society, the response of a younger person to an elder's call was usually by the expression 'ooo!' In *Omọ̀ Òkú Ọ̀run*, Ìyá Kúnlé, who is one of Àbèké's friends, shows much respect to Wálé's father on his return from work.

*Màmá Kúnlé dide lẹ́sẹ̀ kan láti lọ pàdẹ̀ bàbá Wálé, bí ó sì ti n sẹ̀sẹ̀ maa lọ sí ibi ẹ̀nu ọ̀nà ní bàbá Wálé pàápàá wọ̀ ilé...
'È káàbọ̀ sà-à. Sẹ̀ àlàáfíà ní ẹ̀ dé? È mà kú ìrìn o.' Màmá Kúnlé ni ó na ọ̀wọ̀ gbà àkẹ̀tẹ̀ ọ̀wọ̀ rẹ̀ láti báa gbé wọ̀n wọ̀lé.*
(o. i. 18)

Màmá Kúnlé promptly rose to welcome bàbá Wálé. As she was going to receive him at the door, bàbá Wálé came in... 'You are welcome, sir, how was your journey? Welcome from your journey'. It was Màmá Kúnlé that collected the hat and the garment he held in his hands, and brought them into the house.

...E mà ɛ é púpò. E kú ilé. Ẹ àlàáfíà ní mo há yín? E ɛ é
gan-an ní. E kú à díró-tí...

(o. i. 19)

Thank you very much, how are you doing? Hope all is well?
Thank you very much. Thanks for your support...

There is a popular saying that respect is reciprocal, hence in orthodox and contemporary Yoruba society, a person to whom an act of courtesy has been given is expected to reciprocate in like-manner. This accounts for Wale's father's response to Iya Kunle above. Courtesy is essential in Yoruba culture as an adage says 'Eni tí kò kí ní kú ilé, pàdánù káàbò'. This means that one who does not show courtesy to one on his arrival, also would be denied a welcome courtesy.

In *Égún Alaré*, Ògúnníran tells us of what is likely to happen to a person who refuses to pay homage to his elders. Ojélàdé refuses to pay homage to the resident Egúngún guilds in a town where he performs. He is confident and relies so much on his charms and medicines. The elder resident Egúngún guild members chastise him, but he does not heed them; so they decide to teach him a lesson. This they do by rendering his charms impotent. After his metamorphosis to a crocodile, he is not able to metamorphose back to human.

*Nihin ni ó pidán dé tí àwọn àgbà ọjẹ tí ó wà ní ilú náà fi
ránṣẹ sí pé àwọn fẹ mọ idi tí kò fi bọdè kí ó tó wọlé... èyí
ni pé nwọn fẹ mọ idi tí kò fi júbà wọn kí ó tó máa ɣéré lọ.
Ẹgbón kàkà kí Ojélàdé túúbà, kí ó sì júbà wọn níbití onísé
gbé báa, iró, orin ni ó ní wọn dá pé...*

(o. i. 27-27)

On performing up to this point, the elder masquerade guilds resident in the town sent to him that they wanted to know why he did not pay homage to them before he started to perform. But, instead of apologising and duly paying homage to them, Ojélàdé as soon as he received the message, started calling their bluff...

In *Kádàrá àti Èghon rẹ*, Kádàrá extends courteous behaviour to his brother and father in spite of the family feud that was necessitated by Kádàrá's rejection of

crop farming in preference of animal husbandry. As his brother and father return from the farm, he runs to welcome them home:

*Bi Kádàrá tí rí wọn l'ókèrè ni ó sáré lọ pàdé wọn pèlú
òyàyà... (o. i. 24)*

As Kádàrá sees them from afar, he runs to welcome them cheerfully...

Kádàrá does not stop at that: he relieves his father of the yam load he is carrying:

*Imú ni Àgbégbèmi fì dǎa lóhùn kí ó tó gbé erù isù náà fún un...
Kò pé tí nwón wọ ilé ni Àkòbí tí hère fífó ikòkò tí ó fé fì se isù;
sùgbón Kádàrá tètè gba isù náà l'owó rẹ, ó sì yára báa bù ú sí
orí iná láì bikítà rárá nípa ojù burúkú tí Àkòbí fì n wò ó. Lèhìn
náà, ó gbé akèrègbè, ó lọ pón omi, ó tún fọ odó, àti àwọn àwo
silẹ, ó sì gbá gbogbo ilẹ ilẹ pèlú. Níghàtí isù náà sì jíná, Kádàrá
náà ni ó gún un ní iyán, lèhìn ìghà tí Àkòbí tí hóo sínú odó tán.
Sùgbón ó ya omọ náà l'enu pé bí wàhálà tí ó sè lóri iyán náà tí
pátó, bàbá rẹ àti èghòn rẹ kò fún un ní òkèlè kan jẹ rárá níni
rẹ, bée ni omitóro gbè tí wón fì jéé pèlú kò kán sí l'enu rárá...
Sibèsibè, Kádàrá kò jé kí ó hàn fún aiyé rí pé ara òni òun rárá...
(o. i. 24-26)*

Àgbégbèmi replied him snubishly before handing the load of yam to him. Soon after they entered into the house, Àkòbí began to wash the pot that he would use to cook yam, but Kádàrá quickly helped him and cooked the yam without giving a damn about the attitude of his brother. After that, he picked the pitcher and went to fetch water, he equally washed the mortar and plates in readiness for serving the meal. When the yam was done, Kádàrá was the one that pounded it after Àkòbí had put the yam in the mortar. But to the surprise of the boy, and despite the troubles he went through in preparing the food, his brother and father did not offer him a morsel nor was he offered a drop of the soup used in eating the pounded yam. Still, Kádàrá did not allow it to reflect in his expression.

Kádàrá does not only extend courtesy and respect to his father, he also extends these to his elder brother, by carrying out the domestic chores, which are the responsibility of the children in a Yorùbá home. The worst thing that can happen to a child is to partake in preparation of a meal in which he would not have a taste. However, Kádàrá is unperturbed: he does not let this deter him from carrying out his responsibility and extending courtesy to his brother and father.

3.4. Yorùbá traditional dressing

Neo-colonialism has succeeded in ensuring that African countries abandon their cultural norms and values to embrace the foreign ways of life in all areas. For instance, in dressing, the usual full Yorùbá regalia of Aṣọ-Òkè that was hitherto being used during wedding ceremonies has been abandoned for the European suits and wedding gowns. The use of traditional regalia has been limited to only the traditional aspect of the ceremony, with all other Yorùbá cultural attachments abandoned for the Westernized type. Moloje (2004:377) rightly notes this attitude thus:

Not too long ago, Yorùbá elite (sic) were expected to demonstrate the depth of their assimilation to European cultural values by the variety and quantity of European haberdashery in their possession.

The aim of these people is to showcase how much of European values, education, religion and system of government they have imbibed and acquired. This is in particular reference to some professions and professionals. For example, law practitioners have a dress code of white and black with a wig, while physicians and bankers also have dress codes of appearing in formal dressing of skirt-suits, trousers-suits or three-piece suits. The Europeans from whom they copied these are justified for dressing these ways, considering the climatic conditions in their countries. The Yorùbá who practise these aforementioned professions and others like them may adapt the traditional textile materials to sow these smart styles. The "àdìrẹ", "sányán", "ẹtù", "Àlàári" fabrics may be used to sow our own formal dresses. These fabrics are more suitable to the humid, tropical climate in Yorùbá land.

A way of identifying a people is by their culture; hence, material and non-material culture ought to serve the purpose of differentiating between one people and the other. The Yorùbá are very elegant, sophisticated and fashionable. A typical Yorùbá woman is dressed in her traditional wrapper and a round-necked loose blouse (*Író and Bùbá*) under which she wears underslips (*òghéko*) or underskirt (*yèri*). She plaits her hair or wears her hair in braids, after which she ties her "gèlè" (head gear) uses beaded jewellery, if she is from a royal family or is married into

one. She may use other jewels made of different ornaments of gold, silver, bronze, stones, among others. The result of all this is a well-blended, fashionable and decent woman of splendour and dignity in appearance. When a woman is thus dressed, the Yorùbá would commend her and say 'ó mà yááyì ó' (she looks good) (See Molye 2004).

Furthermore, Molye (2004) expresses that the varieties of clothes that are available to traditional Yorùbá men are more than those of the women. A Yorùbá man may choose to wear baggie trousers and knickers (*Ṣòkòtò àti kẹ̀nḡ*), a jumper and pencil trousers (*hùbá àti sọ́rọ́*), loose trousers and jumper (*ṣòkòtò àti hùbá*). He may wear 'ṣaparú', or 'agbádá' that is, the loose robe worn over 'hùbá and ṣòkòtò'. He may also choose to wear casual top (*dàńṣíkí*). The complete attire (*agbádá*) is the formal and complete dressing of a man; this is spiced up with a matching cap, such as, 'abẹti ajá'; which is a ceremonial and regal cap.

Royal fathers wear beads such as 'iyim' or 'sẹgi' as neck-chain and hand-chain. Eminent personalities use gold necklace as accessories to complete their dressing, while traditional chiefs and honourary chiefs also use beads and gold chains to complete their dressing. A Yorùbá man, thus dressed, distinguishes himself, as 'omoluwabi', that is, a decent and cultured gentleman. A Yorùbá adage says: "Írínisí ní isonilójò" (one's appearance tells a lot about one). Another says: "Bi a ti rìn, làá ko ní" (the way one is dressed determines how one will be addressed).

The fashion trend in the modern society is that some men wear long hair, some braid, weave or plait, perm, curl or even tint their hair. All these are female hair styles; besides, perming, jerry curls, hair extension and hair tinting are all foreign hair styles. It is disheartening that men wear these hair styles which are hitherto exclusive preserve of women. This trend is especially notable among men in show business, football stars and artistes, who use these as a form of identity in order to distinguish themselves from other artistes. However, in Yorùbá culture, among Ṣàngó's (god of thunder's) adherents, Mọgbà (a leading male priest) plaits his hair; no other man wears his hair this way. The male also pierce their earlobes and nostrils and adorn them with ear-rings made of different stones. Meanwhile, Oyètádé (2005:289) informs that "Traditionally, men do not make holes in their ears and even today the practice is still very much restricted to girls and women".

Among younger females wearing clothes that hardly cover their nudity, especially the ones that reveal their belly otherwise called midribs is rampant today. They also wear clothes that trouble the sexual feelings of men; these are especially common on campuses. Today, some Yorùbá females pierce their navels and adorn them with glittering jewellery in order to draw attention to the spot. This practice is copied from the Indians, whose culture it is to expose and adorn their bellies. It is pathetic that:

In the name of modernization, we are often persuaded that African cultures is out modelled and needs to be brought into the world of the Third millennium. (Bámgbósé, 2001:5)

But it is pertinent to realize that:

In any situation of long time culture contact, elements in both systems do change. Afóláyan is quick to add that, it is not all elements in the system that change, even if the culture-contact is imposed, like in a colonial situation where one culture assumed a position of superiority over another", otherwise, the victim society will hardly be recognizable later. (Loomis, cited in Oyèdípe, 2004:234).

This shows that rather than abandon traditional dressing, it is better to modernize such ceremonial dressings in line with the modern trends.

3.5. The marriage institution

Different people view marriage from diverse points. While some see it as a social obligation that must be accomplished, others see it as a necessity and indeed a fulfillment of God's order in the scripture that must be obeyed. Yet others see it as a convenience, and a means to an end (Shehu 2000:12). Marriage is an act of giving female children of marriageable ages out to males, either old or young, who are mature enough in age and experienced and have the economic capacity to take care of women/wives. Fádípe (1970:65) corroborates this:

For a woman who has reached the age of marriage to remain single is against the mores of the Yorùbá. Men get married even when they are sexually impotent in order to save their own faces or the faces of their immediate relatives, as well as to get someone to look after the domestic establishment. There are a few cases of confirmed bachelors; men who have

reached middle age without getting married, even though they are in a position to do so. But they are a product of modern times with its greater individualism, and are almost invariably Christians.

In Yorùbá culture, marriage is for companionship and procreation. Marriage is considered to be so important to the extent that it is considered a taboo for a man or woman, under whatever reason to refuse to get married. Basically, a Yorùbá man's purpose for getting married is for procreation. This he cherishes to the extent that a marriage which does not produce children is considered unproductive and a failure. The traditional Yorùbá society value marriage so much that a yet to be married member of the society, who is mature enough to take a wife or marry a husband is not considered as responsible until he or she takes a wife or marry a husband and begins to raise his or her own family. Babátúndé (2004:217) takes a functional look at marriage among the Yorùbá and concludes that: "Marriage and family constitute an important process of transition into adulthood. Marriage is the commencement of that transition into adulthood".

Marriage is the coming together of a man and a woman in order to start off a new family. Johnson (1921:113) avers that where all other things are equal and normal, there are three stages to be observed in marriage, namely an early intimation, a formal betrothal and the marriage proper. Johnson (1921:113-117) and Fádípè (1970:65-68) share the same opinion about the ways of acquiring a wife to be:

- By inheriting widows by the husband's kinsmen.
- By full-fledged legal marriage: which entails the consent of the girl's parents being sought and obtained, and the dowry being paid, with the payment of 'bride-price'.
- Free-wife to make a free-gift of girls of marriageable age.

However, Fádípè goes a step further by adding a fourth way of acquiring a wife to be, one in which:

- The principal parties neither assume the consent of parents nor involve the payment of bride-price.

This form of marriage is identified by Fádípè (1970:68) as marriage by mutual consent. The marriage by mutual consent of the two principal parties alone does not require the consent of the relatives of both parties and does not include payment of bride-price, yet the bride is regarded as a lawful married wife of her husband:

There are cases in which all forms of ceremonies are not gone through, and yet the woman is regarded as the lawful wife of the man of her choice. Mutual agreement is the only thing in all such cases, the woman's free consent, and the recognition of her by the members of the man's family, is all that is required for her to be regarded as the man's lawful wife. This classification is inexhaustive as we would soon see other ways of acquiring a wife as x-rayed by the novelists. P.68.

An example of this is found in Olábímtán's *Àyànmó*, where Jókè marries Àlàbí by mutual consent of the principal parties concerned, without the consent of both relatives. Though they are living in Europe, there are couples who get married by the law abroad, but also intimate the relatives of both parties in Nigeria. The relatives of the groom pay the bride-price in absentia and thus contract the traditional marriage proper. This is not the case in the affairs of Jókè and Àlàbí, as we observe:

Níghàtí ó dì osù kéta gééré tí òrò yí xelè, Àlàbí àtí Jókè jókò sí iwájú ẹ̀nì tí yíò sọ wọn dì tọkọ-taya gégé bí òfin ilẹ̀ Gẹ̀ẹ̀sì. Àwọn òrẹ̀ wọn tẹ̀lé wọn lọ; nínú àwọn òrẹ̀ wònyí ní ó sì x ọ̀bí ọkọ àtí aya. Látí ọjó náà ní Àlàbí àtí Jókè sí tí nǵbẹ̀ pọ̀ bí tọkọ-taya.
(*Àyànmó*, o. i. 100)

Exactly three months after this incidence of this event, Àlàbí and Jókè sat before the officer who was to pronounce them husband and wife, according to British ordinance. Their friends acted as parents of the bride and that of the groom. Jókè and Àlàbí started to live together as husband and wife from that day.

Lóòótọ̀, ó tí fẹ̀ yàwó kan ní ilu Òyínbó nisisiyí; ó tí fẹ̀ ẹ̀ tán kí àwá tó gbò...
(*Àyànmó*, o. i. 102)

Truly, he has now married another woman abroad; they were already married before we got to know about it.

This form of marriage that is contracted without the knowledge and approval of the parents is further confirmed in Iyá Àlábí's conversation with Bádéjò. when Iyá Àlábí says:

*Bí kò bá jé àìfèni-peni, àìfèniàpènià tí mǐ ará oko sán
bànté wọ ilú", àwọn ọmọ isiyí, bíwo ní ènià se òfè
obìnrin tí kò mọ ilé rẹ, tí kò mọ ọna rẹ? (Àyànmọ, o. i. 117)*

It is nothing but sheer disregard that makes a villager enter the town with ordinary *bànté* (ordinary cover for the genitals). How can someone get married to a woman whose family he does not know and of whom he does not know much?

Bádéjò replies her:

*...Sé ọjú àwọn méjèjè sítí já a? Ìrì tí wọ ilé tí ọ̀un àti Àlábí fí
itọ mọ, ohun tí ó dà wọn pọ tí yà wọn. Sé ijọba ló so wọn pọ,
hèn-èn ijọba náà titú wọn ká. (Àyànmọ, o. i. 117)*

They have now seen the consequence of their action. The dew has demolished the house they built with saliva. they have been separated by what hitherto united them. It is the government that joined them together, and it is the same government that has put them asunder.

From the above statements, the import of the approval and active involvement of parents of the bride and groom in marriage process cannot be over emphasised. This is confirmed by Fadipe (1970:69) 'the kindred of the man and woman who are to be married are as equally interested in the marriage as the individuals who are entering into the union'. Through traditional marriage, the sustainability of marriage is encouraged. Jókè and Àlábí's broke up due to non-involvement of parents of the couple in the marriage arrangements. If they had been involved, the families would have intervened and revolved the issues amicably without it resulting into divorce. This further proves that in Yoruba traditional society, traditional marriage is the proper marriage: unlike the foreign marriage which is capable of joining couples together and the same time capable of dissolving the marriage.

In *Omọ Òkú Òrun*, Àbèké moves in with Bàbá Wálé as a wife. Màmá Wálé, who is Àdió's legal wife, is erroneously believed to have sunk and died in a boat mishap.

*Àbèké kii se iyèwó bàbá omọ náà tẹlẹ́ kí iyá rẹ̀ tí ó di olóòghé
yìí tó kú; òrẹ̀ iyá Wálé ní ó jẹ́... Sighón láti ìghà tí iyá Wálé tí
kú ní Àbèké tí kó wà ilẹ̀ ọkọ rẹ̀, òun ní ó sì kù ní iyá lé àti àiyò
fún un. (o. i. 1)*

Àbèké was not married to the child's father before the child's mother died; she was iyá Wálé's friend... But, Àbèké has since moved in with her husband and become his favourite since the demise of iyá Wálé.

Àbèké moves in with her husband as a wife without any formality of marriage. She is, however, sent out of the Àdió's family by a judge in a court of law when màmá Wálé returns home as she is lucky to have survived the boat mishap. Though màmá Wálé was thought to have sunk in the accident, she was rescued and later returned home.

3.5.1. Types of marriage

Acuff (1973:277-279) classify families according to the number of legal mates in such. Three types of marriage union are identified from the Western point of view: as Monogamy, Polygyny and Polyandry.

3.5.1.(i) Monogamy

This is the most common marital form which is legal in Western societies. The principle of monogamy restricts each adult to one partner at a time. This system of marriage is economical and advantageous. It is the type of marriage that is approved by Christendom. Although it is most common among the educated elite, monogamy, which is borne out of Christianity, conflicts with the Yorùbá culture, which permits a man to have as many wives as he could marry. There is the dilemma of how to marry the second wife for anybody that embraces monogamy. This is why Bádéjọ, after embracing Christianity, is reluctant to take another wife.

3.5.1.(ii) Polygyny

This form of marriage is that in which one male may be married to several females at the same time. This form of marriage is adopted mostly for economic purpose. In it, the wives thus acquired in the man's harem of women are to help him with farm work and also procreate. The strength and wealth of such a man is determined by the number of wives and children that he has. This form of marriage, also known as polygamy, is very common in Yorùbá traditional society.

Today, polygyny is rapidly going into extinction. There is a popular saying that, "men are polygamous in nature". Rather than marry all the women that the modern men have love affairs with, today's Yorùbá men are hypocritical about such love affairs. Most men now have love nests, wherein they keep their secret lovers. Sometimes, such secret lovers bear children outside of marriage. In Yorùbá traditional society, there was no such thing as "bastard".

A man had the right and claim over the number of children that were born outside marriage. An example of this is found in *Ki Ni Mo Se* where we find that Èbana was born outside wedlock; yet, this did not stop Gbólátutù from claiming her as his legitimate daughter.

3.5.1.(iii) Polyandry

This form of marital union is very rare. In it, one woman marries several husbands. No case of polyandry has been discovered in Yorùbá society. But an attempt is now being made by women to engage in polyandry. This runs contrary to Yorùbá culture. For instance, in *Atótó Arére*, Yétúndé Ayílukọ encamps many men in her house. She practises polyandry and cares for all the men; which is against the rich Yorùbá culture; in fact, it is an aberration:

*Tábilì ọ̀tò ni Yétúndé Ayílukọ dá gbà; Àlàbá gbọ̀ pé àwọn
òkùnrin tó n kó jẹ̀ ló fì yì ara rẹ̀ ká. Àwọn òkùnrin yì ní sísé
agbára tó bá ní ní sísé; ọ̀dọ̀ rẹ̀ sì ni wọn í sùn lálaalé, wọn
ò nílẹ̀ tí wọn ó padà rẹ̀. Àwọn kan tilẹ̀ ni Yétúndé ú máa pín
oorun láàrin wọn ni bí òkùnrin aláyapúpọ̀ tí ðe láàrin
àwọn iyàwó rẹ̀...* (o. i. 119)

Yétúndé Ayílukọ arranged for her own separate circle: Àlàbá

heard that the men that followed her about surrounded her. These men were the ones that performed strenuous duties for her; and the men used to sleep in her house every night, they had no house of their own. Some people even say Yétúndé would sleep with the men in turn just like a polygamist would do among his wives...

This is not too far from promiscuity. In Yorùbá culture, promiscuity is, sometimes, referred to as a thing of popularity on the side of women. An instance is in a song by Odólayé Àrémú, a popular Yorùbá traditional musician. He sings about Aminatu Abiódún, a popular single woman, in a compact disc titled *Olówe Mòwe*. he eulogizes Aminatu Abiódún thus:

*Alhaja Aminatu Abiólím,
A – ah. Èn pèé l'ólóbìnrin ni, isé tí olókó n ɔ ni n ɔ
Èlè tí m̀bẹ̀ nídiè, akọ ni.
Àjìkẹ̀, ẹnì ó wù á, lo n gbólá fún.
Eégúnbìnrin Abòjà dẹnghere
Ijọ tó lọ Èkó ló ghé m̀jò bọ...*

Alhaja Aminatu Abiódún,
A – ah. You call her a woman, but she behaves like a man.
The vagina she possesses is that of a man.
Àjìkẹ̀, you offer yourself to whosoever you are pleased with
A female masquerade with a loose girdle.
She brought back a car, the day she went to Lagos...

The musician subtly calls the woman concerned a society woman, who wields her vagina power. The artist uses the metonym of "Olókó"; one who possesses penis, to refer to her masculine power. He also says, she brought back a car the same day she travelled to Lagos. This shows that she is an affluent woman.

3.5.2. Culture orthodoxy in marriage

Fádípè (1970:65) observes that in early Yorùbá society, a maiden was considered to be ripe enough for marriage at maturity and she was not expected to remain unmarried at full maturity. Her male counterpart was also not expected to remain single by choice, after he had become mature enough to do so.

The task of choosing a life partner was not only the concern of the man and woman who contemplated such relationship. Rather, it was the concern of the

whole relatives of both the man and the woman. In *Àyànmó*, *Ìyá Àlàbí* and *Bádéjò* (*Bàbá Àlàbí*) shop for a wife for *Àlàbí*, who refuses to get married at maturity; this made *Bàbá Àlàbí* to make the following statement to *Ìyá Àlàbí* :

... *Mo ti rò ó sí ọ̀tún, mo ti rò ó sí ọ̀sì, mo sì ti pínmu*
l'òkàn mi pé ng ó fẹ́ bínrín kan fún un fúnra mi. (o. i. 25).

I have thought about it seriously, and I have decided in my mind that I will find him a wife myself.

3.5.3. Seeking a partner

According to *Fádípè* (1970:70), after a youngman had reached puberty, it became the responsibility of his female relatives, like sisters, paternal aunts or first cousins on the father's side to look round for a suitable mate for him.

In *Orúkọ l'òyàtò*, to acknowledge the fact *Fálọ́lá* is eligible to get married, his mother attempts to enquire about the relationship existing between him and his wife-to-be:

Bí iyá rẹ̀ ti ń wádíi èwo ló ẹ̀ nípa ti Moréniké ni àwọn ọ̀rẹ̀ rẹ̀
àti aládiùgbò pàápàá ń bá a dápàára pé iyàwó kò níi pé wọ́lé.
Oghón tí àwọn Yorùbá fí ń sọ fún èniyàn pé iyàwó ti tó ó gbé
nìyẹn. (o. i. 15)

As his mother was investigating his decision concerning *Moréniké*, so also were his friends and neighbours making jests of him that he would soon take a wife. This was a device used by the *Yorùbá* to tell a mature man that it's time to get married.

In *Aiyé D'aiyé Ọ̀yinbó*, *Balógun* (*Àṣàbí's* father) looks for a husband for her, upon attainment of maturity age:

Lí ọ̀jọ́ kan ni bàbá mí pé mí ní fẹ́rẹ̀ ọ̀wùrọ́, ó wípé:
"Àṣàbí, orí rẹ̀ á dára, ọ̀nọ́ rẹ̀ á sunwòn, mo rí ọ̀kọ
kan fún ọ́". (o. i. 6)

One day, my father called me early in the morning and said: "Àṣàbí, may you prosper, may your path be smooth, I have found a husband for you".

In the pre-colonial times of about 1880, according to *Fádípè* (1970:70), at the age of about ten, a girl was considered ready for betrothal; whereas in the more recent times, *Babatunde* (2004:10) considers the period of search to be between the

ages of twenty-three to twenty-eight for the male, and age eighteen to twenty-five for the female. In looking out for a suitable partner, the first step to take was to ensure that the proposed partner was not related to the family of the youngman by blood. The issue of social class was played down: the important consideration was for the maiden to come from a good family background. She must come from a family which was not indebted or afflicted by hereditary diseases or social miscreants. The girl in question must also not be a prostitute. There should not be a trace of such diseases as insanity, leprosy, alcoholism and epilepsy in both families (Fádípè, 1970:71).

3.5.4. Acquaintance of parents

Once the parents of the boy were satisfied with the antecedents of the girl in question, the next step was to acquaint the parents of the girl of their intentions directly, or to approach member(s) of her extended family, of their intention, through a go-between, as obtained in *Ìyábò II* (between *Ìyábò* and *Olúfẹ̀mi*'s families) and vice versa.

*Àwọn Èbí ì mi àti ènìyàn wa diè tí wón sọ fún nípa ọ̀rọ̀ èmi
àti Olúfẹ̀mi n fẹ̀ láti ẹ̀ iwádú diè nípa idilé Olúfẹ̀mi. (o. i. 23)*

My immediate family and a few members of our extended family that were told about my relationship with *Olúfẹ̀mi* wanted to make enquiries about *Olúfẹ̀mi*'s family.

The parents of the girl and the boy would in turn ask for a little time to think over the proposal and also to consult the *Ìfá* oracle. An instance of this is observed in *Ó le kú*. *Àjàní* is confronted with a dilemma of choosing the right partner between *Àsàkẹ* and *Lọ́lá*. *Àjàní* seeks *Bòdẹ*'s brotherly advice and *Bòdẹ* responds thus;

*Bóràn bá sì wá rí báyíí, ó ní ohun tí àwọn bàbá wa máa n ẹ̀.
Olórun má jẹ̀ ẹ̀ kágbà tán lórílẹ̀. Ọ̀dọ̀ àwọn àgbà la máa lọ.
A ó lọ wo nńkan sí í. (o. i. 38).*

When things turn out this way, there is something our fathers do, may God not let elders go into extinction. We shall consult the elders. We shall seek spiritual solutions.

Bòdé goes to make enquiries from the three popular religions that are practised in Yorùbáland: the Christian and the Islamic clerics who represent foreign religions on the one hand, and an Ifá priest who represents the traditional religion on the other hand. Upon Bòdé's enquiries, he is informed that both Lọlá and Àşàké are good wife-material as they both will be fruitful; they will give birth to both female and male children. This is the result Bòdé got from the three places he inquired from. However, the result of the same enquiries made by Bábá Kékeré was manipulated as he had earlier directed Àşàké to take the names of her prospective husbands to Bábá Aládùúrà at Kòsódò with whom he had obviously had a discussion with over the matter. Bábá Aládùúrà thus informed Àşàké of the falsified result of the spiritual enquiry by saying that Àjàní is the worse of the three candidates submitted to him by giving reasons of promiscuity and the possibility of polygamy in the nearest future. The falsification of information by Bábá Aládùúrà is further confirmed in Bábá Àjàsá, Bábá Kékeré's friend's utterance:

*Èmi tí ẹ́n wó yìi kò yé iró aládùúrà sí mó.
Sé lódò ọ́rẹ̀ bàbá yín ní Kòsódò, lo ló?*

(o. i. 88)

I personally do not believe in prophets anymore.
Did you go to your father's friend at Kòsódò?

Àşàké replies in the affirmative:

*À-à tà lẹ̀sù ihá gbè. hí kò se agbẹ́họ?
Ohun tí bàbá yín bá sọ fún Kéléébí aládùúrà ló máa se!*

(o. i. 88)

Who would the devil have supported if not his advocate?
It is whatever father tells Celeb that he would do.

Àşàké's family also tows the line of spiritual guidance concerning the relationship between Àşàké and Àjàní. Àşàké goes to Bábá Kékeré to formally

intimate him of the existing relationship between her and Àjàní. Bàbá Kékeré replies:

En, irú ọ̀rọ̀ bẹ́ẹ̀ gba a sinùrù, ó sì gba iwádìí dáadáa. Bí a ọ̀ tilẹ̀ tí ì wádìí idilẹ̀ e wọ̀n báyii. A ni láti mò bóyá ọ̀rọ̀ náà dára tàbí kò dára. Ghogho ohun tí a bá fé ẹ̀, ó yẹ kí a bèèrè lẹwọ̀ Olúwa. Olórun má jẹ́ kí a sọ̀yàn o. Nìtorí náà mo fé kí o mú orúkọ gbogbo àwọn tó wà lókàn rẹ̀ lọ sáálo Bàbá Aládúúrà tí Kòsódò, kí ó lè so fún ọ̀, èyí tí ó bá dára nìbẹ̀. Ẹ̀ ó yẹ ọ̀ bẹ́ẹ̀? (o. i. 80).

Yes, such matter calls for patience, it also calls for careful consultation. Even if we are not investigating their family now, we need to know whether the relationship will be positive. In everything we intend to do, we ought to seek the face of the Lord. God forbids that we make a wrong choice. Therefore, I want you to take a list of all your prospective partners to Aládúúrà at Kòsódò, so that he will tell you the best amongst them. Do you understand?

This shows how deeply religious the Yorùbá are. It also indicates that the Yorùbá hardly make any important choice, such as choosing a life partner, without seeking spiritual guidance from any of the three religions of African Traditional Religion, Christianity and Islam. The parents of the boy would go back for an answer through the go-between, when the given period lapses. When the spiritual investigation is completed, the family would then inform the go-between that the finding was favourable or otherwise. After the parents had accepted the proposal, the formal espousal known as *Ijehẹn* would be announced. Parents of the boy would send symbolic gift items in appreciation to the girl's family and to formally announce the formal sealing of the proposal. At that point, the girl was considered engaged to the boy.

3.5.5. Chastity

The bride is actually expected to remain a virgin till her wedding night. It is a taboo for a girl to be found unchaste on the bridal night; it is shameful to her family. The issue of virginity is one that the Yorùbá attached much importance to in times past. Hence, value was attached to 'meeting a new bride at home'. This is what Fádípè (1970:63) calls 'virgo intacta'. It is expected that a would-be-bride

maintains her chastity and honour till her wedding night. It is to the pride and honour of a bride's family if such a bride is 'met at home'. Fádípè describes the events of the bridal night, in the next day:

A bride who was found *Virgo intacta* was the cause of much rejoicing and self-congratulation to her parents and relatives. The white sheet smeared with blood was sent in a covered up calabash bowl to her parents the first thing in the morning, accompanied by a sum of money, and a hen for sacrifice to the head of the bride. Early in the morning, the husband, together with friends, came to thank the parents of the bride, he repeated his visit later in the day, accompanied by drummers and by a whole host of his associates. (p 83 – 84).

An instance where the bride's family is honoured is found in *Ìyábò II*. Olúfèmi finds *Ìyábò* at home, as shown below:

Ní ojó kejì ní àwọn mífà nínú èniyàn oko mi múra dáadáa, tí wón sin bàhá oko àti iyá oko mi lọ sí ilé wa, láti kí àwọn òbí mi kú ináwó àná. àti láti dúpé lówó wọn fún iyàwó tí wón fún omọ wọn. Olúfèmi. Wón tún dúpé pàtàkì fún itójú tí wón fún omọ wọn ohinrin tí ó fí yege. Wón fún àwọn òbí mi ní èhùn owó ní ifihàn wípé, òkún àwọn lójú wípé omọ àwọn bá èmi iyàwo rẹ̀ nílẹ. (o. i. 65)

The following day, six of my husband's relatives dressed elegantly and accompanied my parents-in-law to my family house, to thank them for the previous day, and to specially thank them for the wife they had given to their son, Olúfèmi. They also thanked them specially for the care they had given to their daughter, that made her complete. They gave my parents a gift of cash to show their appreciation how pleasantly surprised they were, that their son met me his wife a virgin.

However, a bride that has been found to be unchaste is treated with disdain. For instance, Fádípè (1979:84) says that:

Such a woman suffers a considerable loss of face in the circle of her husband's kindred. She missed a great deal of the present(s) that a bride normally looked forward to receiving from important members of her husband's kindred. (p 84)

This is not all: her parents are made to face the shameful consequence of their daughter's indiscipline. Olábímtán, in *Àyànmó*, makes Àlàbí lament on Àjoké, his former fiancée's disappointment. Àjoké has left Àlàbí for Alhaji Sùbèrù, who is his father's choice of a marriage partner for her. However, the marriage is fruitless. Àjoké then comes to iyá Àlàbí to help her solicit for Àlàbí's understanding and to appeal to him to take her back, since an Ifá priest had told her that, except she goes back to her former fiancé, she has no chance of bearing children. In Àlàbí's conversation with his mother about Àjoké, he detests Àjoké's unchastity: hence he refuses to marry her, when his mother presents the idea to her. Àlàbí replies his mother thus:

Ìyá mi, inú mi kò dùn láti kọ ọrọ sí nínú lénú. Eléda ñyín sí mò pé mo ñgbiyànjú tó. Sùghón, ñjé ó ha yẹ kí ng ẹ ohun tí yíò ma bà mí nínú jé títí aiyé? Bí mo bá fẹ ẹ, b́áwo ni mo ẹ lè gbàgbé pé "ààbò ohínrin" ni mo fí ẹ iyàwó àkókó? (o. i. 11)

Mother, I am usually unhappy to disobey you. Your Creator knows that I try not to. But, is it right for me to accede to something that would forever sadden me? If I marry her, how can I ever forget that I married an unchaste woman as a first wife?

3.5.6. Orthodox wedding as reflected in Yorùbá novels

Marriage as an institution is mirrored in Yorùbá novels. In *Ìyábò II*, issues related to marriage and marital lives are exhaustively discussed by the novelist. The only difference in this novel and tradition in marriage earlier discussed is the fact that *Ìyábò* and Olúfẹmi meet on their own. They are not a product of match making; neither is there an intermediary, that is, *alárinnà* between them. This is predominant in contemporary times, as couples to be usually meet at schools, places of worship, parties or places of common interest.

The traditional wedding today, as discussed in *Ìyábò II*, consists of introduction between the two families. The family of Olúfẹmi comes to introduce themselves to the family of *Ìyábò*. This formally brings the already established relationship between their son and *Ìyábò* to the knowledge of *Ìyábò*'s extended family. Before the ceremonies and formal introduction, members of *Ìyábò*'s family

had made enquiries about Olúfẹ́mí's family background. This shows that before families embark or give their consent to a marriage to be contracted between their children, they make enquiries in order to know more about each other to find out if there is any blemish in either of the families.

Also, marriage contract is not arranged by the immediate family of the bride: the extended family has to be duly informed.

Ìyá gbó, bàbá gbó, kì n' ɛ ebi gbó ni ilẹ̀ Yorùbá. Ebi ní láti gbó, kí wón fì ibúkún wón sí ọ̀rọ̀ àwọn toko-taya méjèjè, kí wón tó dá ojó ìgbéyàwó. Nítorí náà, wón wí fún Olúfẹ́mí kí ó sọ fún àwọn ọ̀bí rẹ̀ kí wón kọ̀ ìwé sí idílẹ̀ tẹ̀mí wí pé àwọn fẹ́ kí idílẹ̀ wá yòrìda láti fì èmi fún omọ̀ àwọn, Olúfẹ́mí. Èyí ní a n' pè ní Èkó ní, ikòwé silé tàbí ikòwé itorọ̀ omọ̀.

(o. i. 23)

The knowledge and consent of the bride's parents is not the approval of the extended family in Yorùbá land. The extended family has to consent and bless the union of the intending couple, before the wedding date is fixed. Because of this, Olúfẹ́mí was asked to inform his parent to write a letter asking for Ìyábò's hand in marriage to their son, Olúfẹ́mí. This is what is referred to in Lagos as 'writing in' or 'letter of proposal'

The use of letter writing to request for a bride's hand in marriage is foreign; it is as a result of culture contact which is one of the consequences of post-colonialism. It is after a favourable reply has been given to the proposed relationship that the families may agree on a fixed date for the wedding proper. On the engagement day, which is the day before the church wedding, the family of Olúfẹ́mí brings the engagement tray with the message that reads.

A ti jìsé gbogbo ebi Àjàyí fún gbogbo ebi Ìsòlá, gbogbo wón sì fì ohùn sọkan wí pé kí Olúfẹ́mí omọ̀ yín, kí ó gbé Ìyábò omọ̀ àwọn ní iyèwó... Àjogbá oríṣíríṣí tí a fì idẹ̀ ɛ ní wón fì di erù idána náà... Olórí ebi oko kọ̀ ẹ̀nu sí alága ebi iyàwó, ẹ̀nítí ó máa gba idána náà. Ó wí pé 'Ebi Àjàyí ni kí n máa kí gbogbo ijókòó kí n sì gbé èbùn idána wá fún gbogbo ebi ọ̀lọ́lá Ìsòlá'. Pélú ifé tokàn-tokàn, pélu okàn irẹ̀lẹ̀, àti okàn opé gidigidi ni gbogbo ebi fì gbè idána yíi wá fún yín ó. Ebi wa sì ní èrò wí pé, gbogbo ijókòó yíi tí ɛ ebi Ìsòlá yóò ghàà tífétífé bí àwọn ebi wa tí fì bèè wá...

(o. i. 40 - 42).

We have delivered the message of Àjàyí to Ìsòlá's family, all

the members of Ìṣòlá's family have agreed that Olúfẹ́mí, your son, should marry Íyábò, their daughter... Many trays made of bronze were used to carry the engagement items... The head of the family of the groom faced the representative of the bride's family, who would receive the engagement trays. He said Àjàyí's family sends greetings to everyone present and they asked me to bring to you the gifts of engagement to all the family members of honourable Ìṣòlá with heart-felt love, with a humble heart, and a heart of gratitude, the entire members bring this engagement. Our family hopes that all present, the entire Ìṣòlá family, shall receive them with love, just as our entire family presents them with love.

With the engagement materials presentations, the traditional aspect of the wedding ceremony is completed. The remaining aspect is the solemnization of the matrimony in the church.

However, in *Àyànmọ́*, Àlàbí's parents refuse to acknowledge Jọké's parents by neither paying them a courtesy call nor paying her bride price because of her behaviour, which falls short of expectation. The bride price, which is the traditional marriage, and termed "marriage proper" in Yorùbá culture is thus denied her. The consequence of this is that when the marriage later developed a problem, there was no family intervention:

Báyìí nì bàbá àti ìyá ñfí. ọkàn wọ́n dàníyàn lójoojúmọ́ kí Àlàbí àti Jọké lè pín yà. Wọ́n kò bá Àlàbí sọ nípa kíkí ànà rẹ, wọ́n kò sì dá àbá àti ẹ owó orí Jọké. (o. i. 110)

This is how both father and mother started to hope that Àlàbí and Jọké would separate. They refused to discuss with Àlàbí how to pay the traditional visit to Jọké's parents. They also didn't suggest how they were going to pay Jọké's bride price.

In *Ó le kú*, Ìṣòlá examines relationships and courtship among youths. Àṣàké, Lọlá and Şadé are in a relationship with Àjàní. Àjàní eventually marries Şadé with pomp and pageantry. The wedding proper is also preceded by a traditional marriage.

*Bii monawáà ni ojó iyàwó kòla... Ní ìróté iyàwó kòla, àwọn
èniyàn ọkọ gbé gbogbo nńkan imọyàwó lọ sílé bàbá iyàwó
l'Àremọ.* (o. i. 114)

Soon, it was a day before marriage... On the evening preceding the marriage, the family of the husband-to-be brought all the items of introduction to the bride's family house at Aremọ.

Though this ceremony is not described in the text, the importance of introduction and traditional marriage engagement preceding the formal (religious or court) wedding ceremony is mentioned.

In the same vein, Fágúnwà, in *Ìrìnkèrindò Nínú Igbó Eléghèje*, brings the importance of the traditional marriage preceding the wedding proper to the fore. *Ìrìnkèrindò* falls in love with and marries a troll. In spite of the fact that *Ìrìnkèrindò* is on a journey and this could not take his family members to his in-laws home, he makes up for this by taking his fellow-travellers along to pay homage to his bride's family.

*Nìgbàtí ìgbéyàwó ku ọ̀la ni diẹ̀ nínú àwa tí a ǹ lọ sí Òkè-
Ìrònú lọ sí ilé Ọ̀ghéni Ajédùbùlẹ̀ tí ó ǹ gbé etí odò ìràntí
tí ó jẹ̀ àna mi.* (o. i. 84).

A day to the wedding ceremony, a few of us who were heading for Òkè-Ìrònú went to Ajédùbùlẹ̀ who resided on the bank of the river of remembrance, who is, my in-law ...

This visit to Ajédùbùlẹ̀ further buttresses the fact that traditional marriage and engagement are considered a vital aspect in marriage in Yorùbá society. If the entourage had not been on a journey and in unfamiliar grounds, they would have taken engagement materials, as a token of love and a sign of respect for the family of the wife-to-be.

Conversely, Olówóaiyé, in *Igbó Olódùmarè* is wooed by Ajédìran. This contradicts Yorùbá culture, because it is the man that seeks the hand of a woman in marriage and not the other way round. Besides, the relationship is consummated before the marriage proper takes place.

*O wù mí gidigidi mo jé kí o jé hálé mí, mo jé kí n jé aya rẹ...
Òrọ̀ didùn láti ẹ̀mú obìnrin yíì mú kí bàbá mí tó ifẹ̀ wò, fún
ìgbà kìnì ní ìgbésí ayé rẹ. Ó tò oṣù méta lẹ́hìn èyí kí wón tò
gbé arawọ̀n ní iyàwó. (o. i. 26).*

You appeal to me very much, I want you to be my husband, I want to be your wife... Sweet words from this woman made my father to taste love for the first time in his life. It was about three months after this event that they got married.

Queens in Yorùbáland were so conservative that no other man could have sexual relationship with them. The queen would remain faithful to the king for life. It is a taboo for any ordinary man to have sexual intercourse with a woman that has been married to a king or a woman that is still married to him. It is unheard of:

A kíí sán bàrùtẹ̀ Ọ̀ba

You don't wear a king's bàrùtẹ̀ (pant-like wear)

We see a reverse of this case in *Àdìtú Olódùmarè*, where Ọ̀ba Òkònkò voluntarily allows Alábàpàdé to take Èsan-ńbò as a wife, after she had been married to the king. This contradicts Yorùbá tradition; it is a result of colonial experience. In this novel, Alábàpàdé meets the acquaintance of Èsan-ńbò: a queen of Ọ̀ba Òkònkò in a mysterious circumstance. In spite of the prevailing circumstance in which they have found themselves, Alábàpàdé makes an attempt to have sexual intercourse with Èsan-ńbò. On sighting the inscription on Èsan-ńbò's undergarment which reads:

*Èmi kò lè bá ẹ̀lòmíràn pín ọ̀ ní òde aiyé, èmi l'ó ní
ọ̀ tíí ikú, Aláiyé línwà, Òkònkò... (o. i. 97)*

I cannot share you with any man in the whole world,
you belong to me till death, His royal majesty, Òkònkò.

Alábàpàdé becomes cold and asks;

Tàbí ayaba ni ọ̀? (o. i. 97)

Are you a Queen?

Èsan-ńbò replies in the affirmative. Thus, Alábàpàdé withdraws from making sexual advances to her. They are alone in the same hotel room, which contains two beds, but they both slept on separate beds. Eventually, the king gets to

know of the circumstance that led to the meeting of the two and finds it difficult to believe that they did not have sexual intercourse together. He, therefore, locks Èsan-ńbò up in her room. One day, when Èsan-ńbò is lamenting her innocence of the offence of adultery the king accuses her of, the king overhears her:

Ìwọ Ọlórún, mo ẹ bí nwọ́n ní Ọlórún ẹsan ní ọ? Èsan wo lo mǎ san fún Alábǎpádé mi yí? Tí ó bá mi gbé fún odidi osù méfà tí kò sùn lóri ibùsùn kan pèlú mi rí, tí kò bá mi ní ọrọ ikòkò kan tí ẹnìkẹni kò gbodò gbó! ... (o. i. 105).

Oh God, I think they say you are a God of reward? What reward are you going to give to Alábǎpádé? He lived with me for a whole six months without having sexual relations with me, neither did he have any secret discussions, of which no one should hear, with me.

After hearing these lament, the king decides to release Èsan-ńbò for Alábǎpádé. He also sponsors their marriage:

Kí a má sáfà á gùn lọ bí ilẹ bí ẹnì, Alábǎpádé àti Èsan-ńbò fé ara wọ́n... Ọba Ọkòńkò fún wọ́n ní owó repete. (o. i. 107)

In a nutshell Alábǎpádé and Èsan-ńbò got married. Ọba Ọkòńkò gave them a lot of money.

This is unheard of in Yorùbá culture; it is an abomination in Yorùbá traditional society. But it occurs in the novel as a result of exposure and post-colonial experience which the novelist has had. The event would never have occurred in undiluted traditional Yorùbá system.

In *Ògbójú Ọdẹ*, Fágúnwà says that it is the culture of certain spirits who reside in Igbó-ńlá to take on a live-in lover for seven years in which the couple would have produced children, before such a couple can get married. They can only get married if after the seven years, they find that they are compatible; otherwise, they separate and each spouse happily goes his/her own way.

Gégé bí àsà àwọ́n Iwín tí mbe níni Igbó-ńlá, ọdún keje tí iyàwó wọ́n bá tí ńbá wọ́n gbé ni nwọ́n tó gbódò ẹ iğbèyàwó iyàwó á tí bimọ, tokotaya nǎ á sì ti mọ iwà ara wọ́n. Bí iwà wọ́n bá bá ara mu, nwọ́n á gbé ara wọ́n ní iyàwó – èyíni ní arédè. Bí iwà wọ́n kò bá sì há ara mu, nwọ́n á kọ ara wọ́n sílẹ tayọtayọ. Ọkúnrin á mǎ wá aya mǐràn ká, obinrin á sì mǎ fi ara rẹ wá ọkọ kiri... (o. i. 52)

N kò mò pé o kò fèràn mi. O tún fi ọkọ kan pamọ síbí kan fún mi ní? Tàbí o kò mò nńkan tí àwọn ayé ñ wí nípa wa ní? Bí o kò bá fèràn mi, ẹ̀sì dákun, tètè sọ fún mi o. (o. i. 163)

I didn't know that you do not love me. Did you keep a husband for me somewhere? Don't you know what people say about us? If you do not love me, please let me know in time.

In *Àyànmọ*, Ìyúnadé shares mutual love with Àdiitú Olódùmarè in the novel. Àdiitú Olódùmarè, Ìyúnadé writes a love letter to Àdiitú while Àdiitú also writes her. They both exchanged these letters simultaneously. Ìyúnadé writes:

... Sùgbón mo fẹ sọ nńkan tí obìnrin kì ísábà sọ, mo fẹ ọkọ nńkan tí obìnrin kì ísábà ọ, nkò fẹ láti dúró de ọrọ idúnú tí obìnrin mǎ ñdúró dè láti ọdọ ọkúnrin, mo fẹ wí fún ọ pé mo mǎ fẹ ọ. (o. i. 79)

...But, I want to say something which a woman rarely says, I want to write something which a woman does not usually write, I don't want to wait for the sweet words a woman waits to hear from a man, I want to tell you that I want to marry you.

Even here, Ìyúnadé refuses to be defiled by Àdiitú. When Àdiitú and Ìyúnadé were stranded and isolated on an unknown island, she refused to share his bed as Àdiitú picks two pieces of clothe, he wants to prepare their bed together, but Ìyúnadé disagrees with him, she refuses to sleep with him, saying:

Dìitú, Dìitú tẹmi, gbọ mi sẹ, jẹk'á rọjú k'á dẹ 'lé kí a tò mǎ sùn ní bìsùn kan pọ, kí àwọn èniyàn mi mò mí l'áya rẹ, kí nwọn mò-ọ l'ọkọ mi. Ẹni a bí 're kò gbọdọ hùwà ẹtẹ, gbajúmọ kò gbọdọ hùwà aṣa... (o. i. 85)

Dìitú, my own Dìitú, listen to me, let us endure till we return home, before we sleep in the same bed, for my people to know me as your wife, for them to know you as my husband. A well brought-up person must not behave in a disgraceful manner, a well-known person, must not behave like a shameless person...

This action of having pre-marital sex though an aberration in traditional Yoruba society, is what is obtainable in contemporary Yorùbá society. Young men are now at liberty to violate the persons of the young women they interact with before contracting marriage formality. They may also end up not taking the so violated woman for a wife.

3.5.7. Royal marriage

Oyèdélé portrays royal marriage in *Kí Ní Mo Sé?* In it, it is depicted that a king-to-be must be from a royal family and be born on the throne. The crown-prince who will one day be enthroned as a king must be born of direct lineage of a previous king. His mother must also come from a royal family.

Àwọn ọmọba l'òkùnrin l'òbìnrin kí fẹ ará ita s'aya tàbí s'okọ wọn... Ní tí àwọn ọmọba, wọn kí í tilẹ fẹ ẹnikéni níghà náà nínú àwọn ọmọ olórá... ara wọn nìkan ló máa n fẹ ara wọn nínú ààfín, àfí àwọn ọmọba ilú òdikejì ló tún lẹ fẹ wọn. (o. i. 2)

Princes and princesses do not get married to people outside royal families ... As for princes and princesses, they do not marry anyone among wealthy families... they marry among one another within the palace, or marry princess and princesses from other royal families of nearby towns.

Nítòrí òfín àtí àsì ààfín ìghà náà, àbúrò(Ọmọba tíí sè èjè kan náà pèlú rẹ gégé hí a tí tóka sí ní Ọmọba ghódò fẹ sè iyàwó rẹ; èjè ara rẹ yìí ní iyáálé rẹ. Ọmọkùnrin tí iyáálé yìí bá sè kókó bí ní Àrẹmọ rẹ tàbí bééré rẹ. òun sè ní Àrólé rẹ. Bí ọmọba yìí bá sè j'oba, iyáálé rẹ tí í sè èjè kan náà pèlú rẹ yìí ní olori rẹ, àwọn iyókù ní a n pè ní ayaba. Gbogbo àwọn ọmọ ayaba pátápátá àtí àwọn ọmọ tí Olórí bá tún bí lèhìn Àrẹmọ tàbí Bééré, ọmọ Oba ní wón í sè, kò sí sí òkan tí ó lè dí Àrólé nínú wọn, ikú Àrẹmọ tàbí tí Bééré kò pa ipò olori dà, bí ó bá ní ọmọ míràn nilé. (o. i. 3)

As a result of the law and culture that existed in the palace then, the younger sisters of the same blood with the Àrẹmọ as mentioned are eligible for the Àrẹmọ to get married to. This woman from his own blood is his senior wife and his queen. It is the first child produced of such marriage that

becomes the Àrẹmọ or Bééré. If the prince becomes king, his first wife, who is his own blood becomes his queen. His other wives are known as the wives of the king. All the children born by the king's wives and other children born by the queen after the Àrẹmọ and Bééré are the king's children (Ọmọba), none of them can become the Àrẹmọ, the death of the Àrẹmọ or that of Bééré does not change the status of the queen, if she has other existing children.

The above demonstrates that in the text, traditional Yoruba royal marriage is restricted to those born with blue-blood, that is, both the bride and the groom must essentially be born of royalty. This means that marriage between commoners and the Nobles is not usually encouraged.

3.5.8. Marriage through abduction of the girl

In this type of marriage, the intending groom abducts young maidens. This fact is x-rayed in *Àjẹkú l'ayé*. Àláńí, a non-native from Abúlé Alágbàáá and who is in fact, an outcast marries Adéníkèé, a native of Ológògò, where he sojourns with Bámgbélúú and his wife.

In *Orúkọ ló yàtọ*, Yémiitàn discusses a marriage where Olódàn abducts Moréníké who is already engaged to Fálọlá. After several trials and disappointments at marriage, Àbèbí is given to Fálọlá as a grand-price for winning in a wrestling contest. Fálọlá eventually abducts Àbèbí, his fiancée, on whom he had paid bride price, but he is yet to finalise the marriage ceremony. In Ìsòlá's *Ogún Omọdẹ*, the novelist frowns at Àyòkà's abduction on her way to the Arúlógun market.

Àyòkà àti àwọn omoge miiran ni wón dìjọ n lẹ. Àfi bi wón ti dé idi àgógó kan báyii, lẹbàá ọ̀nà, tí àwọn Wòrípàrì wònyí sáré bọ sójú ọ̀nà; kí àwọn omoge tóó mọ ohun tó n ẹlẹ, àwọn géndé ti nawó gán Àyòkà. Ere ni àwàdà ni, wón ti n tii lógbọ ghò-òh lẹ. Nígbà tí wón sàkiyèsì pé àwọn ará abà ọkọ Àyòkà ni wón, àwọn yòókù fariwo ta. ... Ariwo Èjíníkèé ni a kókó gbó. Ohùn rẹ lalẹ gororo. Ó n pariwo gbogbo ará abà láti wáá lẹ gba Àyòkà sílẹ. (o. i. 90-91)

Àyòkà in the company of other maidens were going together. As they approach a lofty tree by the roadside. Suddenly, the thugs appear before them. Before the maidens know what is happening, the men have abducted Àyòkà. They begin to push her along the road. When the maidens noticed that the men are from Àyòkà's fiancée's village, the remaining ladies cry out. It was Èjíníkèé's scream that was initially heard. The cries of the other maidens went out loud to the villagers to come and rescue Àyòkà.

Though, Àyòkà is lucky enough to have been salvaged from her kidnappers, some other maidens are not so lucky. They are thus unceremoniously married to their

delinquent husbands. The same occurs in *Ọmọ Olókùn Èsìn*, where Lágboókò makes an attempt to abduct Arinládé, before she is rescued by Àjàyí and others.

The act of giving female children of marriageable age out to their father's friend or son in order to seal friendship is also another form of marriage. Also, the act of a father promising to give his daughter to an Ọba or a titled chief, or other influential citizens as a wife which was common among the Yorùbá in the pre-colonial era, is still found occasionally today. In this type of marriage, the would-be wife does not need to know the would-be husband before hand. Sometimes, they only meet on their wedding day. The question of love does not come into traditional Yorùbá marriage as love is secondary, and it is supposed to grow later. Where the bride opposes the choice made for her by her parents, she is abducted by the groom with the knowledge of her parents. Where she has an intended spouse, she is kidnapped and taken away by her new lover.

In *Èégún Aláré*, the king gives his daughter to Ọ̀jéládé (the magic performing masquerade), as a gift after his performance. In *Kékeré Èkùn*, Bádéjọ marries Àláké for Àlàbí, though Àlàbí is not favourably disposed to the idea initially; he even refuses to attend the ceremony, which is fully billed and performed by his parents. However, Àláké is later sent to Lagos to live with Àlàbí. Also, in *Àyànmọ*, Àjọké's father gives her out in marriage to Àlàháji, due to the fact that he is popular, mature, capable, wealthy and experienced. When Àjọké's father informs her that he has decided to marry her off to Àlàháji, Àjọké was unhappy and her father chastises her thus:

*Kíní n ẹ ọ, tàbí o rò pé o kò dàgbà tó láti ní ọkọ nì? ...
Àlàháji tí mo sì fẹ́ fí ọ́ fún yí, iwọ náà mọ ipò rẹ̀ nílẹ̀-lọko,
légbé-lógbà, àní ní ghogbo ilú yí... ohun kan tí mo sì fẹ́
toro lówó rẹ̀ ní pé kí ó má sàì mí ọ lọ sí Mèkà ní àmódún. (o. i. 14)*

What is wrong with you, or do you think you are not old enough to have a husband? You are also aware that Àlàháji that I intend to marry you off to, is popular far and wide, among his equals and guilds, even throughout this town... The only thing I intend to ask from him is that he should send you to Mecca next year.

The above indicates the parent's match-making of marriage partners which was rampant in the pre-colonial era though it still sometimes occur in modern times. Right from pregnancy, the Yorùbá sometimes promise their friends and associates that if their pregnant wife gives birth to a female child, the child will be given out in marriage to either the friend or associates or his son. This is found in *Ó le kú*. Àṣàké promises that if Sádé gives birth to a baby boy and she bears a female child, their children would marry each other.

3.9. Modern marriage

In recent times in Yorùbáland, the trend in marriage has taken a three dimensional outlook. These are discussed below:

3.9.1. Court marriage

In this form of marriage, a marriage ceremony is conducted under the customary law. The registrar performs the ceremony between the husband and wife with a witness each from both parties. The symbol of such marriage is the wedding bands which are exchanged by the couples as a token and symbol of the marriage. Under this form of marriage, the slogan is 'one man, one wife'. A wife is considered as being legally married to a man and vice-versa in this form.

3.9.2. Christian marriage

Christian marriage is a marriage conducted according to customary law. This marriage, according to customary law, commits a man to maintain a single wife. In it a man stays married to one woman and he is liable to be sued for bigamy if he is found to be married to more than one woman at a time. Before a Christian wedding is conducted, the certificate of the court marriage is sought.

3.9.3. Muslim marriage

In Muslim marriage, known as Nikah ceremony, marriage is not a sacrament but a legal, binding contract between a man and a woman. The acceptance of the contract by the spouses involves a mutual commitment to live together according to the teachings of Islam. The contract involves a mutual exchange of rights and responsibilities (*Encarta Encyclopedia Deluxe, 2004*). Though modern Muslims

also partake in court marriage, there is no compulsion in the Muslim society for a legal marriage certificate before a marriage is solemnized. As a matter of fact, according to Islamic injunction, a man is allowed to marry as many as four wives, as long as he is able to so provide for them emotionally, sexually, materially and share his love equally among them.

On the other hand, the Christian wedding, according to Fádípè (1970:96), is usually the most expensive. In it ostentation is displayed, wealth and opulence are also shown-off. The wedding is elaborate and so are feasting and merrymaking in the houses of both the bride and the bridegroom. The accumulated savings of the bridegroom are spent on clothes and feasts. It is also a tradition among the Yorùbá elite parents to give their daughter's hand in marriage in a very flamboyant and superlative ceremony. This of course, includes the grooms' elite parents. In today Yorùbá society, wedding ceremonies stand on the tripod of the traditional marriage, the legal or court marriage and the Islamic or Christian marriage ceremonies.

In *Ó Le Kú*, Àjàní marries Şadé in a very elaborate wedding ceremony which is the talk-of-town. There are six groups of people adorning six different 'aşò ẹbí' (uniform). The pirate fraternity is also present in their full regalia to add colour and glamour to the occasion. The wedding reception takes place in the government hall at Oríta-méfà in Ìbàdàn. It is a high society wedding ceremony. *Àyànmíó* narrates how Jọké marries Àlàbí before the marriage registrar according to British laws. They are accompanied by their friends. Among their friends, they choose those who stand in as the parents of both brides and groom. Theirs is a very low-key and modest marriage ceremony.

Likewise, in *Gbóbaníyí*, Títílọlá marries Bámídelé under the British Law in far away London. Both the bride and the groom refuse to inform their parents about their association and impending marriage. Friends represent their parents at the occasion. There is much to eat and drink at the wedding and the guests have a good time. The only exception, it seems, is the absence of 'Aşò Ẹbí'. The fact that the groom and the best man wear a similar dress can also be seen as "Aşò Ẹbí" in the English culture and court marriage.

In *Ménumó*, a superlative marriage ceremony is described. The crown-prince to the throne, Prince Kòfowórọlá, takes a wife. The ceremony lasts several

days with display of wealth and affluence. Likewise in *Ijànbá Sélú*, there is a display of frivolities when Àjùwòṅ takes a wife. As a head of government, the occasion is graced by many dignitaries from home and abroad, foreigners and the natives compete for attention. There is much to eat and drink. Lots of wedding gifts, including motor vehicles, are received. The elaborate nature of the wedding is coloured with the aircraft display by the Air Force.

In sum, the institution of marriage is taken very seriously in the Yorùbá culture. The tradition is strictly adhered to, except in some very few cases where we find deviances. Marriage in Yorùbá community is an aspect of the culture that is still guarded jealously and celebrated with pomp and pageantry, a grand and colourful event which is the pride of the Yorùbá.

3.10. Divorce

Divorce is an official ending of a marriage by an official decision in a court of law. *Encarta Encyclopedia Premium (2008)* says

Divorce or dissolution, is a legislatively created, judicially administered process that legally terminates a marriage no longer considered viable by one or more of the spouses and that permits both to re-marry.

The Yorùbá woman is highly resilient; she stays with her husband even when it is detriment to her happiness. In good and bad times, she remains with her husband. She is supportive of the entire family. In Yorùbá tradition, divorce is not a common occurrence. This is due to the fact that all family members are involved in the process of marriage. As such, the members of both extended families will have to be intimated and persuaded that the situation is beyond control, before they accede to the final decision of divorce. As a matter of fact, the issue must be between life and death before the Yorùbá would resort to divorce. Òjó (2004:240) corroborates this viewpoint about the Yorùbá woman:

The Yorùbá culture is not very supportive of divorce since marriage is a family affair rather than individual business, the community makes provision for solving family feuds and fostering harmony. The Yorùbá believe that no family problem is unsolvable. Hence, the divorce rate is very low among the Yorùbá.

In the past, divorced women who returned to their family houses after a failed marriage were referred to as 'dálémoṣì', such a woman was viewed as an outcast and an unruly woman. But today, the trend is changing fast; more couples get married abroad, or get married by the law here at home. This makes their marriage the exclusive preserve of the couples involved only. This is what Fádípé (1970:68) describes as the informal extra-legal marriage by the mutual consent of the two principal parties alone. As such, rather than seek advice and resolve issues within the extended family fold before matters get out of hand, such people rush to the court of law where they were married to file for divorce and thus bring the marriage to an end.

In *Bàbá Rere*, Bàbá Lékè abandons his wife and four children and moves in with his concubine. They live together until he is exposed, having defrauded the bank, where he was working. He serves a year jail term after which he returns home to his wife and children. Also, iyá Wálé, in *Omọ Òkú Òrun*, has a good ground for divorcing her husband, but rather than divorce him, she forgives and forgets.

In these two instances, the marriages would have ended up in divorce on the ground of infidelity and adultery. But not for the Yorùbá woman who believes that 'Ilé ọkọ obìnrin l'obìnrin n'ghé' that is, a woman's place is with her husband. Iyá Wálé and Iyá Lékè, in both texts, take back their husbands. They decide to pitch their tents with their children rather than leave them in the care of another woman who may maltreat them.

However, the same cannot be said of; Musili, Iyá Àlàbá in the novel *Atótó Arére*. In it, Òkédìjì informs that Musili eventually divorced Busari, bàbá Àlàbá, when she could no longer endure the criticism of her parents that she married a non-native, and the subsequent death of her twin children, including the third child, Ìdòwú, which bàbá Àlàbá attributed to be the consequence of Iyá Àlàbá's parents' disapproval of her marriage to a non-native. When Musili could no longer bear the tongue-lashing of her husband on this event, she bowed out of her marriage, leaving her son, Àlàbá, behind.

Musili kò sọ fún enikéni tí ó fì kọ Busari silẹ, tí ó sì fì lọọ fẹ ọkọ miiran. Onitòhún jáwèé fún un tán, ó sì ti sanwó fún

*Busari, kí Musili tóó yojú sí àwọn èniyàn rẹ. Omọ odún méjọ
ni Àlábá nígbà náà.* (o. i. 12-13)

Musili did not inform anyone before she left Busari, her husband, and married another man. She had served him a divorce letter, and paid compensation to Busari, before Musili informed her family of her actions. Alábá was only eight years old.

As a result of this, Àlábá becomes circumstantial victim of the divorce of her parents; he pays dearly for this as he was severely maltreated by Taibatu, his step-mother, whom his father later married. Àlábá eventually becomes a run-away child; the event culminates into his becoming a street urchin, a thief, before he eventually joined a gang of armed robber, and becoming one himself. This is one of the havoc that divorce wrecks on the lives of divorced couples. The practice is unwholesome.

CHAPTER FOUR

CULTURE ORTHODOXY IN POLITICAL INSTITUTION

4.0 Introduction

In this Chapter, culture orthodoxy in Yorùbá political institution as reflected in Yorùbá novels is appraised. The focus is on governance as a sub-division of the political institution. Generally, monarchical governance was prominent in Yorùbá traditional societies. Democratic governance was later introduced as a result of the Yorùbá interaction and association with the British colonial masters. Military governance also found its way in the polity in 1963, when the first military coup took place in Nigeria. All these forms of ruling constitute the contemporary Yorùbá political system.

4.1 Governance and the Yorùbá society

Àyántáyò (2003:2) defines governance as a system having to do with formulation and execution of rules and regulations for the benefit of the society. During the period preceding the formation of society, as observed by Hobbes (cited in Àyántáyò 2003:2).

There were no laws, no authority, no morality, no sense of Justice, no notions of right and wrong. Everybody just minded his affairs and tried to fulfil and protect his interest. The establishment of society put a stop to this chaotic situation. The creation of the society brought about a change to this condition and heralded governance.

Therefore the emergence of society paved way for governance. Chiefs are the governors of their various societies. Afọláyan and Afọláyan (2004) reiterates that governance in Yorùbá land is hierarchical, with the paramount ruler or 'Oba Aládé' as the political and spiritual ruler of the society. The Oba is assisted by the chiefs in running the affairs of the town. The chiefs are in charge of various departments of the Oba's cabinet. The major chiefs ascend to the chieftaincy stools by heredity. There are also honorary chiefs who are given titles as a mark of honour and for their contributions to the advancement and development of the society.

There are also Baálés who reign over their different domains. They are responsible to the Baálès. After the Baálés come the Mógàjís. The Baálés are in charge of each compound and they are responsible to the Baálés. Below the Baálés, are the heads of each family unit, who are also responsible to the Baálè. All the chiefs, whether traditional or honorary, work together for the advancement, peace, unity, progress and stability of the town. The political system of the Yorùbá evidently reflects their cultural unification. This shows that governance in traditional Yorùbá society was democratic before the incursion of colonialism.

4.2. Kingship

An Ọba is a traditional ruler among the Yorùbá. He is both the political and spiritual leader of his domain.

Afọláyán and Afọláyán (2004:266) assert:

Traditional rulership among the Yorùbá is quite different from modern-day kingships. The Yorùbá Ọba commands both political and spiritual clout in his domain.

The Ọba is in the centre of all activities, and everything revolves around him. Traditional rulership has undergone a number of socio-cultural metamorphoses, but in spite of all odds, it has survived. The leadership style in Yorùbá culture has also been polluted as a result of post-colonialism, in that the normal practice of choosing an Ọba has been bastardized. According to Bámgbóşé (2001:5):

Leadership roles among the Yorùbá have become politicized. Even the most sacred institution of kingship has been polluted with irregular strategies of succession, government-approved chieftaincy declarations have had to be made to determine which ruling house can present candidates for succession and what procedures are to be adopted. Gone were the days when all that was required to fill a vacant stool was to consult Ifá as an impartial oracle.

Unlike in the traditional Yoruba society, today, the Ọba is no longer regarded as next in command, only to the gods, as claimed by Afọláyán and Afọláyán (2004: 272):

By the turn of the twentieth century, the *Ọba* no longer occupied the same traditional status of sacro-sanctify in the heart of the people. The *Ọba*'s power had been weakened by the presence of colonial administration, and they were no longer seen as being above the reproach of their people.

Oyèdípè (2004:233) also commens that:

The Yorùbá were affected by the consequence of world activities prevailing at that time. An instance is that of the Trans-Atlantic slave trade which led to the admittance of non-Yorùbá slaves into Yorùbáland, from Cuba, Brazil and Siera-Leone into Yorùbáland also brought about, a lot of changes in the family structure, in the architecture, dress, religion and education.

The postcolonial times have not been the best era for the *Ọba* (Afọláyan and Afọláyan, 2004:272). What is obtainable today in the institution of *Ọbaship* is the situation whereby the consultation of *Ifá* as an arbiter is condemned as idolatory or fetish with the notion that people sometimes manipulate the result of such consultations. *Ifá* is the deputy of *Olódùmarè* in matters of wisdom and fore-knowledge, while *Ọrìsà-ńlá* is His deputy in respect of the creation of the universe. The Yorùbá believe that *Ifá* was sent to the world by God to protect man and that he knows everything about man and can give advice on any event. Hence, people consult him on all occasions for guidance. The Yorùbá would not do anything without consulting *Ifá*. Alana (2004:77) comments on the link among the three religion prominent among the Yorùbá:

Traditional religion is very much alive just like Islam and Christianity. The three religions have continued to borrow or appropriate some practices and beliefs from one another, though with slight modification and new interpretations, where necessary.

According to Afọláyan and Afọláyan (2004:268), normally, an *Ọba* is selected by his people through a process that includes progenial elimination and rotation, oracular consultation and popular acclamation.

4.3. Monarchical governance

According to Afọláyan and Afọláyan (2004:285), "the traditional institution of Ọbaship among the Yorùbá was a system of theocracy, with democratic undertones and a proclivity for subtle autocracy". *The Chambers Universal Learners Dictionar* describes monarchy as a state governed by a single person. It is the rule of one man, or woman as the case may be, whether good or bad, legitimate or unlawful, wise or incompetent.

In the traditional Yorùbá society, the Ọba is the paramount ruler. Ascension to the throne of Ọbaship in Yorùbá land is by heredity. The methods adopted for the installation of an Ọba, according to Àyántáyò (2003:6), are both social and religious. The Ọba heads the chieftainship. Traditionally, the Yorùbá community is headed by the Ọba, who is next, only to the gods, and whose authority and actions cannot be challenged. Fádípè (1970:198) confirms further that: "The prevalent system of government of sovereign political units in Yorùbáland is monarchical". Ògúntómisìn (1993:230) corroborates these facts:

Theoretically, the Ọba was regarded as a divine ruler with absolute powers. He was a companion of the gods and possessed the power of life and death over his people. He was a constitutional monarch who had to consult his council of chiefs in the day-to-day running of the affairs of his town.

It is agreed that the prefix, Ọba (king) or Olú (ruler) as appellations to the names of these rulers indicates that they were sovereign heads of their domains".

In Yorùbáland, chieftaincy is mostly hereditary. The heir apparent assumes the position of his late father, just as his father assumed same from his own father; he is thus enthroned. Yémitán's *Gbóbaníyì* satires the level of political corruption in Nigeria after independence. We find that chieftaincy title is acquired in Yémitán's *Gbóbaníyì*. Bámidélé buys the title of "Gbóbaníyì" through his wealth:

Inú púpọ̀ nímú àwọn ijòyè ilú kò dùn sí ohun tí Olókè-irà ẹ̀ yí. Igba wo ni ayé bàjé dé 'bè - kí odidi Ọba máa tan iná wá iyì kiri! Láti ojó tí Agidimgbì ti tẹ ilú Òkè-irà dó ní nńkan bí igba odún séyin a kò gbó irú ẹ̀ rí. Àwọn ijòyè àbáláyé ní je nìbè. Sùghon Olókè-irà t'óté yí tó tún gbé oyè àtọwá lá dé. Iho nímú itàn isèlálẹ̀ Òkè-irà ló sọ pé oyè kan wà nìbè tó ñ jẹ Gbóbaníyì? ... (o. i. 114 -115)

Most of the chiefs of the town were unhappy with the decision of Olókè-irà to confer a honorary chieftaincy title on a citizen. When did things get so bad that a whole king would start to seek honour. Since the time Agidimgbi founded the town of Òkè-irà, about two-hundred years ago, we never heard of such. It is traditional chiefs that are installed there. But the reigning Olókè-irà has brought a new dimension into it by introducing honorary titles. Where in the history of Òkè-irà is it stated that a chieftaincy title of Gbóbaniyi exists?

The chiefs are angry with the king. They contend that the king can only confer chieftaincy titles as traditional titles rather than creating honorary titles arbitrarily and conferring same on Bámidélé, without consulting the chiefs and obtaining their approval. The chiefs wonder why the king has to seek honour, since providence has conferred honour on whoever is the enthroned king, as the title, *Ghóbaniyi* translates into "Honour the king". They wonder why the king has to look for a chief that will honour him. This amounts to an aberration.

In *Ìrìnkèrindò Ninú Igbó Elégbèje*, Fágúnwà views chieftaincy titles as purely hereditary. In *Ìlú Àwọn Èdidàré*, the heir apparent, Òmùgòdiméta, is enthroned the king after the demise of his father, Òmùgòdiméji.

*Ní ojò keje tí Òmùgòdiméji ká ní mwón, fi àkòbí omo rẹ
joyè, oríkọ ẹni tí ń jẹ Òmùgòdiméta. (o. i. 49)*

Seven days after the death of Òmùgòdiméji, his first son, Òmùgòdiméta was enthroned as the king.

In order that this tradition is preserved, and that the royal blood is not polluted by circumstances, Oyèdélé in *Ki Ni Mo Ẹ?* writes:

*Nígbà tí Bàbá Gbólátutù wàjà tán, tí ilú sì ẹ gbogho ètùtù
isínkú rẹ tán, ilú mú Gbólátutù, wón sì fi sórí oyè bàbá rẹ
láàrin àwọn omọba tí wón fà lélé fún wọn. Sùgbón
Gbólátutù kò tún ní iyàwó kankan tí ẹnikéni mọ mọ on
gégé bí àsà ìgbàani hikò ẹ Odésèítán tí ó bi Èbàná fún un
bí àkòbí rẹ. Awọn ará ilú àti àwọn mọlébí Gbólátutù Oba
kò ka Èbàná sí Àrẹmọ 'binrin Oba rára hikò ẹ Omọba
lásán, hẹ ẹni wọn kò sì ka iyá rẹ sí olorì bí kò ẹ ayaba,
nitori àsà ìgbà náà tí a ti fẹnu kàn sàájù. Àsà nlá ilú yìi kò
gha Odésèítán láyè láti kó wá sí ààfin tí tí a ó fi rí Olorì tí
Odésèítán yóò há ní ààfin bí iyáálé rẹ. (o. i. 21).*

After the demise of Gbólátutù's father, and the completion of all his rites of passage, Gbólátutù was chosen and enthroned as the new king among the prince(s) that were on ground. But Gbólátutù did not have any known wife according to the culture then, except Ọdẹ̀sẹ̀ítán, who was the mother of Èbánà, his first child. The town people and extended family did not recognize Èbánà as the crown-princess at all, but only an ordinary Ọmọ̀ọ̀ba. Also, her mother was not acknowledged as the queen, except an ordinary Ayaba, because of the then existing culture that has been mentioned previously. This important culture of the town does not permit Ọdẹ̀sẹ̀ítán to move into the palace, until a queen is found for the king, whom Ọdẹ̀sẹ̀ítán would meet in the palace as her senior co-wife.

The novelist adds a new dimension to the process of enthronement of a new monarch, in which a king had to be borne of royal families on paternal and maternal sides. This is when the firstborn child of such a king is allowed to ascend the throne of his forefathers. This shows that in the past, traditional rulers were enthroned to rulership positions based on the tradition of the people. Rájí and Danmole (2004:68) comment on the influence of neocolonialism on Yorùbá traditional institution thus:

Towards the end of colonial rule, and since independence, the dictates of modern times have not allowed the Ọbas to exercise their powers and authority, although their influence continues to endure.

The Ọbas' position and status have changed to that of royal fathers, who are only consulted by the ruling government in power on various issues. They are supposed to remain non-partisan. The current situation is that the Ọbas remain at the background, mostly seen, but not heard.

In contemporary times, the Ọbas are at the mercy of successive ruling governments, who pay their salaries and most of whom demand absolute loyalty from the Ọbas, to the extent that an Ọba is not expected to travel out of his domain without seeking and obtaining the approval from the local government chairman and the governor of the state where he is domiciled.

4.4. Erosion of power

In *Ìrèkè Onibudó*, Fágúnwà metaphorically depicts kingship and challenge of authority in the animal kingdom as it is applicable to humans. It is an abomination to challenge monarchs in Yorùbá society. Fágúnwà claims that monarchs can be challenged when they err. The tiger that is second in command in animal kingdom is challenged. Ológbò Ìjàkadi successfully outwits the Tiger, by deceptively killing his six children whom he pretends to beautify through traditional facial marks. Hitherto, the Tiger had been killing and eating lesser animals. But Ológbò Ìjàkadi is able to stop this action, as he eventually conquers the Tiger, who, in the animal hierarchy, is next in command to the Lion, the king of the jungle.

*Mo fé láti kọ ilà sí àwọn omọ re lára, ilà tí mo sì nífé kọ yìí
yàtò sí ilà tí ó wà lára àwọn eranko gbogbo. Bí mo há kọ
ọ́tún, gbogbo àwọn eranko inú igbó ni yóò mọ pé iwọ́ ju
àwọn lọ. Kìniún pàápàá yíò mọ pé àwọn eranko n pé òn
l'Ọba lásán ni, iwọ́ gan ni o ni nńkan Ọba.*

(o. i. 25)

I want to put marks on your children, the mark that I intend to put on their bodies is different from that which is on all other animals. After I have put the marks, all the animals in the forest will know that you are superior to them. The lion also will realize that animals merely refer to him as the king, it is you that has got what it takes to be a king.

The tradition of facial marks raised here by Fágúnwà is very important among the Yorùbá in the past. According to Oyètádé (2004:396),

Yorùbá anthropologists agree that although the original purpose of facial scarifications is to distinguish various Yorùbá families and lineages, and also to identify people during war and or slave trade, facial marks have also become part of the efforts of the Yorùbá to enhance their natural beauty.

In old Ọ̀yọ́, body marks are put on princes and princess to show that they are members of the royal family. This must be what prompted Fágúnwà, to make use of this idea in relating the Ológbò Ìjàkadi account. Facial marks as beauty-enhancement method is what Ológbò Ìjàkadi exploits in order to deceive the Tiger, and carry out the heinous act of murdering Tiger's children. This tradition of facial marks as beauty enhancement has almost gone into total extinction today. As a

result of modernism, there is no longer need for the use of facial marks as means of social identification of natives. Formal education now enables individuals to identify themselves and their ethnicity. Also, inter-tribal wars that made the use of facial marks as a means of identification important, are no longer rampant in modern societies.

4.5. Erosion of power in traditional Yoruba Society

In *Aiyé D'aiyé Òyìnbó*, Dèlànò paints the picture of governance in traditional Yoruba society, before and after the British rule, which diminished the power of the Obas and chiefs and brought about rule under the law. Babalọlá commits arson against Adánójà, but he sees it as exercising his traditional role and powers as the political head of Ojúṣàngó. He simply does not understand why his authority over his domain has to be challenged by the white colonial masters. He stands firm against any whittling down of his powers. Babalọlá vehemently stands against violation of traditional rules by the foreigners in spite of the fact that monarchs are not challenged in Yorùbá tradition, hence the traditional greeting “Kábíyèsí” – which means ‘Ká-bi-ò-kò-sí’, that is, he who holds sovereign power and whom no one challenges.

Ní ìgbà láíláí, kí Òyìnbó tó gun òkè, àwọn àgbà ilú àti olóyè ní wón n̄ ṣe ètò ìjọba, tí wón sì n̄ dájó...
(o. i. 29)

In olden days, before the whites came on board, the elders and chiefs were governing, they were also in charge of justice ...

After Adánójà, a non-indigene has snatched the wife of an indigene, Babalọlá metes out justice which he feels is commensurate to the offence committed. The colonial Whiteman challenges his authority and effrontery, which undermines the powers of the whites who are ruling. Babalọlá is therefore, handcuffed and arrested. Babalọlá laments

Ó ṣe, aiyé d'aiyé Òyìnbó. Òyìnbó wá b'aiyé jé ... Ènià gba obìnrin aláádùghò rẹ, kí a má lè dá sẹrià fún u.

(o. i. 36)

What a shame, it is now the world of the Whiteman. The whiteman has spoilt the world... somebody snatches his neighbour's wife, yet we cannot bring him to justice.

The Whiteman's erosion of the powers of Obas resulted into the fusion of the foreign form of governance and justice that eroded the roles of traditional rulers in Yorùbá society. This was the beginning of modernity in justice and rule of law. Gradually, there came reduction in the absolute powers hitherto enjoyed by the kings under the native law and customs.

Fálétí, in his novel *Ọmọ Olókùn Èsìn*, presents another challenge to authority. Àjàyí challenges the authority of Olúmokò, the feudal Lord. He wants the Òkè Ògún people to gain freedom from the shackles of the feudal lords. He struggles for the people's independence, and eventually the Òkè Ògún people gain independence from the Ọyó.

A ó ẹ ẹrú kú ní bí? Àbí asingbà kò su yín ní? N jé bí kò bá su yín, ó sù èmi ní tẹmi... èmi kò fé kí á sìn asingbà mọ ní. Bí Ọlórún bá sì fé, a kò sì ní sìn ín mọ ...
(o. i. 6)

Are we going to die as serfs in serfdom? Are you not fed up with being serfs? If you are not fed up, I am... I don't want us to remain serfs to the feudal lords. God willing, we shall not remain so.

Thus, Àjàyí challenges the authority of the Ọba. Whereas, Ládélé, in *Ìgbì Ayé Níyí*, affirms the exalted and esteemed position which God places the rulers, the honour and respect that is bestowed on them:

Àwọn Yorùbá ní ọwò tó kọyọyọ láti bù fún Ọba wọn. Àní ìgbàghbọ wọn ní pé Ọlórún l'áyé yí ní Ọba jé fún ilú, bée ní Baálé jé fún ìletò, bée ní Baálé jé fún ọmọ ilé...
(o. i. 3)

The Yorùbá have a lot of respect for their Ọba. Their belief is that the Ọba is God on earth for the town. So is the Baálé for the village and so is the Baálé to the members of his household.

4.6. The democratic dispensation

Abrams (1981:109) says modernity involves a deliberate and radical break with the traditional bases. Ajélétí (2002:13) defines modernism as having to do with recent things and changes that occur within a system. Ajeleti describes it as the introduction of new things into a system. This brought about the new democratic

dispensation which is now being emphasised over other forms of governance such as monarchy and military administration.

Microsoft Student Encarta (2007) explains that the term democratic governance is a recent development and has its root in Western cultures. Democratic governance is a representative government. It is a form of government in which the people freely elect representatives to govern them. In it, everyone has a say in making major decisions. Democracy is the nomenclature of a constitution in which the poorer people called 'demos' exercised power in their own interest as against the interest of the rich and aristocratic. It is a participatory government. Right from the grass roots or the local government, the people elect their leaders. There are also legislative members who are elected into different states of Houses of Assembly.

Owólabí, in *Ọ̀tẹ̀ N'ìbò*, depicts governance in the light of elective and democratic form of governance. But he is quick to go back in time to remind us that:

*Kí Ọ̀yìn bó tó gòkè odò, àwọn Ọ̀ba, Baálẹ̀. Ijòyè ní múa ẹ̀
ètò ijoba agbègbè wọn... bí Ọ̀ba bá ti lè pẹ̀ àwọn ijòyè rẹ̀
jọ, kò sí bírà tí wọn kò lè dá tán. Ọ̀ba á wò sùnsùn, á gbé
esẹ̀ lẹ̀ obìnrin tó bá wùú. Ijòyè á wò sùnsùn, á pàṣẹ̀ wàá bí
ó ti wùú... ayé fà mí létè kí n tutọ̀ ni wọn n jẹ...*

(o. i. 1)

Before the Whiteman arrived the shores, the Ọ̀bas, Baálẹ̀s, Chiefs were in charge of the governance and administration of their domains. When the Ọ̀ba surmoned the chiefs, there was nothing they could not do, the Ọ̀ba might take over any woman he liked, the chief might just command and proclaim orders as he wished... They ruled their domains according to their whims and caprices ...

The novelist discusses the processes of democratic governance and representative government. He dwells on democracy and its processes from nomination to campaigning and proper election. He also discusses the party activities and the rivalry among party members and co-aspirants. He does not, however, fail to point to the shortcomings of democratic government. Though it is an all inclusive form of governance, it is not without its faults and flaws:

Ọ̀rọ̀ dī ọ̀rọ̀ ìbò, ìbò dẹ̀, ọ̀tẹ̀ dé! Tu làá mú, ta làá jù

sílẹ̀? Ta ní kò kún ojú òsìwón, irú òsìwón wó?... (o. i. 13)

It is now a matter of votes, voting brings along with it intrigues! Whom do we pick, whom do we drop? Who is not competent and what criteria do we use?

These were the questions that arised with the emergence of democracy in Yorùbá society. Democracy also came with political thuggery, rancour and acrimony. But as soon as a winner emerges, he becomes a respected and honourable member of the society. This is depicted by Owólábí (1988) when he says :

*Kòsókọ tí dí ọ̀rẹ́ Ọ̀yínbò, ó tí dí asòfín, ó tí dí eni tí terú tọmọ
ń bú iyì fún láàrín ìghoro. Bí ó bá tí yọ lóókán, 'Họnarẹ̀bù' ní
wọ́n ń pè é... (o. i. 20).*

Kòsókọ has become a friend of the whites, he has become a legislator, he has become one that is honoured by all and sundry. As he comes along the road, 'Honourable' is what he is called ...

The novel *Ọ̀tẹ́ N'ibò* traces the history of democracy in Nigeria and Yorùbáland from its inception to the Second Republic. Its attendant prospects and problems, merits and demerits are fully exposed in this work of art. The same political situation is recorded by Akínládé in his novel titled *Sàngbá fọ́*, which depicts partisan politics and the unbecoming attitude of politicians. He discusses the formation of political parties, campaign strategies and the voting system. He also beams his searchlight on thuggery and violence in the process of election and electioneering. He places Adéníyí against Adélańwá, his political rival, both of whom are presidential aspirants under the umbrella of Ẹ̀gbé Ẹ̀lẹ́ja and Ẹ̀gbé Ẹ̀lẹ́ye, respectively. The novel can be said to have fictionally traced the real life situation in the Second Republic with the political thuggery, violence, election rigging and the corrupt attitude of politicians that are discussed in the novel. Adéníyí and his Ẹ̀lẹ́ja Party represent the late Chief Ọ̀báfẹ́mi Awólówọ́ and his Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN) in real life situation. Alhaji Shehu Uthman Shagari and his National Party of Nigeria (NPN) are represented by Ẹ̀gbé Ẹ̀lẹ́ye. Incidentally, the symbol of the NPN is Ẹ̀ye (A bird). This representation may be intentional on the part of the novelist. The novel also portrays politicians, especially the winning parties, as not

necessarily being the most popular, but those which have the power of incumbency and enough money to dole out. Such winning party must also have a lot of political thugs, social miscreants and hooligans who do not only threaten to use fetish substances, weapons and ammunition, but are quick to use such, when the need arises and the price is right.

In the novels as well as in real life situations, thugs kill, maim and commit other heinous crimes against rival party members during campaigns and elections. Sometimes political assassinations are also carried out by politicians. This is further described by the take-off campaign between Egbé Èlèyẹ and Egbé Èlẹja of Àrikógbón country.

Péki ni wón pàdé mótò Egbé Èlẹyẹ! Okò akẹrù ni wón kókó ẹ bí ó n bọ. Afí bí wón ẹ rí eyẹ gágàrà tó wà lára mótò náà. Tó fẹrẹ lẹ máa sọrò. Adéníyí yára fí mótò tirẹ dábiú ònà, kí mótò Egbé Èlẹyẹ má lẹ rí ibi kọja, kí àwọn èniyàn tó wà nímú mótò Egbé Èlẹyẹ tó hẹrẹ ohun tó dé, àwọn giripá Èlẹja tí kí Olóri wón mólẹ, wón wá sí ìta, wón sì ẹé bí ọx ti n ẹ ojú. Okan lára wón fẹ ẹ akọ, sùghón Ọgidán tó jẹ olóri Ẹsọ fún Adéníyí sùnmó okunrin náà, ó sì fí òrùka ẹrẹ lúú, iyẹn sì súbú lulé, ó n yọ ifòòfò lénú, àwọn yòókù tóká, ó di bóò lọ, o yà fún mí.

(o. i. 8)

Unexpectedly, they ran into Egbé Èlẹyẹ's vehicle! They had initially thought it was a truck that was coming along, until they saw the logo of a large bird that looked so real on its side. Adéníyí quickly crossed the road with his vehicle so that Èlẹyẹ's vehicle would not be able to move further. Before the occupants of Èlẹyẹ's vehicle knew what was happening, the henchmen of Èlẹja had manhandled Èlẹyẹ's leader, they dragged him out of the vehicle, and beat him mercilessly. One of them wanted to struggle with them, but Ọgidán, who is the Chief security officer of Adéníyí, moved closer to the man and hit him with a magic ring, and the man fell down and began to foam. Others dispersed and ran helter-skelter.

This vividly describes the kind of treatment that is usually meted out to the opposition during electioneering campaigns. Party leaders also blackmail their opponents in a campaign of calumny. Chief Fálàná, a contestant under the Èlẹyẹ party, condemns the opposing party thus:

Kò sí ohun tí n jẹ Èlẹja ní Ípinlẹyí. Kò sí àyè fún irú egbé játi játi bẹẹ lọdọ wa. Egbé játijáti tí kò ní èniyàn àtátà...

(o. i. 12)

There is nothing like Èlèja party in this State. There is no place for such a useless party in our domain: a useless party that does not have credible members...

But for luck, political thugs of Ègbé Èléyè almost set Adéyemí, who is the director of programmes of Ègbé Èlèja, ablaze in his house. Besides the fact that they burnt his house, the law enforcement agents refuse to assign a police officer to his house for protection, because he is in opposition to the incumbent ruling party.

In the novel, *Sàngbà fò*, it is found that in financing political parties, members sometimes embark on fund raising knowing fully well that, once their party wins the election, the members will be in full charge of the government coffers. This aptly describes the practise of democracy in Nigeria, which is about the winner takes all. This becomes obvious when Adéníyì reiterates that:

Òké márùn-ún-lé láadojò náirà ni a máa ná sí ihò yí. Owó púpò ni, sìghòn tí a bà wólé tùn, owó kànyìn kànyìn lúsán ni èyí yòò jé fún eghé wa. Tí ijoba àpapò bá bọ sí wa lówò ara yòò dè wá nítorí gbogbo dúkiá Orílẹ̀-èdè yí yòò bọ sáhé àṣe wa... (o. i. 19).

We are going to spend about three million, one hundred thousand naira only (₦3,100,000.00) for the forthcoming election. This is a lot of money. But if we win the election, the amount is so little compared to what we will have in our party. If the central government is under our control, we will find things easy because all the wealth of the nation will be in our charge...

Sometimes, politicians employ threat and blackmail to extort money from public office holders, politicians and citizenry, as exemplified in the character of Lánróyè who sends a hoodlum to Chief Ọdúnlámi to demand a huge sum of twenty-five thousand naira (₦25, 000.00). He says:

A rán ni láti sọ fún yín pé, bí ẹ bà fé kí àpéjọ eghéyín tí ẹ fé ṣe ní Gbòngan Odúduwà parí lójú ẹmí Adéníyì, kí ẹ fún mí ní eghèrín méèlógbòn náirà. (o. i. 102).

I am sent to inform you that, if you want your party's forthcoming congress, billed to take place at Odúduwà Hall, to come to an end with Adéníyì alive, give a sum of twenty-five thousand naira to me ...

In spite of the fact that Egbé Eléja gives service and dividend of democracy to the populace, during a campaign, Adényi posits that its party's ability to win in the forth-coming election, is still subject to the electorates's decision.

Ó bá wón sòrò àìsèdédédé e ijoha Egbé Eléye, níbi ijoha àpapò àti àwọn Ijoha Ipínlè... Ó wá ké sí àwọn olùdìhò pé nínú ìdìbò tí n' bọ, kí wón má ẹ̀ dìbò fún Egbé Eléye rara. Egbé Eléja ni kí wón dìbò fún... kí wón lè ní ijoha rere, aásìkí àti idàgbàsókè isé ajé ní Orílẹ̀-Èdè náà. (o. i. 121)

He spoke to them about the shortcomings of Egbé Eléye at the federal and state levels ... He called on voters that in the coming election, they should not vote for Egbé Eléye at all. They should vote for Egbé Eléja... in order to have good governance, wealth and progressive economic activities in the country.

The above reveals that politicians make promises to people, and the promises are hardly fulfilled when they get into offices. In mentioning atrocities being committed by the ruling Egbé Eléye, Adényi says:

Oríṣíríṣí ìvà àìtító tí n' wáyé nínú àwọn kòòtù ibílẹ̀, níbi tó jé àwọn alátiléyìn Egbé Eléye ni wón yàn bí adájó, tí wón kò fí òdodo ẹ̀ yàtọ̀ sí kí wón máa gba rihá, kí wón máa gba owó éyìn, kí wón máa ẹ̀ idájó èpè nípa gbìgbé èbi fún aláre àti àre fún ẹ̀lẹ̀bi. (o. i. 121).

Different acts of indiscipline are carried out in the court, where Egbé Eléye's loyalists are judges that are corruptible as they take bribe, kick-backs and pervert the course of justice by acquitting the guilty and convicting the innocent.

Eléye party members also encourage acts of indiscipline. For instance, when Ìdòwú meets Òjó, he says:

Ẹ̀ tí ará ilú ni ìwọ̀ ndù tàbí tí ara ẹ̀? Bí èmí bá tí rí jẹ, tí ìdílẹ̀ mí sí n' ẹ̀ yótòmì, àṣeyorí niyẹn... kíí ẹ̀ gbogbo èniyàn ilú ni a lè sọ dí aláásìkí... (o. i. 124).

Are you struggling for the people or yourself ...
As long as I am okay, my family members are enjoying,
That is success... all citizens cannot be wealthy.

Ìdòwú replies,

Tó bá rí bé ẹ̀, iwọ̀ kíí ẹ̀ ọ̀sẹ̀lú, ọ̀jẹ̀lú ni iwọ̀... (o. i. 124)

If that is so, you are not a politician, you are a looter.

The author clearly shows that it is not the best party or well-meaning aspirants that are necessarily voted into power. Instead, the wealthiest politicians and those who have the machinery and the wherewithal to rig elections, especially the incumbents, employ the state machinery to steal funds and buy their way through. The highest bidders, not the best parties, win elections. Thus, *Sàngbà fò* depicts the flaws in democratic governance in Yorùbá society.

Owólabí, in *Ọ̀tẹ̀ N'ìbò*, also corroborates these. The title of the novel aptly describes what happens during elections and electioneering campaigns. It reveals the crude methods that are being employed during campaigns and voting proper. It discusses the deceit, indiscipline, untruthfulness, hooliganism, rigging and the like that are common and rampant in our polity.

Ọ̀lábímtán further reveals in *Bàbá Rere* all the misbehaviour and negative dispositions that are inherent in our politicking. He condemns the self-servicing and pretentious attitudes of politicians in *Bàbá Rere*. In the novel, Balógun pretends to be a father of all, a philanthropist par excellence and a problem-solver to all. His acts are deliberate, as he has political ambition. He therefore, uses his resources and all the machinery within his powers to intimidate Sohó electorate to vote for his Tọ̀baláṣẹ̀ Party. He seems to be eulogized by all, but his inordinate ambition enables him to suppress the opposition within the Teachers' Association, when the body stands against his popular policies. Balógun later retaliates by clamping down on the Association and withdrawing the benefits hitherto enjoyed by them. Ọ̀lábímtán portrays how teachers are treated, cheated and punished with how they are denied their rights under fake pretences. When teachers fall out of Balógun favours, he uses the lawmakers to promulgate laws against teachers:

... èkínní, a ó sòfin pé kí gbogbo àwọn tíṣà tí kò kà
ju ìwé méfà lọ máa sanwó ilé tí wọn n gbé... Èkejì, àwọn omọ
tíṣà gbọdọ máa san owó ilé-ìwé. Èketa, bí gbogbo omọ tí tíṣà
kan n kọ́ lórún kan kò bá yege nínú idánwò, tíṣà náà kò ní
gha èkúnwó odún. Èkerin, a ó Ẹ é lófin fáwọn tíṣà pé wọn ó
gbọdọ kó ara wọn jo Ẹ eghé kan. Èkarun, tíṣà ó gbọdọ Ẹ ilú,
kò sì gbọdọ gbé àpótí ibò. Èkẹfà, eèkan lórún ní tíṣà yíò máa
gha isinmi... (o. i. 180).

... first, we shall legislate that all teachers who hold First School Leaving Certificate should pay house rent... Second, teachers' children should pay schools fees... Third, if all the pupils a teacher teaches in one session do not pass their examination, the teacher will not receive annual increment. Fourth, we shall promulgate into law that teachers should not gather up together to form any association. Fifth, teachers should not be involved in partisan politics, they should also not seek elective positions. Sixth, teachers will only go on leave once a year.

The real reason Balógun turns against teachers is that the teachers did not congratulate him when he was given an honorary degree from a university headed by his friend who solicited for funds to build a university complex. The teachers feel he does not deserve it.

Balógun sì ɛ b'ò ti wí lóòótó. Okàn ìmoore yí ni ọrẹ rẹ fí hàn, tí ó sì jẹ kí yunifásitì rẹ fún un l'óyè. Bí okàn nínú olórí àwọn tíṣà ɛ ghó ni Sohó kò yé Balógun, ó sì dùn-ún púpò pé wón n fí òun ɛ yèyè rẹ... (o. i. 182).

Balógun fulfilled his promise. His friend shows his gratitude by making his university confer an honorary degree on him. How one of the head teachers in Sohó knew about it remains a surprise, it pains him that he is being scorned by the teachers...

In *Bàbá Rere*, the novelist dwells on the roles media practitioners play in promoting and making political programmes successful. Thus, the significance of the media in any political dispensation cannot be over-emphasised.

Ìgbìmò wa n dúpé gidigidi lówó yín fún isé nlá-nlá tí ẹ n ɛ. Àwa mọ rírì isé yìí. Ní orilẹ̀ èdè kòrìlẹ̀-èdè tí a bá yọ̀ tí àwọn oníwě-ìròhìn kúrò, àti ghé orí Orilẹ̀ Èdè ọ̀hún kù sówó Olórún. Nítorí náà gbogbo wa, gégé bí oníwě-ìròhìn àti àwa gégé bí ìgbìmò tí n ɛ l'ọ̀ba, ghòdò wà ní iréyọ̀ kí a sì máa fowósowópò fún idàghàsókè ilẹ̀ wa. Kò sí idáwókò kan tí ẹ̀ lè rí lát' ọ̀dọ̀ wa. Ẹ̀ sì mọ̀ dájú pé, kí nì kan kò lé ɛ oníwě-ìròhìn kan ní lẹ̀ yìí... (o. i. 169)

Our committee expresses its gratitude to you for the hard work you do. We appreciate the importance of your work. In any country that plays down the roles of the journalists, it is only God that can make it possible for such a country to progress. Therefore, all of you journalists, and those of us that are in government must be in accord and co-operate for the development of our country. You shall not meet

any opposition from our side. You know quite well
that no evil shall befall any journalist in this country...

The function of the media in governance is also presented by Owólabí, the novelist as a body that plays an important role of a watchdog and custodian of good governance in the society. This role can be played negatively or otherwise, depending on the actors. Hence, Owólabí accuses media practitioners of partaking in bad governance by praise singing bad actors in government.

*Rédiò a kòrin yìn in yàà, tẹlifisàn á sọrọ rẹ bí igbá kejì Olórún,
àwọn iwé iròyìn a sọ fún un pé k'ò fi isù kaná, t'òbẹ kò sòro.*
(o. i. 32)

Radio (broadcasters) sing his praise, television (broadcasters) talk of him as a deputy to God, journalists also tell him that he should move ahead there is no hinderance. Musicians are also not left out of the sycophancy.

*Àlào jé kí wọn ó máa hù ọ, àwọn ẹlẹnu bí Ògún wọlẹ l'ágbèdẹ,
òsìkà b'enu yààbù bí enu sòkòtò. Àlào, tiẹ l'àwá n sẹ. A ò l'ẹni
mẹjì láì sẹ'wọ. Àlào, iwọ ni baba wa...* (o. i. 32)

Àlào, let them rain abuses on you, their mouths are like the Ògún pierced ground in the blacksmith shed, evil doers, their mouths as wide as trousers' mouth. Àlào, we are on your side. We have no one but you. Àlào, you are our father...

Such is the hypocrisy displayed by sycophants who encourage him and give him the impression that all is well. The role played by the law-enforcement agents in electioneering processes and democratic governance cannot be overemphasized. Since democracy adheres to constitution and the rule of law, the law enforcement agencies play a very crucial role in enforcing compliance and obedience to the rule of law. This fact is abused by politicians who make use of the police to carry out their nefarious activities. The police collude with politicians and their parties in rigging elections in favour of the incumbent government or the highest bidder. This is shown in the speech of Balógun. The collaboration of the electorate and teachers who serve as returning officers are also presented thus:

*Okàn Balógun kúkú ti balẹ pé òun kò ní sàì wọlé ni, ó ti
sètò bí yìò ti fi ọkọ akó-èrò méfà ránṣẹ sí Ikejà, Ògùnpa ...
láti máa kó èrò wá dibò láì sanwó ọkọ. Áádóta kòbò ni owó
enìkòṣkan tó há lọ dibò, ọkọ tí ó há bálo ni yìò sí tún bá*

padà lófè. Léyìn èyí, ó tún tí ǵetò pèlú àwọn tí ǵà tí yíò ka ibò hí ìwé-ibò àwọn omọ eghé Tòbalàṣe yíò ǵe lé. Òkòòkan nímú wọn ló sì tí mò pé, hí Balógun àti àwọn omọ eghé bá tí wólé, náirà márùn-ún ní t'òun. Àwọn Olóṣá wáyí o, tí mulẹ̀ pèlú eghé Tòbalàṣe. Wón sì tí pinnu láti máa ghé àwọn tí ó jé alátìlẹ̀hìn eghé Sohó Parapò ní ibi-ibò, kí wón má baa rójú orísirísi tí àwọn tí n ka ibò yíò ǵe... Yàtò sí èyí, Balógun tí bá gbogbo àwọn òsìsẹ̀ rẹ̀ ǵe ipàdẹ̀, enikòòkan yíò sì dìbò lẹ̀mẹ̀jìmẹ̀jì. Àwọn omọ ilé ìwé rẹ̀ tó ga dáadáa pàápàá gba ìwé-ibò, àwọn náà sì tí míra láti dìbò... (o. i. 135)

Balógun is confident that he is going to win, he has made provision on how to send six buses to Ikeja, Ògúnpa... to take voters to polling stations free of charge. Also, each voter will get fifty kobo (50k) for voting, he will also be conveyed back by the same vehicle that takes him to the venue for free. Besides, he has also made an arrangement with the teachers, who are going to be officials, they are to increase the number of votes cast for Tòbalàṣe Party. Each of the official has also known that he is to get a sum of five naira (₦5) once Balogun and his party members win the election. The police is into a pact with Èlẹ̀yẹ Party. They have decided to arrest the representatives of Sohó Parapò at polling booths, so that they will not be able to witness different kinds of atrocities that will be committed by the enumerators. Besides these, Balógun has also held a meeting with his employees, each one of them will cast his vote twice. The tall ones among the pupils in the school he established also have voters' cards, they are also prepared to cast votes ...

Democracy and the rule of law, though a foreign system of government have become a part of the Yorùbá tradition.

4.7. Military governance

Military governance is alien to our culture. It is another foreign institution that has influenced our society. *International Encyclopedia of the Social Sciences* (1968) defines military governance as a belligerent exercise through its armed forces of governmental powers in the conquered and occupied territory of another nation. It is said to presuppose actual, effective, physical control of the territory in question and ability to impose on the inhabitants the will of the military commander.

Military governments are easily formed in times of political crises. They are the product of an intervention in the political arena aimed at displacing disliked politicians and calling for a new election. They do not enjoy the support from the civil society except in a severely polarized situation.

Ukpokolo (2004) explicates that military governance was introduced into the Nigeria polity shortly after the attainment of the nation's hard-earned independence in 1960. Precisely, on January 15, 1966, some group of soldiers hijacked the power of leadership under the guise of patriotism of ethnic motivation. This action later plunged the country into a bloody civil war between 1967 and 1970 and since Nigeria was under the dictatorship of military juntas till May 29, 1999, when the Third Republic began.

In *Ijànba Sèlú*, Owólabí discusses the process of assuming political power through military intervention. He presents Àjùwòn right from his school days till he graduated from a foreign military college. While in training, he promised to go back to his country to improve the lot of the country and its citizens.

The military seize power by exploiting the opportunities provided them by the political ruling class. Given the slightest opportunity they would seize power. This is exactly what Àjùwòn does:

Ètò òsèlú kò lọ déédé mó, ijàngbòn n bẹ láàrin àwọn èniyàn ilú, ilé sísun, èniyàn pípa, títe òfin lójú gba ilú kan... Àwọn egbé òsèlú n dojú ijà kọ ara wọn... Parí parí gbogbo rẹ, àwọn ológun rí èyí, wọn sì fa ibọn yọ, wọn lé àwọn òsèlú kúrò lóri àléfà ijọba... Ijọba bó sí owó ológun, lèhìn ipàdánù emí àti fífi nríkan ìní sòfò. (o. i. 22).

Civilian rule was no longer peaceful, there was chaos among the citizens. Arsons murder and break down of law hold sway... Political party members engaged themselves in physical attacks... Most of all, the military observed this, they picked up their guns and drove out the politicians from the seat of power... the military thus seized power after the loss of several lives and properties.

Given the chaotic situation on ground, the citizens welcome the intervention of the military in the politics of the country.

*Lákòókò, ghogho ará ilú ló fì ara mó ètò ifipágbàjòba yí
nítorí ghogho èniyàn ní òfù àti òlúà igbà náà tí sù pátápátá.*
(o. i. 28)

Initially, every citizen accepted the seizure of power because everyone was tired of the prevailing situation at the time.

After the coup and consequent seizure of power, the coupists chose Àjùwòn as the new leader of the country.

*Àwòn ipéèrè ológun wò yíká, wòn sì mú Àjùwòn gégé
bí asáájú wòn.* (o. i. 28)

The middle-ranking military officers chose Àjùwòn as their leader.

After a period of time, Àjùwòn also becomes corrupt and negligent. All the institutions and the top government officials become corrupt, gross indiscipline and violation of the rule of law take over. This agrees with the maxim, 'power corrupts, but absolute power corrupts absolutely! This can be said to be the true picture of the government led by Àjùwòn.

*Àjùwòn omọ bàbá ijọ tó tí jẹ olóòtọ láti kékeré ní ó wá dì ẹni
tí n fì ojú fọ ijekújẹ bí ẹni pé kò jẹ nńkan ibi... Agbára mà le o.*
(o. i. 31)

Àjùwòn, the son of a cleric that has once been honest from youth has now become one that overlooks mismanagement and corruption as if it is not a bad thing... power can be intoxicating.

In spite of the fact that bribery, corruption and nepotism are institutionalized by Àjùwòn's government, the co-actors, that is, the ministers, commissioners and so on play on, as if nothing is amiss:

*Ju ghogho rẹ lọ, àwòn nńkan burúki tí ó n ba ilú jẹ gha
òde kan, owó ẹhìn àti rihá tilẹ tí kúrò l'ówó ẹhìn, ó tí di
owó iwájú... Bí èniyàn bá fẹ wọ ísé, tí kò mọ èniyàn, irọ
lásán gbàà ní.* (o. i. 33)

Above all, bad things which spoil the country are rampant. Bribery and corruption have become a common thing, they are now fashionable... Applicants are not employed except they have a god father.

This misrule is the practice until there is a counter-coup and another military junta overthrows Àjúwòn's government. Táyése becomes the head of government, thus discipline, transparency and good governance which have eluded the country are restored. The populace welcomes and accepts the new government and gives it full support:

*Ghogbo èniyàn tí ó tí tàpá sí àwọn ijoba olubi l'àná ní ó
fèràn ijoba tuntun yí dé ibi géé. wòn a sì máa fì ighà
ghogbo yín in-l'òsàn-án àti l'óru. (o. i. 45)*

The citizens who have opposed the former bad government, embrace the new government. As such, they always praise the Táyése government day and night.

By this assertion, it has become apparent that people do not really mind those who actually rule them, or the type of government in power, as long as they are well governed. Paramount in the people's minds is justice, security, good governance, and a land where equal opportunities are given to the citizens, where progress and peace reign.

CHAPTER FIVE

CULTURE ORTHODOXY IN RELIGION AND ECONOMY

5.0 Introduction

This chapter examines the orthodoxy in Yorùbá system of worship, belief and economy. The chapter examines Yorùbá orthodox religion as it was practised in the pre-colonial days, and before the advent of the missionaries. It also considers the emergence of the two prominent foreign religions, Christianity and Islam, vis-à-vis the traditional Yorùbá religion, as they are discussed in Yorùbá novels. The chapter also investigates economy in Yorùbá culture vis-a-vis land acquisition, food crops, live stock keeping, medicine and pharmacy, hunting and fishing, and other professions.

5.1 Religion

Pacten (2008) says the word 'religion' is derived from the Latin noun 'religio', which denotes earnest observance of ritual obligations and an inward spirit of reverence. According to him, religion covers a wide spectrum of meanings that reflect the enormous variety of ways the term can be interpreted.

According to Hastings in Adeniji (2008), religion is described as "man's" relation to that which he regards as "holy". Religion can, therefore, be described as "the complete or total belief system of a given people". The *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* defines religion as the belief in supernatural power, (creator and controller of the universe) who has given man a spiritual nature which continues to exist after the death of the body. Hastings (1917) is of the opinion that:

Religion is the opium of the masses created and dominated by the ruling class of the society with the aim of providing moral pressure and psychology outlet which preserved the class structure.

Marx not only traced the sources of religion in any society but also its essence. Adeniji (2008:6) avers that religion seems to make life tolerable for the oppressed in the society. In his opinion, religion is as natural to man as other essential dimensions of the human nature. It stands to inject fundamental and ultimate

explanation and meaning into human existence and life itself. Smith (1964) approaches the issue of religion in a more scientific manner:

A religion or the religions of the people may be defined as a set of institutionalized rituals identified with tradition and expressing and or evoking social sentiment directed at divine focus seen in the context of the human phenomenon, logical environment at least partially described by myths and doctrine.

Certain peculiarities highlighted in this definition make it obvious that there are religions and each is peculiar to a people, and each has a set of institutionalized rituals with a purpose. What have been described as rituals can also be referred to as practices which are distinctive to a specific religion. There are different types of religious practises, each proclaiming to be divinely inspired by God. The well-known monotheistic religions in the world include Islam, Christianity and Judaism. Islam is the religion of the Muslims which started at Makkah with its leader Prophet Muhammed who was given the Holy Qur'an as the guide to its followers. Christianity is a way of life named after Jesus Christ at Antioch. All the religions play some vital roles in the development of individuals, the societies and the nations at large.

Many committed believers recognize only their own tradition as a religion, understanding expressions such as worship and prayer to refer exclusively to the practices of their tradition. The Yorùbá practise African traditional religion. Considering the large number of gods in Yorùbáland, one would be amazed at how deeply religious the Yorùbá people are. With the emergence of the missionaries and their activities, Christianity and Islam were introduced into the Yorùbá society. The aftermath of this is that the once-valued African religion came to be regarded as fetish practices. Among the newly converted Christians, the Pentecostal churches are most intolerant of African culture, according to Bámgbósé (2001:9):

Not only are physical symbols of African cultures to be discarded, even innocuous manifestations of African tradition are held up to ridicule. Works of arts such as wood carvings and engravings, paintings, brass sculptures that adorn many homes are being openly condemned as "fetish" or "demonic".

Islamic scholars and advocates are not left out. The Muslims see the traditional religious practice as *Ebo* (sacrifice) and condemn the practitioners. They have no tolerance for traditional practices and, as such, they pose a serious threat to Yorùbá traditional religion. There is an element of hypocrisy in this, because the Alfas also run back to the traditional religion practitioners, once they are boxed into a corner and when they have difficulties that require spiritual solutions. The same thing is applicable in Christianity.

5.1.1. African Traditional Religion

Alana (2004:65) identifies the five core elements that make-up Yorùbá traditional religion to be:

- Belief in God
- Belief in Divinities
- Belief in Spirits
- Belief in Ancestors
- The practices of metaphysics (*idán*) and medicine (*òògùn*)

He adds that the commonest name of God among the Yorùbá is:

Olórun (the owners of the heavens). It is always on the lips of the Yorùbá: in their prayers, in their conversations, in their discussion and sayings... (p 66)

The name “*Olórun*” points to *Gód* as the author of the earth and the heavens. Thus, when the Yorùbá offer supplication or prayer, they end it with ‘*Áṣ*’ (*Amen*). This is contrary to the belief held by most people who have embraced Christianity and Islam that the Yorùbá pray to divinities or gods. According to Alana:

...*Olódùmarè* as both king of both heavens and earth is followed in rank and importance by divinities, then, the spirits, and finally, the ancestors. To reach *Olódùmarè* directly for whatever reason, in the thinking of the Yorùbá amounts to lack of decorum and common etiquette... Ancestors and divinities, especially are believed to be there to convey whatever feelings or message to the Majestic God. The Yorùbá as a mark of respect normally approach God through divinities and ancestors who they believe are his messengers. (p 74)

This was what the traditional religion of the Yorùbá was in the pre-colonial period, and what it still is today among its practitioners. Hence, the Yorùbá approach God Almighty in supplications and prayers through various gods that are in existence in Yorùbá land. According to Alana, the number of these gods range between two hundred and one and seven hundred (201 – 700). In *Kékeré Èkùn*, Olábímtán describes the traditional religion in Aiyéro town thus:

Bì ilé Olúwaiyé tí mbe, bée ni tí Òrìṣà-oko, tí Èṣù kò jìnà sí tí Ògún, bí ènià bá sì wà ní ìgbàlè Eégún, yíò máa wo ìgbó orò ní òkún. Sùgbón nínú ghogbo wón, tí a bá ti mú àwón Onìgbàgbó, àwón Eléégún l'ó kàn nípa ilàjú àti gbajúmò. Àwón Onìgbàgbó kò tó nńkan rárá, iye wón kò sì soro láti mọ.
(o. i. 3)

As we have Olúwaiyé's shrine, so also do we have that of Òrìṣà-oko, Èṣù's shrine is not far from that of Ògún, and Eégún's shrine is within the vicinity of that of orò. But among them all, after the Christians, the Eléégún are next in terms of civilization and popularity. The Christians are not many, it is easy to know how many they are.

Bámgbóṣé (2007:10) points out that prayers are basic ingredients of Yorùbá religion. God is appealed to for help, and his favour is sought before one embarks on any undertaking. He also expresses the view that:

The basic beliefs underlying the actions and attitudes of people in the novels are traditional Yorùbá ones. These include belief in witches and spirits; medicine, charms and sacrifice, and the basic tenets of traditional religion, including the more recent Christian influence on it... Witchcraft is a basic ingredient in the story of Àkàrà-ògún's father...
(o. i. 33)

He also points out that:

The belief in spirits by the Yorùbá is responsible for numerous stories told by Fágúnwà in his novels. Where the hero in *Ògbójú Ode nínú Igbó Irínmalè* encounters spirits, trolls, fairies and gnomes with whom the hero fights belong entirely to the world of fiction. The Yorùbá believe in the existence of spirits of different forms not visible to humans, but which play an important role in their lives. There are spirits of the forest and spirits associated with the 'Awúsá

tree'; walnut tree. *Èbòrà inú 'Ògán'*: The troll associated with the anthill. (p. 8)

It is also believed that these spirits often take on different shapes and appear to humans. The spirits also include those of the dead. It is believed that the dead can re-appear in their former human forms in order to warn or help those they love, as found in *Òghójú Ode*. *Àkàrà-ògùn* calls on the spirit of his dead mother to help him out of a difficult situation.

À! Ìyá mi òwón, ìyá mi tòótó, ìyá tí ó pé, ìyá tí ó ní láárí, ìyá tí ó mú yányán, ìyá tí kii se ìyá lásán, ìyá tí kii se ìyá kékeré, ìyá tí kii se ìyá búburú. Ibikibi tí o bá wà lóní, má sàì jé kí n rí o. Bí mo tí wí báyítán ni ilẹ̀ là pèrẹ̀, ìyá mi sì jáde, ó sì bá mi, tí èmi tí omi lójú... (o. i.p 39)

Ah! My dear mother, my mother indeed, a complete mother, a worthy mother, a brilliant mother, a mother that is not an ordinary mother, a mother that is not of a small measure, a mother that is not a wicked mother... wherever you may be today, let me see you. As soon as I said this, the ground opened and my mother came out of it, she met me with tears rolling down my face...

The hero's dead mother re-appears and intervenes in order to help her son out of a very difficult situation. The use of medicines, charms and incantations are commonplace in Yorùbá traditional society. All the heroes in the *Fágúnwà* novels are armed to the teeth with various medicines, magical charms and herbal drugs which they supplement with incantations. In *Orilawé Àdígún*, *Àlùkò* discusses magic and medicine with *Adé*, he asks:

Kí tilẹ̀ ni à ñ pè ní òògùn? Lójú tẹ̀mi, kò sí ẹ̀ni tí kii se òògùn, bẹ̀ẹ̀ ni kò sì sí ẹ̀ni tí kii lò ó. Alùkò ní; àfi èmi. Iwo wo? Sé o kii jeun, òògùn ebi kó loúnjẹ̀ ni, ẹ̀ máa tan ara yín jẹ̀. Òògùn lòyìnbó se tí tí tó di ẹ̀ni ñ fò lójú ọ̀run, àrà màdà òògùn òyìnbó ló sẹ̀dà amóhùnmáwòran... Mo tilẹ̀ gbà báyii pé àwa náà ní òògùn tíwa, sùghón ẹ̀ má jé ká fi wàlái wé Olórún o. Tí àwọn òyìnbó yátò, ibi kan kó ni wón ti bẹ̀rẹ̀? Ara iwà ọ̀pè tí a máa ñ hù náà niyẹn. Ohun a-bí-wa-bí kii wù wá, tẹ̀ni eléni ló máa ñ yá wa lára. (o. i. 24)

What is called medicine? To me, there is no one who does not partake in medicine, so also there is no one that does not use

it. Àlùkò says, 'Except me.'

You? Don't you eat, isn't food the medicine of hunger, keep deceiving yourself. It is medicine that the whites used until they are able to fly in the sky, it is the mysterious medicine of the whites that manufactured the television...

I now accept that we also have our own medicine, but don't let us compare *walahi* with God. The medicine of the whites differs, didn't they start from somewhere? That is part of our foolish behaviour. We don't appreciate our cultural heritage, we embrace that of other people.

The Yorùbá go to Babaláwo and Oníṣẹ̀gùn for various health and spiritual problems. These problems are solved through the use of herbs, shrubs, leaves and barks of different plants, depending on the nature of ailments. Sometimes, the use of incantations and incisions are employed. At other times, spiritual problems are solved through Ifá divination and offer of sacrifice.

Native medicines are potent in preventive and curative treatments of various ailments which may be physical, emotional and spiritual. But today, majority of the Yorùbá have relegated to the background, the traditional way of treating ailments, especially the elite. The elite prefer to dump the traditional medicine in favour of orthodox drugs which may be lethal. These are mostly imported from abroad. Perhaps, if the elite and the super-rich in Yorùbá society begin to look inward for medical treatment rather than jetting abroad for any slight symptom of ailment, the huge amount of money spent on these trips and medical bills, especially by government officials, may be spent to develop, re-package and refine the indigenous medicine made of herbs, roots, leaves, shrubs, and so on, which do not contain chemicals.

In Yorùbáland, natural plants, and, sometimes, part of animals and birds are processed and added on incisions which mix with the blood instantly to cure ailment. The indigenous composition of drugs from plants that are grown on the native soil can cure the different ailments of the Yorùbá. Nature has provided each nation with materials that are good enough for medicinal treatment of ailments that the people may suffer from. In *Ó Le Kú*, Ìsòlá portrays this hypocrisy on the part of both Christians and Muslims. The reaction of 'Bòdé, Àjàní's elder brother, on the issue of the right choice of partner for Àjàní, illustrates this:

*Bóràn bá sì wá rí bá'yí, ó ní ohun tí àwọn baba wá máa ń
 ṣ. Olórún má jẹ́ kágbà tán lórílẹ̀. Ọ̀dò àwọn àgbà la máa
 lọ. A ó lọ wo nr̄kan sí i.
 ...Àwọn Babaláwo kán wà tó ríran gidí. Ohun tí mo rí ni, kò
 sí wá-ká-tẹ̀ ní bẹ̀. Ó dájú tójó òní. (o. i. 38).*

When things turn out this way, there is something our fathers do. May we never lack elders on earth. We have to contact the elders. We have to go for consultation. ...There are Ifa practitioners that can see into the future. It is what I have seen. there is no secrecy about it. It is as sure as this day.

This shows that the Yorùbá, albeit in secrecy, contact the African Traditional Religion practitioners when they face serious predicaments. Sometimes, we see novelists making use of *Eṣe Ifá* (Ifá verses). Ifá is consulted at the time of trouble. In *Kékeré Èkùn*, Àyàwó goes to consult the Ifá oracle when she could not bear any more children. In *Ó le kú*, Bòdé consults the Ifá oracle as well in order to help Àjàní, his brother, to choose the best suitor in marriage.

In *Jé Ng L'ògbà Tèmi*, Ládélé displays the ethical and religious significance of cultural mix. The novelist presents modern values as a violation of Yorùbá traditional values. In Ọ̀wo village, in the nineteen forties, Bánkólé, like Bádéjò of Aiyéro, is a notable actor in the Egúngún cult. Bánkólé embraces Christianity despite all antagonism. He becomes well-known and revered among the congregation. However, his wife becomes embittered and a strong force of antagonism as Bánkólé is poisoned by his wife and becomes ill. His illness is said to be a consequence of his action of abandonment of the worship of ancestral gods and acceptance of Christianity which is offensive to the ancestral gods. He has to make atonement to the gods as an antidote. He makes the atonement and eventually stops attending both church and Egúngún cult meetings. Consequently, Christianity is made to succumb to the traditional religion:

*Bí ó tilẹ̀ jẹ́ pé Bánkólé kò lọ sí ẹ̀ṣọ̀sì mó, tí ara rẹ̀ sì ti balẹ̀
 dáadáa: síbẹ̀ kò kọ̀ ibi ara sí ti eégún síṣe mó, kò tilẹ̀ bá
 wọn forí kan èkù mó. Inú àwọn ará ilú dùn sí èyí níwọ̀n*

*ìgbà tí kò tí lẹ sí sòsò mọ: tí ó sì ñ ẹbọ. tí ó ñ rùbọ nígbà-
kuùgbà tí ẹbọ bá yá sí i lára. (o. i. 21)*

Though Bánkólé no longer goes to church, and has fully recovered from his illness; still, he no longer involves himself in Egúngún cult, he no longer performs as a masquerade. The town people are happy about this, as long as he equally no longer attends the church; as long as he continues to offer sacrifices whenever he feels like offering it.

It is worthy of note that the traditional religion practitioners remain sincere to their religion and religious tenets. They are loyal to the gods and divinities; they stick to their deities. They do not engage in "religious adultery". We can, therefore, conclude that the Yorùbá traditional religion, though practised by few people nowadays, is not totally ruled out of the lives of the Yorùbá; it is inherent in them as a way of life in spite of the infiltration of foreign religions into the Yorùbá society. In *Kékeré Èkìn*, Bádéjọ stuck to the òjẹ cult completely until he decides to convert to Christianity.

*Bádéjọ ní òn kii ẹ onígbàgbọ, bẹẹ ní òn kii ẹ imàlẹ. Ó ní
òjẹ ní òn sùgbón òn sì tí fì egbé òjẹ náà silẹ nítorí ijà tí ó
ẹlẹ l'áǎrín àwọn. Àlùfáà sì bí í bí ó bá fé di onígbàgbọ,
pélú itara ní Bádéjọ sì fì dáhùn pé òn tí múra tán láti ẹ
ìgbàgbọ. (o. i. 15)*

Bádéjọ said he was neither a Christian nor a Muslim. He said he belonged to the òjẹ cult, but that he had also denounced his membership of the òjẹ cult because of a fight that broke out among them. The priest asked him if he wanted to be converted to Christianity and he replied with zeal in the affirmative, that he was ready to become a Christian.

Some other people, might decide to practise Christianity alongside traditional religion, which he has just been introduced into. In *Kékeré Èkìn*, Olábimtán makes Àlábí, the protagonist in the novel, to condemn African Traditional Religion in favour of his newly imbibed foreign religion, Christianity. While he sermonizes on the pulpit in Church, he says:

*Ìgbàgbọ kii ya èrẹ, ìgbàgbọ kii bọrìsà. Olúwa ní fún 'ni l'ómọ,
ẹ má bọ 'gi bọ'pẹ nítorí àti-bímọ, ẹ má sì fì igi rópò ìbejì nýn
tí ó há kú. Olúwa ní ñsómọ. Ẹ má sọ omọ di igi, omọlánígidi*

*ni èrè ibejì, onìgbàgbò kò ghòdò yà. Ènyìn ará, ẹ má máa sọ
 igi d'omọ. Igi tí a ya l'òbẹ tí kò lè sòrò, tí a fún l'ómì, tí kò lè
 mu, tí a fún l'òhje, tí kò lè jẹ, igi tí a fi síná tí n'jó tí kò lè ké,
 ẹ eléyìni ni òrìṣà? Ẹ òrìṣà tí a fi síná tí kò lè yọ ara rẹ
 kúrò, òrìṣà tí ebi n'pa tí a fún ní ohje tí kò lè jẹ, ni yíò fi ohje
 fún elébi. (o. i. 67)*

A Christian does not make idols, he does not worship idols. It is God that gives children, don't worship trees in order to have children. Do not substitute an idol for your dead twins. It is God that gives children. Don't turn children into images. The carved Ibeji idol is but an effigy. A Christian must not carve it. Brethren, don't turn idols into children. The idol that is shaped with a knife but cannot talk. The one that is given food, but cannot eat. The idol that is put in a burning fire, but cannot cry, is that a god? The god that is put in a burning fire, but cannot free itself from it. Is it the god that is hungry and food is given to it but cannot eat it that will provide food for the hungry?

The protagonist in the above novel thus condemns African Traditional Religion in favour of Christianity. He talks as if it is the images or effigies (or òrìṣàs) that the Yorùbá worship as God, and not that they only make sacrifice to the òrìṣàs and see them as the go-between.

In traditional Yoruba society, each family had its own òrìṣà that it worshipped out of the deities available in the society. For instance, when Àdùfẹ, in the novel *Kékeré Èkùn*, goes to consult the Babaláwo, in order to bear a child, she is asked about the god that is worshipped in her husband's family:

*Irú òrìṣà wo ni nwón mbo n'ilé oko re?
 Onìgbàgbò l'oko mi, kii b'òrìṣà. (o. i. 81)*

Which god do they worship in your husband's house?
 My husband is a Christian; he is not an idol worshipper.

*Ọrẹ Àdùfẹ bii pé:
 Ání kí wón tó di onìgbàgbò, irú òrìṣà wo ni wón n'sin (o. i. 88)*

Àdùfẹ's friend asked her:
 Before they became Christians, which god did they worship?

Ládélé also condemns African Traditional Religions in *Jé Ng Lò'ghà Tèmi*, when he makes a priest say:

*Nitorinàà, isé òkinkim ni isé àwọn ahòrisà. Níní èsìn
ìgbàghò, kò sí àwò, kò sí ògbèrì. Bákanaà ni gbogbo wá rí.
Ìgbàghò kò l'áwò; ìgbàghò kò l'èèwò. Ìgbàghò kii jin ara
wọn lésè. Ifé ni àwa fì mbá ara wa lò... (o. i. 8 – 9)*

As a result of this, the activities of traditional religion practitioners are that of darkness. In Christianity, there is neither initiates nor non-initiates. We are all the same. The Christians do not belong to any guild; Christians have no taboo. Christians are not hypocrites. We relate with one another lovingly.

This is the extent to which the foreign religion practitioners would defend the newly imported religions against the traditional religions. Àdúfè challenges Bádéjò in *Kékeré Èkùn* on the sacrifices prescribed for her by the herbalist she consulted:

*Onìgbàghò ni nyìn, onìgbàghò ni nyìn.
A sà n rí àwọn àlùfàà tí nse aájò... (o. i. 83)*

You claim that you are a Christian.
But we see clergymen who patronize herbalists

In Ìṣòlá's *Ó Le Kú*, buttressed this fact when Àjàní tells 'Bòdé that:

*Ṣé ẹ̀ mò pé ẹ̀pè lẹ̀pẹ̀lẹ̀pẹ̀ àwọn wòlù èké wònyí nìlò? Bàhá
Aláàfàà kan sọ fún wa pé, òun á máa se tírà fún àwọn
wòlù, lórulóru ni wón máa n yó wálé òun. (o. i. 38)*

Do you know that most of these prophets make use of traditional charms. One Islamic cleric told us that he prepares Islamic charms for the prophets, that they secretly come to him at night.

Some elements of religious hypocrisy is also observed in *Kékeré Èkùn*. After embracing Christianity, Bádéjò and iyá Àlàbí claim that under no circumstance can they practise the traditional religion, but iyá Àlàbí eventually succumbs to the persuasion of her relative to consult Ràimì, the herbalist, so that she could bear more children:

*Ṣìghòṣn lẹ̀hìn ọ̀dún keta tí nwón tí mbá a sọ ọ̀ tí kò gbà, òn
nā bẹ̀rẹ̀sí ronú pé ọ̀ di ọ̀dún kẹ̀sàn tí òn tí dúró, òn kò mà rò
pé Ọ̀lórún kọ aájò lóòtò ní iwón ìgbà tí òn kò fẹ̀ se ibi sí omọ
enikeji òn...*

Ní àkókò yī gan-an ni ebí iyá Àlàbí kan tún n sọ fún u nipa àlùfàà wọ̀n àtíjọ̀ tí hàbá ọ̀kọ̀ ọ̀n ẹ̀ eghògì fún iyàwó rẹ̀ tí ó fí lóyún... Obìnrin yìí sì sọ̀rọ̀ yī tó hẹ̀é tí ọ̀kàn iyá Àlàbí fí yí pátápátá. Ó ní 'ẹ̀bí Èdìmàrẹ̀ t'ó dá ọ̀ l'ó dá egbò?' (o. i. 71).

But after three years that they had been trying to persuade her, she also began to think that she had been waiting to conceive for nine years and that she did not think that God was against traditional treatment as long as she was not doing it to harm her partner...

It was at this time that one of iyá Àlàbí's relatives told her about her former clergyman, whom her father-in-law prepared traditional medicine for, before his wife became pregnant...

The woman discussed this issue to the extent that iyá Àlàbí was totally convinced. The woman added that 'isn't it the same God who created you that also created herbs?'

Bádéjọ also gives in to the demand of his relatives to marry another wife, since iya Alabi does not seem to be able to bear more children.

Ní iwọ̀n ìghà tí iyá Àlàbí kò sì lè hímọ̀ lé Àlàbí, àwọ̀n ebí Bádéjọ̀ fún u ní ìmọ̀ràn pé kí ó fẹ̀ iyàwó kejì. Ní àkókò Bádéjọ̀ kò fẹ̀ tẹ̀lé ìmọ̀ràn yī, ó ní onígbàgbó kii ní iyàwó repete, ibi ọ̀bẹ̀ lílá l'olè tí m̀bèrè. Ẹ̀ má kọ̀ mi ní 'àgbèrè'. Sùghọ̀n nígbàtí àwọ̀n ebí n yọ̀ ó lẹ̀nu, tí wọ̀n n sọ̀ pé iyá Àlàbí ní kò jẹ̀ kí ó gbà láti ní iyàwó kejì, ọ̀rọ̀ náà bẹ̀rẹ̀sí fí í l'émí. Nwón ní 'obìnrin yẹn tí tẹ̀ é mólẹ̀, kò lè gbé́rí, bí kò bá jẹ̀ béé ni, ẹ̀bí iyàwó méjì ní bàbá tirẹ̀ ní'. (o. i. 76)

Since iyá Àlàbí was not able to have additional children, Bádéjọ's family members advised him to marry a second wife. Initially Bádéjọ was not favourably disposed to this advice, claiming that a Christian does not marry many wives, that stealing begins with tasting of a soup. Do not encourage me to practise 'adultery'. But when his extended family members began to worry him, saying it is iyá Àlàbí that does not allow him to marry a second wife, the matter began to trouble him the more. They said 'the woman has cast a spell on him, and he can not free himself, if not so, is it not two wives that his father married'.

He eventually takes to the advice of his relatives:

Ní iwọ̀n ìgbàtí ghogho ebí kò sì yě há a sọ̀rọ̀ yí, ó gbà ní ìkẹ̀hìn, ó bẹ̀rẹ̀sí fẹ̀ ọ̀mọ̀ kékeré kan...

(o. i. 77)

Since his extended family members continued to discuss the issue of a second wife with him, he later succumbed and began to date a young lady...

It is apparent from the above that Bádéjò and iyá Àlàbí initially adhere strictly to the tenets of Christianity, when it is convenient for them to do so. In each of the stated cases, they bow to African Traditional Religion.

5.1.2. Sacrifice

According to Brumbaugh (2007), Aristotle submits that:

Sacrifice means religious rituals. The word emanates from the Latin word 'sacrificium', which originally means "something made holy". It is a ritual act in which a consecrated offering is made to a god or other spiritual being in order to establish, perpetuate or restore a sacred bond between humanity and the divine.

Such offerings may comprise humans or animals which are 'blood offerings' or fruits, such as crops, flowers and sundry items. *Microsoft Student* also opines that sacrifice is a kind of a non-verbal communication between human beings and their gods, and the forms of sacrificial rituals resemble the structures of human relationships: "The rituals are therefore symbolic not only of religious aspirations, but also of the daily lives of those who take part in them".

Alana (2004:68) submits that:

According to some tradition, the world enjoyed the perfect bliss in the beginning. There was regular communion between man and the world beyond. Man freely fed. He did not have to sweat to fend for himself. He usually went to heaven to have some ration of food. He simply depended on God. Then, man became disobedient to the rule of God. The aftermath of this is that there occurred a separation between heavens and earth or between God and man. That was not the end of the matter. Man could not do it all alone without God. Hence, God gave man a new opportunity of reaching Him in sacrifice. So, through sacrifice, man continue to seek the face of God. That this continued dependence on Him may not be interrupted.

Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary simply says that sacrifice is the fact of giving up something important or valuable, in order to get something that seems more important.

In Yoruba oral tradition, there is a popular legend named, Mòremi Àjàsorò, a woman who distinguished herself as one who fulfilled her promise of sacrificing her only child to Èṣinmínrin river deity. A legend and a heroine and an indigene of Ilẹ̀-Ifẹ̀, she delivered her people from the oppression of the Ùgbò. This woman offered herself to the Ùgbò in order to carry out an espionage assignment, which enabled her to get to the secret behind the fearful appearance and the powers of the Igbo. She was able to get the secret the masquerade paraded by the Ùgbò. This made the Ifẹ̀ to defeat them she thus put a stop to the looting and enslavement of her people.

Mòremí in a quest to free her people from the bondage of the Ùgbò went to seek the spiritual help of the Èṣinmínrin river goddess, a deity worshipped by the Ifẹ̀. She made a solemn promise to the deity that she would sacrifice anything the deity wanted, if the goddess would assist the Ifẹ̀. The goddess did help the Ifẹ̀ and they were able to capture the Ùgbò masquerades. On the return of Mòremí, the deity requested for Olúorogbo, the only child of Mòremí. Mòremí redeemed her promise to the deity by sacrificing Olúorogbo, as the supreme price she had to pay to secure the freedom of her people. This is a great lesson in 'promise keeping'. Ìdòwú (1996) avers that:

Sacrifice is primarily a means of contact or communion between man and the Deity. It is a man's best way of maintaining an established relationship between himself and his object of worship.

In *Ìrèké Oníbùdó*, *Ìrèké* gets to Àlùpàyídà town, where a princess is about to be sacrificed to a killer flying snake that has been troubling the townspeople from time immemorial:

Apanirun ejò kan tí ìmā fò lófùrufù tí mǎ nyo àwọn ará ilú yì lénú láti ibèrè aiyé, á mǎ fò láti ojú ọrun wá bá àwọn ará ilú ní. Sùgbón lólún yì, àwọn Babaláwo àti Adáhunṣe gbogho wádí ọràn nǎ mwón sù wípé àfi hí Ọba bá fì ọmọ rẹ obinrin yì rùbọ lóṣṣòní, ní apanirun ejò nǎ kò fì ní wá mọ. Láipé yì ní ejò nǎ ñbò láti ọrun yíò sù pa ọmọ yì jẹ. (o. i 73)

A destroyer flying snake that flies in the sky and troubles the residents of this town from creation, flies from the sky to the town, to destroy residents. But this year, the Ifá priests and herbalists made consultation and found that except the king offers his daughter as a sacrifice today, that the destroyer snake will not stop coming. Soon, the snake would come from the sky and eat up the girl.

On a mission to Òke Lángbòdó in Ògbójú Ọde Nínú Igbó Irúnmolè, the hunters are in a precarious situation whereby darkness envelopes them. Elégbède-ọde hears the conversation of two birds nearby in a discussion, that if the hunters do not kill it and offer it as a sacrifice, they would be trapped in the dark forever.

Eléyì ní ó mú kí Elégbède-ọde paá. Gégé bí àṣà ilẹ̀ wa, a mú eiyẹ̀ yí, a la inú rẹ̀, a bu epo síi a sì gbé e sínú àpàdì kékeré kan báyi, a gbé e lọ sí idí igi nílá kan tí m̀bẹ̀ lẹ̀bà ọ̀dò wa. Inú Ọlórùn dùn pé a ronúpiwàdà – kì iṣe nítòrí ebo tí a rú. s̀ngb̀on nítòrí o mò pé ibáṣepé a ní òye jùbẹ̀ ̀lọ̀ ní, à bá sin òn ní ọ̀nà tí ó dára ju èyìni lọ. (o. i 59)

This made Elégbède-ọde to kill the bird. According to the culture of our land, we took the bird and opened it, we poured palm-oil in it and put it in a small potsherd and placed it under a big tree nears us. And God was pleased with our repentance. It was not because of the sacrifice we offered, but because he knew that if we had had a better understanding, we would have worshipped Him in a way better than this.

The sacrifice is meant to atone for the sin that Kàkó committed in Igbó-nílá by killing his innocent wife. This implies that sacrifices offered are ultimately accepted by God, especially to atone for sins committed. Alana (2004:75) asserts that:

Yorùbá take the divinities as means by which petitions to God, are sent. The authority to accept or reject the offerings Are not vested in the divinities but in God Himself. Hence, the Yorùbá end their prayers before the divinities with *Áṣe* (may it be sanctioned by God or may it receive approval).

Fágúnwà also avers that offering of sacrifice is acceptable by God. In Ògbójú Ọde nínú Igbó Irúnmalè, when Ògòngò, the King of birds in the city of birds, gives Àkàrà-ògùn and other hunters feats to perform: it offers a sacrifice, so also do Kàkó:

Nìgbàtí a dé ibè, Ògòngò dùró, ó mú màlù kan ó paá láti fí rúbọ̀ sí àwọn iwin-ilẹ̀ wọ̀nni. Imáḍòye nā̀ sì yáru mú eiyelẹ̀ pèlú àdàbà kan, ó pa wón ó fí wón rúbọ̀ ó wí pé: Yíyẹ̀ ní iyẹ̀ eiyelẹ̀, dídẹ̀ ní idẹ̀ àdàbà lórùn, yíyẹ̀ ní kí ó yẹ̀ Kàkó lóni dandan... (o. i. 63).

When we got there, the Ògòngò stopped, took a cow and offered it as a sacrifice to the earth spirits. Imódòye also promptly took a pigeon and a dove, killed them and offered them as a sacrifice with this prayer: honour is the lot of pigeon, comfort is the lot of dove, honour must be the lot of Kákó today...

In *Kékeré Ekùn*, Àdùfẹ́, Bádẹ́jọ's second wife, offers a sacrifice to *Egúngún* (masquerade); her husband's elder brother, does it on Bádẹ́jọ's behalf.

Bàbá àgbà; iye n ẹgbón oko Àdùfẹ́ bo eégún, ó pe eégún baba won lójú oóri rẹ̀. Bàbá sì dàhùn. Lẹ́hin tí nwón tí rúbọ̀ tán, eégún ní 'Mo gbàá à à'. (o. i. 21)

Bàbá àgbà; that is the elder brother of Àdùfẹ́'s husband sacrificed to *eégún*, called their father's *eégún* at their ancestral tomb, and his father answered. After the sacrifice, *eégún* said 'I accept it'.

In essence, in order to ensure that the already established relationship with the spiritual is intact, sacrifice must be offered at the appropriate time. Awólàlú (1981) and Ídòwú (1996) describe thanksgiving and Communion Sacrifice as one that is normally offered to show appreciation for the benevolence of the deity in all areas of the adherent's endeavours. Nowadays, people offer their sacrifice in form of money in their various places of worship while traditionalists offer theirs at the shrines of their gods.

In *Ibú Olókun*, Ògúndélé presents Òrògòdògànyin and his dreams. After his dreams, he consults Ifá oracle, through the Ifá priest, who makes Ifá divination thus:

*... Ó dífá fún Elégbèje-Àdó
Ní ojó tí ó fẹ́ re àjò Ìgbèrí-òsà.
Ó ní kí ó rúbọ̀ fún Àjà tí n jà ní òkè
Kí ó rúbọ̀ fún Olókun, ...
Ó ní kí ó rú ẹbọ̀ yìí dárádára
Nítòrí odù tí ó wá kì í pa iró.*

*Elégbèje-Àdó kò rúbọ̀ fún Olókun,
Kò rú fún Àjà.
Nítòrí náà ní a ẹ̀ yí Elégbèje-Àdó padà,
Ó sì dì Àròni Elésékan.
Ó lọ sí àjò náà. sìghón kò hò.* (o. i. 27).

Ifá was consulted on behalf of Elégbèje-Àdó, the day he was to travel to Ìgbèrí-òsà. He was asked to sacrifice to the spirit of the whirl.

and the goddess of the sea.
He was told to make the sacrifice well,
because the divination does not lie.
Elégbèje refused to offer the sacrifice to
the goddess of the sea, nor the spirit of the winds.

That was why Elégbèje-Àdó was turned into
a one legged fairy.
He went on the journey, but he did not return.

In this instance, Elégbèje-Àdó refused to make a sacrifice to the whirl and
the sea goddess as prescribed. He was made to see the consequence of non -
compliance.

According to Abimbólá (2006:20),

*Rírú ẹbọ ní gbè ní
Àírú kìì gbèèyaàn*

Offering sacrifice is rewarding
Refusal to offer sacrifice spells doom

This confirms that the offering prescribed and the specific sacrifice carried
out bring about solution to the problems of the suppliant. Abimbólá (2006:15)
mentions Olaiótán, who consulted the Ifá oracle when he was surrounded by enemies,
Ifá prescribed a sacrifice for him to offer so that he would not fall prey to his
enemies.

*...A diá fún Olaiótán, omọ Ọrúnmilá,
Ìgbà tí ñjè ní ọgbùn ọ́tá, wọ́n ní ó rúhọ nítorí ikú.
Ó ẹ é, ikú ò pa á...*

Ifá divination was made for Olaiótán, the son of Ọrúnmilá
When he was in the midst of enemies,
He was asked to make a sacrifice in order to avert death,
He complied and averted death...

Awólàlú (1981) and Ìdòwú (1996) also describe preventive sacrifice as a
type of sacrifice which is offered as a precautionary measure to ward off evil or
misfortune. In it, prediction is made in order to have knowledge of an impending
disaster or a doom to a person, family or the community. In such a situation, the
traditionalists would organize for a sacrifice to be made in order to ward off the

impending doom, and salvage the situation. Similarly, Christians and Muslims prescribe fasting and prayers of revival in the community.

The aforementioned sacrifices are the most common ones which are still observed within the Yorùbá community. In the novel *Ọmọ Olókìn Eṣin*, Fálétí presents Àjàyí, who is a freedom fighter. He attempts to liberate the people of Òkè Ògún from the shackles of Olúmokò. Àjàyí is eventually apprehended along with other freedom fighters and Olúmokò plans to sacrifice him and others to the gods of the land. He tells Àjàyí, when he is brought before him that:

...*Nítorínáà, gbogbo èrò rẹ tí ó gún rẹgẹ lójú rẹ un, ìbòrìṣà ní yóò pin sí. Iwọ tí o mọ pé òminira ní ó yẹ gbogbo ilú, bí wọn yóò tilẹ̀ di òminira náà, kò ní Ẹjù rẹ, mo mọ nńkan tí ó yẹ ẹ. Nààrì náà ní n ó fi ẹ bọ.* (o. i. 129)

...Therefore, all your lofty ideas will end in sacrifice. You who think your town deserves freedom, even if they will have it, you will not witness it. I know what befits you. I will sacrifice you to *Nààrì*.

Alana (2004:74) hints that:

Although sacrifices are often offered to the divinities, the divinities do not constitute ends in themselves; they are only means to an end, namely, God Himself.

He adds that:

Such sacrifices, like those offered to the divinities, are to be delivered to Olódùmarè whose say on the sacrifice is final. The divinities and the ancestors are no more than channels of reaching God. Hence, the rationale of making petitions through them. Yorùbá religion is becoming increasingly unfashionable among the educated people, particularly Muslims and Christians. (Alana, 2004:72)

It is noteworthy that the plan of the King to sacrifice the captives at the Ògún shrine is not prescribed by the gods. The King unilaterally decides to offer humans to the gods. However, in Christianity the practice of making sacrificial offerings dates back to the biblical times, when Abel offered the best of his cattle to the Lord; and Cain also offered some fruits to Him. The book of Genesis 4:3 says:

And in the process of time, it came to pass, that Cain brought of the fruit of the ground; an offering unto the Lord. And Abel, he also brought of the firstlings of his flock and of the fat there of...

Likewise, the Lord God accepts offer of sacrifice from time to time for one reason or the other. Hence, when people obey the Lord's commandments, and follow His principles and laid down rules, they can be said to be offering sacrifice of obedience.

Also in the Holy Quran, God instructs Ibrahim to make a burnt offering of his only son, Ismaeel, to Him. In obedience to God, Ibrahim was about to comply with God's instructions, when God commanded Angel Jubril to give a ram to Ibrahim as a substitute offering instead of Ismaeel. This event till today is commemorated by the annual Iléyá festival celebrated by the Muslims.

Today, despite the emergence of foreign religions among the Yorùbá, traditional religion still retains its grip on the people, even though traditional religion is mostly condemned and regarded as outdated, out of vogue and fetish by the adherents of Christianity and Islam. It can be inferred from the above that sacrifice is an integral part of religions; African Traditional Religion is not exempted from the rituals of religion.

The Yorùbá make sacrifice to the numerous gods that exist in the Yorùbá traditional society. Sacrifices are made in order to appease the gods, to atone for the wrong deeds of an erring member of the society or to seek favour from the gods. Sometimes, sacrifices are offered to appease the gods when the norm of the society is broken, when a member of the society breaks the societal law or flouts a societal taboo. The Yorùbá also offer sacrifice to accompany their requests of goodwill, children, safety, protection, wealth, good health, peace and so forth. They particularly offer sacrifice to the gods in order that their farms yield bounty harvest. Thus, offering of sacrifice is an integral part of African Traditional Religion.

5.1.3. Metaphysics

Metaphysics, according to *Encarta English Dictionary* "is the branch of philosophy concerned with the study of beings, existence, time and space and casualty".

Brumbaugh (2007 encartar) quotes Aristotle, in his contribution on metaphysics, thus:

In his metaphysics, Aristotle argued for the existence of a divine being, described as the Prime mover, who is responsible for the unity and purposefulness of nature. God is perfect and therefore the aspiration of all things in the world, because all things desire to share perfection.

Metaphysics, according to Olálówò (1995:56), denotes belief in supernatural phenomenon. Metaphysics thus refers to something beyond the ordinary. Roget's II *The New Thesaurus* defines magic as:

The use of supernatural powers to influence or predict events: conjuration, sorcery, wizardry and witchcraft. It is also defined as an object or power that one uses to cause evil events: charm, evil eye. It is the use of skillful tricks and deceptions to produce entertainingly baffling effects...

The practice of magic is one of the traditional professions of the Yorùbá. This is typified in *Olówólayémò*, where we see Olówólayémò and Òsèni, one of his numerous friends, where they practise magic. Though Olówólayémò is complacent with his various friends, he soon becomes disillusioned:

Èmi pèlú òré mi kan tí ñ jé Òsèni ni a jùmò ñ x eré idán. Kí bàbá mi tó kú ní ó ti fún mi ní òògùn kan. Bí mo bá hu òògùn yìi sènu tí mo sì sọ òrò rẹ sí i, kò sí idán tí ng kò lè pa. (o. i. 108)

I and my friend Òsèni were performing magic. Before my father died, he had given me a charm. If I put this charm in my mouth and chant the right incantations, there is no magic I cannot perform.

This attests to the fact that the art of magic is a part and parcel of the Yorùbá. It runs within and among families and is handed over from generation to generation.

This profession is common among the Egúngún Guild. There is "Éégún Onídán"; magic performing masquerade, as presented in Ògúniran's *Éégún Alaré*. In the foreward to the novel, the novelist says:

Éégún ni mo fì ìwé nàà sọrí gégé hí orúkọ ìwé yìi kii x àwọn Éégún Alágho. Éégún Àdó tàbí irú àwọn Éégún bée, tí ó máa ñ jáde léèkan lóhùn ni mò ñwí, tàbí irú àwọn kan tí ó máa ñsagbe kiri ní idákúrekú. Irú àwọn wónni kó, àwọn Éégún

aláré tí nwón n pidán kiri ni mo fi sọrí.

(o. i. ix)

I dedicate the book to the Egúngún guild just like the title. I am not talking about 'Éégún Alágbo', 'Éégún Àdó' and the likes that come out once in a year neither am I talking about the ones that go about begging for money from time to time. I am not talking about these types. The ones that I am referring to are the professional magic-performing masquerades.

The practice of magic by magic-performing masquerades is handed over to Ọjẹládé, the son of Lárinnàkà, who is a professional magic-performing masquerade.

*Àwọn mólẹ́hí Ọjẹ Lárinnàkà mú Ọjẹládé wá sí ọ̀dọ̀
Dáṣọfúnjọ pé kí ó máa kọ ọ ní isẹ́ idán pípá nítorí pé
esẹ̀ bàba rẹ̀ l'ótọ̀ w'áiyé.* (o. i. 10)

The extended family members of Lárinnàkà brought Ọjẹládé to Dáṣọfúnjọ, to learn the art of magic performing because he takes after his father's footsteps.

A display of magic performance is perceived in the same novel:

*Lẹ́hìn ijó yìí ni nwón wó kéréé; lẹ́hìn kéréé wíwó, ni nwón
ta òkìtì, lẹ́hìn òkìtì nwón di òyìnbó, ọ́lọpàá, ẹ̀kùn tí ó n gun
ilé àti igi ọ̀dàn. Bí ó ti n pidán wọnyí ni nwón n da ọ̀póró
owó hòó.* (o. i. 14)

After the dance, a coarse grass screen made of bamboo and cut with thin laths were pulled, after the pulling of 'kéréé', he somersaulted, after the somersault, he turned into a white man, a policeman, a tiger and a python. While these changes were going on, spectators were giving him gifts of cash.

Ọlábímtán, in *Kékeré Ẹ̀kùn*, discusses the Yorùbá belief in Egúngún. They are presented as part of the ancestral pantheons. Witchcraft is also part of the worldview of the Yorùbá. The Yorùbá believe in the existence of magic. This is reflected in *Orilawẹ̀ Àdìgún*. The practice of magic begins in the beginning of the novel, where the Àtíngà cultists go into trance, enter into the houses and rooms of the people of Owódé and bring out idols, destructive magic used to cast spells and other evil powers in the possession of such individuals. They also get the people involved in such things arrested and cast a spell on them, which makes them to confess their evil deeds.

*Ohun ti óhń dẹ̀rùba àwọn èniyàn ní ọ̀nà tí àwọn eléḡún òòsà
Àtíngà ń gbà mọ ilé tí òòḡùn wọ̀nyí wà àti ibi gan-an tí àwọn
òòḡùn nàà wà nínú ilé. Ènikan ní: Wón wejú ní o... (o. i. 1)*

What frightened the people was how the Àtíngà cultists who were in a trance knew the houses in which the destructive materials were, and the exact places to find them in such houses. Someone replies: It is magical...

To further prove that witchcraft does exist among the Yorùbá, the victims of the Àtíngà cults confess their evil deeds. Ìyá Olóbi, who has been given a kolanut of the gods, begins to confess thus:

*Èmi lẹ̀ ní n ẹ̀? Ìgbaa `Débísí fòórùn epo rẹ̀ lá mi lójú.
Bí mo sì fómọ̀ mi dá àjọ, ẹ̀bí ohun tí èyàn bá ní
lo fi ń ẹ̀ àlejò, fúnrami ní mo sá lómọ̀ mi. (o. i. 5)*

What do you want me to do?
When `Débísí enticed me with the
aroma of her palm-oil. And if I donate
my child to the cult, it is whatever
one has that is offered for entertainment
of visitors. After all I own my child.

She also confesses that she killed her younger sibling's child because the child refused to run an errand for her. She claims responsibility for the miscarriages of one of her daughters-in-law. The practice of witchcraft is also made manifest in the Yorùbá proverb that has it that: "Àjé ké lánàá, ọ̀mọ̀ kú lóníí, ta ní kò mọ̀ pé àjé ànà ló pa ọ̀mọ̀ jẹ?" (A witch shouted yesterday, and a child died today, who does not know that it was that witch who killed the child?).

In *Orílawẹ̀ Àdigún*, we read about a kind of magic that makes the user invisible to people.

*Géḡé bí àpẹ̀ẹ̀rẹ̀, ohun àmúṣírẹ̀ ní Lawẹ̀ ka ìsìjù sí, á sì máa
mú un lọ sí ilé-ìwé láti fi dá àwọn eléḡbé rẹ̀ láráyá. Bí Lawẹ̀
bá lo ìsìjù láti pa idán m̀íràn lójú àwọn eléḡbé rẹ̀ tán, wón
á máa sàá ní m̀ésàn-án m̀ẹ̀wàá... (o. i. 10)*

For example, Lawẹ̀ regarded the blindfolding charm as a toy, he took it to school to entertain his fellow students. Whenever Lawẹ̀ used the charm to perform a magic before his fellow students, they would hail him...

When Lawè is asked why he uses magic to mesmerize Mr. Àlùkò, one of the teachers, he replies:

*Ìdí ni pé Ọghéni Àlùkò jé ọkan ninú àwọn tí kò gbàgbó ninú
ogbón ijìnlẹ̀ Yorùbá...* (o. i. 13)

The reason is that Mr. Àlùkò happens to be one of the people who do not believe in the ingenuity and depth of wisdom of the Yorùbá...

The use of disappearance magic is also discussed in *Orílawè Àdìgún*. It is published in a daily newspaper that a man used the charm to disappear when marijuana is found in his belongings:

*Ó yẹ kóo kà á. Ọwọ́ tí oò gbàgbó pé òògùn
wá. Àwọn ọlópàá ibodè n wá ọkúnrin kan
kiri báyi. Wón ní eghé gbé e kúrò níwájú
wọn nígbà tí wón rí igbó ninú ẹrù rẹ...*
(o. i. 14)

You need to read it. You that do not believe in the existence of charms. The custom officials were looking for a man. They said he disappeared before them, when they found marijuana in his belongings.

In *Ogun Àwítélé*, Balógun uses *ìsìjù* (magic of illusion) so that the armed robbers would not see him as he counts their number:

*Nígbà tí Balógun tí n ka àwọn olè yìi bọ láti ìbèrè, wọn kò
rì nítorí ìsìjù tí ó lò, sìghón nígbà tí ó dé ọlò ọgá wọn tí a n
wí yì, ewé sun 'ko, ọkúnrin ná rí Balógun.* (o. i. 24)

Balogun had been counting these armed robbers, but they did not see him because of the blindfolding charm that he used, but when he got to the leader of the gang, the charm lost its potency, the man saw him.

Fágúnwà, in *Ọgbójú Ọde Ninú Igbó Irúnmalè*, confirms the existence of the disappearance magic when Àkàrà-ògùn, the hero in the novel, goes on a hunting expedition in the forest, he is faced with a precarious situation with gnomes and spirits. He uses the magic to escape home.

*Ibití nwón tí n pa èrò bí àwọn yìò tí ẹ ré milulẹ̀, ni mo tí
rántí ògùn mi kan báyi; eghé ni; mo bá sà á, wéré mo sí*

bá ara mi ní iyàrá mi ní ilé, eghé ti ghé mi dé ibè. (o. i. 7)

While they were planning how to bring me down from the tree, I remembered one of my charms: it is disappearance charm; I used it and I immediately found myself in my room in my own house. The charm had taken me there.

Somewhere else, after Àkàrà-ògùn and Lámọ́rín's ordeal in the hands of Tèmbèlèkun, Lámọ́rín dies and Àkàrà-ògùn accidentally finds himself on a path that leads to his village. He decides to go back into the forest to bring his spirit-wife home. The wife declines and instead offers him a magic cloth as a parting gift.

Gba aṣọ kékeré yì, èbùn ni fún ọ, nígbàkígba tí ebi bá ñpa ó, bèrè ohun tí o bá fé l'owó aṣọ nà, òn yíò sì fi fún ọ... (o. i. 14)

Take this piece of cloth, it is a gift, whenever you are hungry, ask for whatever meal you desire from the cloth and it shall give it to you...

This is pure magic, because there is no scientific justification for a piece of cloth producing desired meals for someone merely by asking for it.

In a later encounter, the hunters who are on a hunting expedition to Òke Lán gbódò meet Àgbákò on the way, and a fight ensues. During the course of the fight, Àgbákò transforms himself into a snake:

Nígbàtí Àgbákò sùbùlulè, ó di ejò ó l'owó Kàkó lára, ó sì gbé Kàkó lulè, àti ejò nà àti Kàkó sì bèrèsí iyí láti òkè l'owó sí isàlẹ. (o. i. 66)

When Àgbákò fell down, he transformed into a snake, and twisted itself on Kàkó's body, Kàkó fell down, and Kàkó and the snake both began to roll down.

Fágúnwà corroborates the use of pure magic in *Òghójú Ọdẹ Nínú Ighó Irúnmalẹ*. After a fight with Àgbákò, a spirit being, Àgbákò magically locks Àkàrà-ògùn up in a dungeon. Àkàrà-ògùn is hungry, and Àgbákò magically tempts him by placing two-wraps of corn-meal and beef stew before him. But he could not get hold of the meal.

Nígbàtí ó pé, ebi bèrèsí ípa mí bí mo sì tí ñ ronú ònà tí mo lè gbà rí onjẹ jẹ ní mo wo ìwájú, tí mo rí àkàṣù èkọ méjì pèlú ọbẹ ẹran. Bí mo sì tí ñ sùnmọ ọ kí mba mǎ jẹun ní mo rí tí

After a while, I began to feel hungry, as I was thinking of how to get food to eat. I looked up, and found two wraps of cornmeal and beef stew. As I moved near it, so that I could eat, I found my stomach protruding, and it prevented me from reaching the meal.

In the same vein, when Àkàrà-ògùn meets the acquittance of Ìwàpèlè in Èmò town, Ìwàpèlè tells him how bad the town is. She, however, decides to accommodate him. She shows him a room and instructs him not to enter into until after her death. He later enters into the room after her death, only to find himself in his own room in his home town:

*Wíwólé tí mo wólé, inú iyàrá mi ní ilé ní mo há ara mi;
nígbà tí mò sì wo ilé yíká, mo rí ibon mi tí ó tí sọ̀nù sí ibití
èmi àti Àgbákò tí ñjà...* (o. i. 20)

As I entered into the room, I found myself in my own room in my house; as I looked round the room, I saw my gun that had earlier been lost in a fight with Àgbákò ...

Ṣégè makes use of metaphysics in wrestling, in the novel *Kúyè*. Ṣégè is a wrestling champion in his locality, whom no one has been able to defeat in any wrestling contest as a result of his prowess in the art. Ọ̀dúnjọ explains why no one has been able to beat him in a wrestling contest.

*Ohun tí ọ̀mọ ọ̀kúnrin tí a ń wí yìí máa ń ṣe ní pé, ó máa ń pe
ọ̀fò sí etí ẹ̀ni tí ó bá wá da ojú ìjà kọ́ ọ́, á sì dẹ̀rùhà á kí ó tó
bẹ̀rẹ̀ ìjà rárá. Bí ẹ̀nikẹ̀ni bá tí bọ́ síta láti kò ó lójú, yóò tu
itọ́ sí ọ̀wọ́ ara rẹ̀, yóò sì máa kẹ́gbe lée lóri bá yìí:
Oníkú tí ó bá mi ṣe irú ẹ̀yí dá lápá, onígbò tí ó dá àbá rẹ̀
f'ẹ̀hìn gbá 'lẹ̀. Sẹ̀ ẹ̀yìn ológbò kí kan 'lẹ̀. Ṣégè kò ní súbú láì
fì ẹ̀sẹ̀ tẹ̀ 'lẹ̀...*
*Bí ó tí wù kí oliwàrẹ̀ mọ́ ìjàkadì tó, ojo ara yóò mú un, ẹ̀hìn
rẹ̀ yóò sì dín dẹ̀nkù ní ilẹ̀ láì pé.* (o. i. 29)

What this boy does is that, he chants incantations into the ear of his fellow contestant, he will also frighten him before the context begins. Once anyone comes out to contest with him, he spits on his own palm, and begins to chant thus: Bearer of death who tries this with me broke his arm, owner of forest who dared me fell on his back. The cat's back never touches the ground, Ṣégè would not fall down without standing on his feet...

No matter how skillful one might be in local wrestling, he

would be intimidated and he would soon land on his back.

Once Šégè makes these incantations, he is able to defeat his co-wrestler. The secret behind his victory is the supernatural powers he possesses:

*Púpò nínú àwọn èniyàn ni ó ghàghó pé bí Šégè bá fi igè lu
igè pèlú enikéni. àfi bí olúwarè kò bá mì rárá ni kò ní bá
ara rẹ ní ilẹ̀* (o. i. 82)

Many people believed that if Šégè hit his chest against anyone's chest, the person would find himself flat on the ground except the person did not breathe at all.

In other words, Šégè does not win in contests because of his strength and prowess, but as a result of the magic in his possession.

Lastly, in Ògúnníran's *Éégún Aláré*, we see Òjèládé, a magic-performing masquerade turn into a python in a performance.

*...Nígbàtí ó ṣe, ó dúró, kò sì sáré lọ mó, nígbànáà ni àwọn
omọ-èhìn rẹ̀ sùn to kèrèè náà. Sùgbón nígbàtí nwọn yíò
sí kèrèè kúrò, òjòlá ni àwọn òmòràn rí tí ó nà gbalaja silẹ̀...*
(o. i. 14)

After a while, he was still, he stopped running, that was when his followers moved near the coarse grass mat. When they opened the grass mat, they found a python instead, the python lay there...

After the demise of Òjè Lárinnàkà: Òjèládé's father, Òjèládé is confident of himself, due to the legacy of magical charms he has inherited from his father:

*Okàn Òjèládé balè pé àjò náà yòò dára fún òun, ní ti pé, idán
pípa dáa lójú tó adá, àti pé, àwọn òògùn tí a fi ñ ṣe òkúnrin tí
bàba rẹ̀ fún un mbe l'owó rẹ̀ bí abà, àwọn miràn sì kún ilé.
Yàtò sí iwonyi, Òjèládé pàápàá tó òkúnrin fún ara rẹ̀* (o. i. 23)

Òjèládé was confident that his journey would be successful, he was certain and confident of his magic prowess, he was equally confident of the numerous charms and magical spells that his father gave him were in his possession. Besides, Òjèládé himself is 'man' enough.

During a particular performance, Òjèládé metamorphoses into several things:

*Lèhìn idúpéyí ni Òjèládé hère si pidán. Ótún ñjò, ó ntàkítì,
ó sì ñyípadà di orisírìsí ñkan. Ó di màlúù, ó di abá-òwú, ó
di eéran, ó sì tún di èrùùgàlè-kò-dìde...* (o. i. 27)

After expressing his appreciation, Ọjéládé began his magic performance. As he danced, so also did he somersault, and metamorphosed into a cow, cotton gin, and a huge monster...

From the above, it is evident that magic, witchcraft, and spell casting are practices in traditional Yorùbá culture, just as other cultures in the world. Different peoples of the world possess different kinds of charms, witchcraft and magic. The Yorùbá are no exception; this fact is captured in these Yorùbá sayings:

Ọmọdẹ̀ ọ̀ mọ̀ ọ̀ògùn, ọ̀ ń pẹ̀ ẹ̀ lẹ́fọ́

A child knows not medicine and calls it mere vegetable

Ewé ńbẹ, bẹ́ẹ̀ sì ni ọ̀ògùn wà

There are herbs, so also are medicine.

Ibi gbogbo la ti ń dára alé, omi ọ̀bẹ̀ ló ń dùn ju ara won lọ

Supper is prepared everywhere; it is just the soup that varies in taste.

The practice of magic is a manifestation of the level of ingenuity of the Yorùbá, with reference to magic performance, in particular, and metaphysics, in general. Just like other peoples of the world, the Yorùbá are not left out in the wisdom of the unseen science. All the forms of magic discussed above such as mirage magic, illusion magic, disappearance, etcetera, are practised in traditional Yoruba society. The practitioners believe that they are practising magic; and the people effects of the magic believe it as acts of magic involving extraordinary and incredible actions which are astonishing as well.

5.1.4. Christianity

Christianity is a religion which found its way into Yorùbáland through the activities of early explorers and missionaries who came to Yorùbáland. In *L'ọ́jọ́ Ọjóún*, Délànò gives us a picture of the culture and tradition of the past. He reminds us of the beginning of Christianity in Nigeria, with all the activities of the missionaries. In the preface to the novel, he claims that the novel is a presentation of pre-colonial era, a literary portrayal of the effect of British contact with its effect on

Yorùbá traditional society, and the eventual introduction of Christianity with its attendant obligations, which the people could not understand at first. He says the novel is an experience wrapped in fiction:

*L'ójó Ojójún rán mi léti ohun púpò, ó rán mi léti bí àsìkò náà tí rí, ó gbé àwòrán àsà, ìṣe àti itúká Ègbá sí àroko hàn mí...
ó rán mi léti ihèrè èsìn igbàgbó... (o. i. vi)*

L'ójó Ojójún reminds me of a lot of things, it reminds me of how things were then, it portrays the picture of culture and tradition and the dispersal of the Ègbá into villages. It reminds me of the beginning of Christianity.

Ògúnṣínà (1992:128) observes that *L'ójó Ojójún* is a reflection of the grandeur and pleasantness of traditional life before the coming of the Europeans and that of Yorùbá culture of the nineteenth century. It also tells us of the works and times of early missionaries. In the preface to *L'ójó Ojójún*, Délàṅò asks:

*Tani ni Nàìjíríà tí kò fé rántí bí igbàgbó ṣe wọ ilú Nàìjíríà?
Tani kò fé mọ ìṣe àti ìṣe àwọn oníwàásù àkókò? Tani kò rí
ohun ibi tí a mú wá pẹlú ilàjù titun ná? Òwò otí àti
àmupara... Írántí ohun tí ó ti kojá ṣe pàtàkì fún ìṣírí àti
èkó. (o. i. v – vi)*

Who in Nigeria does not want to remember how Christianity came? Who does not want to know the activities and work of the first missionaries? Who does not see the evil brought with the new civilization? Trade in liquor and drunkenness... The remembrance of past things is important for inspiration and knowledge..

This was how the christian religion was introduced to Nigerians. Through the practice of Christianity, European Christians condemned and attempted the abolition of traditional practices. The European Christians wielded so much influence and brought about significant changes to Yorùbá society. The novel paints a picture of the temperament of that age, as observed in the difficulty to change with the time. The changes brought about a transformation in the lifestyle of the people. These changes were strange to the Yoruba people, as they often ran in conflict with their traditional ways of life.

The Yorùbá hypocritically embraced the religion. The acceptance was superficial as whenever a Christian encounters difficult problems in life, they abandon their Christian practices and go traditional. Thus, Etuk (2002:29) observes that:

When any of the crisis of life scratches us a little, such as serious health problems, disasters and misfortunes including death, especially if these appear to be inexplicable, then one is likely to encounter beneath the surface, a solid core of traditional beliefs and practices which cannot be reconciled at all with Christian standards.

The Holy Bible is the reference and scriptural text of this religion. Christians believe in the trinity of God – God the father, God the son, and God the Holy Ghost. They believe in heaven and the hell-fire as rewards and destined abode of those who do good and the evil doers, respectively.

Ìṣòlá (1998:27-29) views Ládélé's *Jé Ng Lò'gbà Tèmi*, retrospectively, when Christianity and Western education were indirectly promoting Western culture. The narrator attempts to inform readers that naive acceptance of foreign culture is dangerous, as he notes at the beginning of the story, when Christianity came to Ọwọ:

Báyì ní àwọn onígbàgbọ́ nǹwà ní idákúrekú láti wàásù fún àwọn ará ilú Ọwọ́ tí ọ̀rọ́ wọn sì n wọ ọ̀pọ̀lopọ́ wọn léti, tí àwọn sì n yipo sí igbàgbọ́. Láipé wón ní sọ̀sọ̀ tiwón, àwọn onígbàgbọ́ ní ilú Ọwọ́ nikan sì nító mǹwá sí mǹéédógún.

(o. i. 9 – 10)

This was how the Christians were coming occasionally to preach to inhabitants of Ọwọ́, many were listening to their preaching and were changing to Christianity. Soon, they had their own church, Christians alone were numbering between ten and fifteen!

The narrator also comments on the modus-operandi of Christians, that they used to attract a large audience with their evangelical music:

Báyì ní àwọn ènià nǹxé láti mú kí ènià wá jáde wá wòran wón, nwón fẹ́, nwón kọ. Oó rí àwọn ọmọ kékèkéké, nwón yíò ma sáré jáde láti inú ilé. Òmiràn yíò mú òkèlè onjẹ lówó, òmiràn yíò máa fa eran bíi rọ̀bà nitorí ó nǹjẹun lówó l'ó ghọ "Lákíribiti", bẹ̀é ní yóò sì dídè fún láiwí fún ẹnìkan láti lọ wòran. Wá wo oríṣiríṣi ikùn àti oríṣiríṣi idí. Ikùn mìi nínú wón yóò yọ bẹ̀m̀bẹ̀ yíò sì máa jà rọ̀dò bí oówo tó Ẹ̀tán tí yíò

*tú, idí rẹ̀ à sí kú wómí hí òjò kú, orí á wá rí jálùghè hí tí ikán
ílà h'ori rẹ̀.*
(o. i. 5)

This was what they used to do to make people come out to watch them, whether they liked it or not. You would see small kids run out from their houses. One would hold a morsel of food, another would tug at a tough piece of meat pulling and stretching it like rubber, because he was eating when he heard "Lákíribí" and he would get up instantly without asking permission and would go out to watch. You will only behold the various types of bellies and

buttocks. Some of the stomachs would protrude greatly and would shine like a boil about to release its pus, and his buttocks would be flat and receding! The head would be disproportionately big like the head of the big termite.

The enthusiasm that the children and youth had for the foreign religion as shown above, explains how Christianity gradually had its firm root in Yorùbáland.

The wide acceptability of christian religion is also portrayed in *Kékeré Èkùn*, where Bádéjò's family which was a strong òjè family embraces christianity. This is contrary to the traditional religion practice which runs in his family as his name is Eégúnjòbí:

*Ní ilé Bádéjò, omọ tí kò bá ka òrò Eégún sí,
àyè omọ àlè ní àwọn máa nítóósí.* (o. i. 4)

In Bádéjò's family, a child that fail to take the Eégún cult seriously was regarded as a bastard.

Bádéjò opts out of the Eégún cult as a result of a disagreement that ensued between him and the Òjè guild. This makes him accept Christianity and he becomes a deeply devoted and religious Christian. The clergyman prays for Bádéjò thus:

*Olúwa Olódùmarè, iwọ eni tí kò fẹ́ ikú elésè, hí kò xepé kí
ó yípadà kúrò nínú iwà burúkú, jówó dárí èsè wa jì wá,
sọ wá dí àkòtun kí o sì tún wa bí nínú omọ Rẹ́ Jẹ́sù Kristí,
Olúwa wa, Amin...
Olúwa Olórún, ìghàlá mí, iwọ eni tí èmí ùkígbe sí lósàn àtí
lórú, jẹ́ kí àdúrà mí nítòrí omọkúnrin yí wá síwájú Rẹ́, de etí
Rẹ́ sílẹ́ kí O sí ghó àdúrà mí. Jówó, Babá wa òrún, má sàí yí
omọkúnrin yí lókàn padà sí rere, mú ojù rẹ́ kúrò nínú iwà
burúkú lórí sírísí, sọ ó dí mínió, nipa oore òfẹ́ Rẹ́, kí o sì máa
x amòná rẹ́ láti isisiyí lọ àtí láíláí. Amin. (o. i. 14)*

Lord God, you who do not want the death of the sinner but for him to repent, and change from his bad deeds, please forgive us of our sins, renew us, let us be born again in your son Jesus Christ our Lord, Amen...
 My Lord and my God, my Saviour, You who I cry unto day and night, let my prayers on behalf of this man come unto Thee. Listen unto my prayers and answer my prayers. Please, our Father in heaven, turn this man's mind positively. Keep his eyes away from bad deeds, make him holy by your grace, and be his guide, from now on and forever more. Amen.

Baba wa ti mbe ni orun, ki a bowo fun oruko Re, ki ijoba Re de. Ife Tire ni ki a se l'aiye, bi nwon ti nse ni orun. Fun wa ni onje doojo wa loni, dari esese wa ji wa bi a ti ndari esese ji awon to se wa. Ma fa wa sinu idewo, sughon gba wa lowo hillsi. Nitari ijoba ni Tire, agbara ni Tire, ogo ni Tire. lailai. Amin.
 (o. i. 14)

Our father who hath in heaven, hallowed be thy name, thy kingdom come. Thy will be done on earth as it is in heaven. Give us this day, our daily bread and forgive us our trespasses as we forgive those who trespasses against us. Lead us not into temptation but deliver us from evil for thine is the kingdom, the power and the glory, forever and ever, Amen.

The picture of a sincere, real minister of God is depicted in *Kekeré Ekùn*. When Àlùfáà (priest) takes over the situation by offering shelter to Ìyá Àlàbí, after Bádéjò had beaten up Ìyá Àlàbí and thrown a stick which hit Àlàbí and made him lose consciousness, Àlùfáà offers him succour as he neither chastises him nor condemns him:

...Dide, dide jokò. Kò si eni tí kò lè se àsi se, ninu àsi se ni a ti nse àtún se. Nípa èyí tí a fi ní ilosiwájú. (o. i. 12)

Get up and sit down. No one is above mistake, it is when we make mistakes, that we find corrections. This leads to making progress.

He later prays for Àlàbí and his family, after which Àlàbí converts to Christianity. Some post-salvation arrangements are then made for him:

Àlùfáà kò si jáfara láti setò bí yìò se máa lo sí ipadé awon tí ó sèsè fé sàmì. Bákannáà ni ó sí fi iyawó rès'áàrín awon obìnrin tí ó nkò èkò isàmì. Láti ighàná àlùfáà ní i pé Bádéjò

*àti iyàwó rè ñwá sí ilé-ìsìn lósè-lósè...
Láti ojó náà ni Bádéjọ kò mu ọtí mọ, ó di onígàgbó tòótó.
kò sì pé rará tí ọ̀n àti iyàwó rè àti ọmọ wọ̀n sàmì. Iyàwó ñjé
Elisábẹ̀tì, ọkọ ñjé Pọ̀lù, ọmọ wọ̀n sì ñ jé Sààmù. (o. i. 15)*

The clergyman promptly made arrangement on how he would attend baptismal classes. He also enrolled his wife among the women who were receiving baptism lessons. Since then, the clergyman ensured that Bádéjọ, and his wife attended Sunday services...

From that day, Bádéjọ stopped taking alcoholic drinks, he became a committed Christian, soon after that, he and his family were baptized: His wife became Elizabeth, Bádéjọ's baptismal name was Paul, while their son's name was Samuel.

Bádéjọ, like most other Africans who are newcomers into the new religion, faces some challenges. The way Bádéjọ handles the challenges he faces as a result of his new religion leaves much to be desired. He is torn between sticking to his new faith and refusing to make the sacrifice which is unbiblical and unacceptable in Christendom. He is advised to take a second wife since the first wife has borne only one child. He later agrees with the extended family members by taking Àdùfẹ as a second wife. Hence, Bádéjọ's new embraced religion stance conflicts with his Yorùbá traditinal religion background. In Christianity, polygyny is discouraged, while it is a thing of pride in Yorùbá tradition. The new wife also experiences delay in getting pregnant. Bádéjọ is encouraged by his extended family members and in-laws to make a sacrifice to his ancestral spirits. Bádéjọ refuses to make the sacrifice:

Rára o, Èmi ò lè rúbo (o. i. 83)

No, I cannot offer a sacrifice.

This assertion is as a result of the fact that Bádéjọ has recently accepted Christianity and has forsaken the Egúngún cult, a member of which he was. Bádéjọ refuses to make the sacrifice because he dreads being seen as a herbalist and devotee of deities. He has been ordained as the "Bàbá ijọ", patron of the local church.

Eventually, Bádéjọ surrenders by giving Àdùfẹ the money with which to make the sacrifice. This shows that Bádéjọ had to indirectly go back to the traditional religion

practice to solve his problem of inability to bear more children. This is a case of culture contact and culture conflict.

*Ng ó fún ọ lówó sí i bí kò bá tó, ohunkóhun tí o bá sì tún fé,
ng ó fi fún ọ. Ilé tẹmi tí di ilé Jéésù, ng kò sì lè jẹ kí ẹ tún
rúbọ sí òrìṣà kan n'ilé mi...
Òfin kejì tí kọ wa pé a kò gbọdò ní Ọlórún miiran lẹhin Ọlúwa.
Sé o rò pé inú Àlùfáà yíò dùn bí mo bá ńrú òfin Ọlórún mi? (o. i. 88)*

I will give you more money if that is not enough, and if you want any other thing I will give it to you. My house has become that of Jesus, and I cannot allow you to offer sacrifice to any god in my house...

The second commandment has taught us that we must not worship any other god besides the Lord. Do you think the clergyman will be happy if I break the law of my God?

5.1.3 Islam

In Islam, a Muslim believes in the articles of faith which are the guiding principles and tenets in the practice of Islam. Going by the belief of the practitioners of both Christianity and Islam, there appears to be uniformity in the belief that there is only one living God. The major area of difference is found in the trinity of God, which the Muslims do not believe in. In *Àyànmọ*, Bàbá Àjọké refers to Christians as ignorant people. He says it is the ignorance of Christians that makes them refer to Jesus as the son of God:

*Ó ní kò sí ohun tí àimọkan kò lè fi ènià ẹ o, ó ní àimọkan
onígbàgbọ ní nwón fi ńpe Jéésù ní omọ Ọlórún. Bí ó bá sì
ń sọ gbólóhùn yí, á máa parí rẹ pẹlú kéwú pé:*

Kúlúfú àlái,

Aádú àlái

Lámú yà lídí

Wà lámú yá ládí

Wà lámú yá kún láú

Kù fúwà, aádu.

*Láìbèèrè lẹwọ rẹ, òun náà fúnrarẹ á sì tún túnmọ rẹ báyí
pé: 'Ọlórún kò bimọ, ẹnikan kò bí Ọlórún, kò sì sí ẹni tí ó
lè bá Ọlórún k'égbẹ'. (o. i. 13)*

He says there is nothing one cannot do out of ignorance, he also says it is the ignorance of the Christians that makes them refer to Jesus as son of God. When he makes these statements, he concludes with this Quranic verse that says:

He is Allah,
The One, Allah,
The Eternal,
Absolute,
He beget not,
Nor is He begotten;
And there is none like Unto Him.

The Christians also believe that only good things come from God, and that anything that appears bad in human conception come from the Devil; whereas, Muslims believe that both good and bad emanate from God, but that what may appear to people as bad is only a means to a good end. Sodiq (2004:137) holds the view that:

Muslims believe that good and bad come from God, which is consistent with Yorùbá belief in a High God. Such belief is inherent in their culture.

On the contrary, Adelowo, cited in Sodiq (2005) submits that:

Yorùbá Muslims do not strictly adhere to the concept of the unity of God in Islam. (In Islam) Allah and only He shall be worshipped and not divinities or ancestral spirits since He is one, the only one of the whole universe. However, as revealed by the practice of Islam in Africa, this cardinal principle of Islam is not strictly followed. Muslims still consult the oracle divinity and some still feel inclined to participate in the annual traditional festivals in honour of the tutelary divinities. They have no qualms about taking part in such festivals with their kith and kin.

A proof of this is the song popularly sung by Muslims in the past:

*Áwa ó ɣe orò ilé wa ò, áwa ó
ɣe orò ilé wa ò. Ìmàle kò pé,
ó ye, Ìmàle kò pé kí áwa má
ɣe orò, Áwa ó ɣe orò ilé wa ò.*

We shall practise our tradition, we shall practise our tradition.
Islam does not mean we should not practise our tradition, we shall practise our tradition.

Despite the influx of the Yorùbá into Christianity and Islam, the Yorùbá still consult the oracles. The Yorùbá in secrecy still return to their traditional religion in order to solve problems. An instance of this is also found in *Àyànmó*. When Àjoké

finds it difficult to conceive, she consults the oracle in spite of the fact that she is from an Islamic home and she is married to an Alhaji:

*Ó ní, nígbàtí àwọn babaláwo sì yé é wò, nwón ní òun kò
lè gbádùn, bẹ̀ẹ̀ ní òun kò silè bimọ, àyàfi bí òun bá padà
lọ fẹ́ ọkọ àfésúnà òun àkòkó.* (o. i. 7)

She says, on consulting with an Ifa priest, it was revealed that she could not be healed, neither could she have children, except she went back to marry her former fiancé.

This shows that when the African is faced with a serious situation, he still goes back to seek solution from the African Traditional Religion practitioners. Contrary to the believe of Christianity and Islam that African Traditional Religion practitioners worship idols, and not the living God, traditional region practioners only send divinities as emissaries to Almighty God, just as Jesus Christ and the Prophet Muhammed in Christianity and Islam respectively. It is undisputable that, it is only God who knows who worships him truthfully and sincerely. Thus, no man should stand in condemnation or judgement of anyone or any group when it comes to the issue of religion.

Everyman is created by God, and shall return to Him to give an account of his sojourn in life. No one religion teaches its believers cruelty and wickedness to fellow beings. The religions are only there to guide man towards the ideal in behaviour and also to moderate man's conduct and behaviour on earth. This is why Adéniji (2008:33) avers that it is needless to fight religious wars or to encourage conflicts in religion, because God is able to make all humanity to practise a single religion, if that had been His plans for the world. Probably, because he is God of variety, He has chosen that humanity worship him in diverse ways, through variety of religions of the world.

Ultimately, the practitioners of each of the religion acknowledge the supremacy of Almighty God, as Fágúnwà notes in *Ògbójú Ọdẹ Ninú Ighó Irúnmalẹ*. After Àkàrà-ògùn is captured by an unnamed mysterious being whose body is covered by scales and who is a hunchback, during his travail in captivity, Àkàrà-ògùn laments thus:

*Nígbàtí ó wá pé sí, ibití mo tí sùnà yé mi, mo ríi pé mo tí ẹ
ògun sí ni nkò fi tí Ọlórún ẹ! Mo tí gbàgbé pé Ọn li ó dá
ewé tí ó sì dá eghò igi. Kí ilẹ ọjó keta tó mọ sí mo ké sí*

Olórun, mo wí báyii pé: Olódumarè, Olójó òní, òràn yí mà pọ́ju mí lọ! Bá mi sé é o, bá mi sé é, èmi kò mà lè nìkan sé é o. Olórun jòwó bá mi sé é. Mà jéki ndi ije fun okunrin yi; mà jéki ó fi aghári mi fon fèrè, mà jéki nṣégbé sínú igbó yii; mà jéki nti ihin di èrò òrun; mà jéki nkú bí adie ti i kú; mà sì jéki okunrin yi je mí hí ológbò ti ije èkúté. Bí elégún bá bọ ēgún tití, òdò Rẹ ni yìò fi àbò sí, bí onísàngó bọ sàngó tití, òdò Rẹ ni yìò fi àbò sí; bí olóya bọ oya tití, òdò Rẹ ni yìò fi àbò sí. Awon onímàlè á mã sìn Ó gégé hí Ànábì; awon onigbàgbó á ma fi gbogbo ojó aiyé won fun O. Jòwó yọ mí o, jòwó yọ mí: èmi kò lè nìkan yọ ara mí Olórun jòwó yọ mí.
(o. i. 25)

After some time, I realized where I went wrong, I realized that I was relying on charms only, I didn't invite God into my situation. I had forgotten that He is the one who created herbs, and also trees. Before the dawn of the third day, I called on God, I said: God, the owner of this day, this situation is beyond me! Arise and help me. God, please come and help me, help me solve this problem as I cannot do it alone. God, please help me out, don't allow me to be devoured by this man; don't let me perish in this forest; don't let me end my life here; don't let me die like a common fowl; don't let this man devour me up as a cat devours up a rat. When the masquerade makes sacrifice to masquerade cult, he returns to you, when the Sàngó worshipper sacrifices to Sàngó, he returns to you; when Oya worshipper sacrifices to her, he/she returns to you. The Muslims worship you through Ànábì (the Prophet Mohammed); the Christians dedicate all their days to you. Please, set me free, I cannot set myself free, God, please, set me free.

This reveals the Yorùbá's resort to prayers in difficult situations. Àkàrà-ògùn acknowledges the power, supremacy and absolute powers of God, while acknowledging traditional religion practitioners, Muslims and Christians as dedicating their lives to God, and ultimately worshipping the only supreme God. From the above, it is obvious that the Yorùbá and other societies are deeply religious and cannot survive without religion. It therefore implies that if everyone follows the teachings of his chosen religion and, at least, attempts to tolerate people who practise other religions, and to recognize that, ultimately, everyone worships the one living God, living and life will be more meaningful.

5.2 Economy and culture

The Yorùbá traditional society is essentially an “agrarian society”. Agriculture is the most important productive economic activity in Yorùbáland. Hence, the Yorùbá are mostly farmers. Agriculture is the mainstay of any nation’s economy. The south-western part of Nigeria, where the Yorùbá are located, is particularly known for agriculture. According to Sills (1976, cited in Fájényò, 2007), agriculture provides food, clothing, shelter, industrial products and employment. To further assert the importance which the Yorùbá place on agriculture, in an Ìjálá chant, Àlàbí Ògúndépò (cited in Fájényò 2003:13) says:

Lílé: *Àtéléwó ò tanniyàn rí,
Bí a bá yòlẹ̀ nìkan
Layé í sù ní
È jé a mò ọ̀n dáko
È jé a mò ọ̀n dáko*

Ègbè: *Àgbẹ̀ ló nilú
È jé a mò ọ̀n dáko*

Lílé: *È gbìnṣu
Gb`ànámó
È ghin kòkó lóko*

Ègbè: *È gbìngbàdo gbìnfó
È gbìnlá
È tún gbìnsàn*

Lílé: *È gbìngé
È gbìnlá pèlata
È gbewébè sàkùurò*

Lead: Your palms cannot deceive you
It is only when you are lazy
That you are tired of this world
Let us farm
Let us farm

Refrain: Farmers own the town
Let us farm

Lead: (You) plant yam
Plant sweet potato

Refrain: (You) plant maize
Plant vegetable
(You) plant orange also.

Lead: (You) plant cassava
Plant okro and pepper
(You) plant vegetables in water-side garden.

The Yorùbá place a very high premium on agriculture. They constantly make reference to it in their discussions and in their aphorisms. *Encarta Encyclopedia premium* (2007) claims that: "Farming is the occupation, business or science of cultivating the land, producing crops and raising livestock". The Yorùbá keep 'Okò etilé'. This type of farm is not too far away from home. In it is planted, maize, cocoyam, yam, plantain, banana, cassava et cetera. In *Àdìitú Olódùmarè*, it is mentioned that Àdìitú's father, had a very big farm:

*Òbìrí-aiyé dá okò lẹ̀ rẹ̀bẹ̀tẹ̀, ó gbìn iṣu, àgbàdo, awújẹ, erè,
ó gbìn onírìurú ata gbogbo, àti ata kékeré ati òlá, gbogbo
wón pò lẹ̀ bẹ̀rẹ̀, ní odún yì, iṣu Òbìrí ta bọ̀òkù, àgbàdo yọ
omọ̀ hòkùà, ọ̀gẹ̀dẹ̀ yọ omọ̀ gbàkùà, erè so jinwinnì, ẹ̀fọ̀rí
gbẹ̀gẹ̀bege...* (o. i. 6)

Òbìrí-aiyé cultivated hectares of land in which he planted yam, maize, cowpea, beans and different types of pepper, small and large pepper, they were so much. In that year, Òbìrí had a bumper harvest.

In *Jé Ng L'ògbà tẹ̀mì*, Ládélé testifies to the agrarian nature and bumper harvest of Bánkólé during harvesting period:

*Àgbẹ̀ gíràá ni Bánkólé í ẹ̀. Àní gbogbo èniyàn ló mọ̀n ọ̀n
ní olóko òlá ní ìlu Ọ̀wọ̀... Iṣu rẹ̀, àgbàdo rẹ̀ níi kòkọ̀ wọ̀ sọ̀sọ̀
gẹ̀gẹ̀ bí àkọ̀so okò. Tí ó bá dì inú ikórè, ní kí o wá wòó bí
Bánkólé yòò tí máa ru iṣu, àgbàdo, irẹ̀ké, ata, ẹ̀gú sí, igbá,
àti oríṣíríṣí irẹ̀ lẹ̀ sí sọ̀sọ̀ fún títà lẹ̀jọ̀ ikórè.* (o. i. 27)

Bánkólé is a typical farmer. Everybody knows him as a big-time farmer in Ọ̀wọ̀ town. His yam, maize, are the first set of crops to be taken to church as the new crops of the harvest season. During the harvest period, you would see Bánkólé carrying yam, maize, sugar cane, pepper, melon, garden-egg and varieties of farm produce to the church for sale during the harvest day.

In *Kékeré Èkùn*, Dèkúnlé makes a declaration to Bádéjò during a conversation, that he prefers farming to any other profession:

*Ní tẹ̀mí, isẹ̀ oko riro ni bàbá mi fì lé mi lówó, òn nàà ni ng
ó sì fì lé omọ mi lówó. Kí ni ó tilẹ̀ n sọ pàápàá? Sẹbí nígbàtí
omọ ọ̀gá ilú lọ s'ílú ọ̀bá ní ijeèlò lẹ̀hìn gbogbo iwé tí o kà,
isẹ̀ àgbẹ̀ ló tún lọ kọ. (o. i. 7)*

As far as I am concerned, my father bequeathed a legacy of farming to me. That is what I am going to hand over to my children. What are you saying? When our boss's son travelled to Britain the other time, after all the formal education he had received, he went to study Agriculture.

In *Kádàrà àti Ègbọn rẹ*, Àgbégbẹ̀mí celebrates the graduation of his son, who has been under his tutelage to learn the farming profession.

*Nígbàtí Àkóbí dàgbà tó omọ ọ̀dún méréndìnlógún, bàbá rẹ̀
pe àwọn ẹbí jọ láti wá bá òun ya isẹ̀ fún un... (o. i. 3)*

When Àkóbí attained the age of sixteen, his father invited extended family members to celebrate Àkóbí's freedom of his chosen profession of farming...

In traditional Yoruba society, subsistence and professional farming are encouraged as almost all

Families practise farming in one form or the other. In the same text, we see Àlàbí teaching his pupils; he leads them to sing the song:

<i>Àlàbí:</i>	<i>Tani òp'ẹ̀mi Àgbẹ̀ o?</i>
<i>Àwọn omọdẹ:</i>	<i>Àgbẹ̀</i>
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	<i>Isẹ̀ oko ni mò n̄sẹ.</i>
<i>Àwọn omọdẹ:</i>	<i>Àgbẹ̀</i>
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	<i>Irẹ̀ oko ni mò n̄ká.</i>
<i>Àwọn omọdẹ:</i>	<i>Àgbẹ̀</i>
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	<i>Isẹ̀ kil'àgbẹ̀ n̄sẹ?</i>
<i>Àwọn omọdẹ:</i>	<i>Àgbẹ̀</i>
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	<i>Oko l'àgbẹ̀ n̄ro.</i>
<i>Àwọn omọdẹ:</i>	<i>Àgbẹ̀</i>
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	<i>Mo gbin 'lá, mo gbin 'gbá</i>
<i>Àwọn omọdẹ:</i>	<i>Àgbẹ̀</i>

<i>Àlàbí:</i>	<i>Mo gbin 'su, mo gbin 'kàn</i>
<i>Àwọn ọmọdẹ:</i>	<i>Àgbẹ</i>
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	<i>Iṣé kí l'àgbẹ́ nǹx?</i>
<i>Àwọn ọmọdẹ:</i>	<i>Àgbẹ</i>
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	<i>Okò l'àgbẹ́ nro</i>
<i>Àwọn ọmọdẹ:</i>	<i>Àgbẹ (o. i. 64)</i>
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	Who calls me a farmer?
Pupils:	Farmer
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	I am a farmer
Pupils:	Farmer
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	I am harvesting
Pupils:	Farmer
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	What does a farmer do?
Pupils:	Farmer
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	A farmer tills the land
Pupils:	Farmer
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	I planted okro, I planted garden egg
Pupils:	Farmer
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	I planted yam, I planted garden egg
Pupils:	Farmer
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	What does a farmer do?
Pupils:	Farmer
<i>Àlàbí:</i>	Farmer tills the land
Pupils:	Farmer

From the above, it is obvious that there are a whole lot of varieties of natural and healthy foods and fruits to choose from the Yorùbá farm produce.

Consequent upon the European incursion into the Yorùbá society in the areas of economy, education, religion, government et cetera, the mode of exchange gradually became the bank notes or currency. This brought about a significant change from the earliest form of goods and commodities exchange, which had been "trade by barter", and later the use of cowries. However, the Yorùbá are very honest in

transacting their businesses. In *Ìrèké Onibùdó*, after the hero's dead mother appears to him,

*Nìgbàtí iyá mi lọ tán, mo fí orí lé ọ̀nà ibi tí ó fihàn mí, nìgbàtí
ó ẹ̀, mo dé oríta kan, mo sì bá ọ̀gèdè pupa nìbẹ̀. mo kígbẹ̀ títí,
kí ẹnítí ńta ọ̀gèdè nàà dá mi lóhùn, sùgbón nkò gbó ohùn kan,
mo sì wo ọ̀gèdè nà, kòju ti sílẹ̀ kan lọ, mo bá fí sílẹ̀ kan sílẹ̀,
mo kó ọ̀gèdè lọ.*
(o. i. 72)

After my mother had left, I followed the direction she showed me, I went on. After a little walk, I became hungry; on getting to a junction, I saw some plantain there. I called out to the owner or the plantain, but there was no reply. I looked at the plantain, it was not worth more than one shilling. So I dropped one shilling there, and took away the plantain.

This is an indication of the level of honesty and sincerity of the Yorùbá in the precolonial era.

Today, the situation is different; it is either the commodity is totally stolen away without the commensurate money left in its place, or if money is left, the so left money is stolen by somebody else. These and many ideals form the principles, paradigms and cultural values of the Yorùbá. They were what made the society enjoyable before the advent of colonialism. The traditional Yoruba society depended mostly on agriculture for the development of its economy as farm produce, especially cash crops were often exported as major source of foreign exchange.

5.2.1. Cash crops farming

Akínjógbin (2002:94) says the sale of cocoa produce, for example, by the Action Group (AG) government, a political party under the leadership of late Chief Ọbáfẹmi Awólówò, recorded tremendous success and progress between 1952 and 1962, free-pay education was introduced in 1950. The government built the then first modern stadium and established the first television broadcasting station in the whole of Africa. The first high-rise building in Nigeria, Cocoa House, twenty-five-storey high was built by that government. Cocoa industry bloomed and the economy was generally buoyant.

Bámgbóşé (1974:10) comments on the setting of Yorùbá novels in relation to agriculture: "Although, in most of the novels, the setting is usually that of rural

life, with its agricultural pursuits of western education". The plantation farm is usually far away from home. In the farms were planted, the "Igi owó" cash crops. In these farms where such crops that take a number of years before they bring forth their yields, such as, cocoa, cashew, palm-trees, rubber, coffee, kolanut, walnut, cotton and the likes were planted. On harvest, the produce of these crops were sold for a lot of money which enriched the Yorùbá. This is why, the Yorùbá say: "Ìgbé lowó wă" (Money resides in the bush). An example of this is observed in *Àjẹkú Layé*:

Oko ni Bámgbólúú àti iyàwó rè lẹ lǝjǝ kan, wǝn fé ká obi diẹ, kí wǝn tà, kí owó diẹ lẹ fi wà lǝwǝ wǝn. (o. i. 55)

Bámgbólúú and his wife went to the farm one day, to harvest some kolanuts that they will sell in order to have some money.

Another example of this is noted in *Jẹ Ng L'ògbà Tèmi*, where Bánkólé's source of income is discussed:

... Wǝn yòd sǝ wǝ ìgbé lẹ láti máa sa èrè-òpẹ, èyí ni eyin òpẹ tí ó ti rè lóri iya rè (o. i. 27)

...They would then go to the plantations to pick ripe palm-fruits, these were the ripe fruits of the palm that fell from the palm trees.

The palm fruits are processed into palm-oil used in preparation of food and it also serves as a source of income for the family as the palm-oil is sold or sometimes exported. Palm fruit is one of the cash crops available in Yorùbá society.

5.2.2. Food crops

According to *The World Book Encyclopedia*, horticulture (Latin "hortus" , garden cutmar; cultivation) is the science and art of growing fruits, flowers, vegetables, shrubs and trees. Crops such as corn, guinea-corn, millet, pepper, tomatoes, yam, sweet potatoes, cassava et cetera were cultivated as food crops. Fruits such as mangoes, banana, plantain, oranges, grapes, cashew, groundnut, paw-paw, coconut, pine-apple, lime, cherries and so on were cultivated for consumption. Vegetables such as okro, ewedu, spinach, water melon, water leaf, bitter leaf, şokò, pumpkin and so on were cultivated by the farmers.

In *Kádàrá àti Ègbòn rẹ*, Odúnjọ and Oládípúpọ discuss the issue of farming.

This is made obvious in the praise poetry of Àgbégbémí thus:

*Àgbé gbè mí, àgbé gbè `ran mí, iṣé oko l'orí dá mí pé kí ng
máa ṣe, èmi Àtándá òkín elégbàá ọpẹ, àní akóṣu kàràbàtá
kàràbàtá l'òko, àbí ewùrà kòròhòrò kòròhòrò l'èbè. (o. i. 1)*

Farming pays me, I am destined to farm, I Àtándá òkín who
has two thousand palms, with big yams, and big water yams.

Apart from cultivating yam, cassava, beans, rice, sweet potatoes and so forth, the
Yorùbá planted fruits as complement. For instance, in the novel *Ògbójú Qdẹ Nínú
Igbó Irúnmalẹ*, Àkàrà-ògùn talks about an orchard:

*... Nígbà tí ó-pě díẹ, mo já sí ọgbà igi eléso kan tí ó kún fún
onírúurú èso didùn, irú èyí tí n kò ì tii rí jẹ láti ọjó tí mo
tí sìnà yìi. Mo rí ibépe, ọsàn, ọpẹ òyìnbó, òro, ọgèdè pupa,
òrombó àti onírúurú èso igi mìràn tí ó ti orígun méréèrin
ayé wá sí ilé náà. (o. i. 67)*

After a short while, I reached an orchard that was filled with
different kinds of delicious fruits, the type that I had not
eaten since the day I missed my way. I saw pawpaw, orange,
pineapple, bush-mango, banana, and other fruit trees that
were got from the whole world.

5.2.3. Livestock keeping

Omoyinmi (2008), an agriculturist, in an unstructured interview opines that:
“agriculture is the art of collecting world birds from the wild, and also it is the art of
rearing the domesticated birds at home and deliberately rearing and nurturing them
for human benefits”.

The average Yorùbá man, while cultivating the soil, growing and harvesting crops
also raise livestock. The grains harvested from crop farming are fed to the livestock.
Also, the shaft of processed crops, like maize and guinea-corn that are left after
milling grains and extracting “Ògi” (maize paste) are fed to the livestock; while the
waste of the animals and birds so kept, are in turn used as fertilizer to the soil in order
to have a bumper harvest.

The Yorùbá are really highly intelligent and economical. Their traditional
system is scientific in nature. Even though, they were not exposed to scientific study

of animal husbandry, they kept animals for both domestic consumption and commercial purposes. Dairy farmers keep large flocks of different animals for economic and family purposes. Crops and domestic meat supplies were also augmented by fish and wildfowl as well as by the meat of wild animals. An instance of free range poultry keeping is seen in *Ìrèké Onibùdó*. *Ìrèké Onibùdó* says:

Báyì ní mo bèrè isé ní oko okùnrin náà, nígbà tí ó di ojó kejì mo sàkiyèsì pé ó ní àgbégbò adìe kan tí ó ní omọ lẹhin, mo sì bẹẹ bóyá ó lè jé kí n máa bá òun tójú àwọn adìe náà, kí a jọ máa pín omọ èhin rẹ. sùgbón ó kò, ó wí fún mí pé àfí tí mo bá ma ra eyò kan nínú àwọn omọ èhin adìe náà. Bẹẹ ní wọn kéré púpò, wọn kò ju omọ ojó méta lọ. Mo bèrè iye tí yóò ta òkan nínú àwọn omọ adìe náà, ó wí fún mí pé épìnni ní, mo sì rà á, bẹẹ ní mo lo épìnni tí n bẹ nínú àpò mí. Nígbà tí ó di odún kan géré, adìe mí kékeré tí mo rà tí dàgbà, ó sì yé eyin méjọ, méjéjọ l'ó pa, méje sì jé abo; òkan jé àkùkọ. Ó yà mí lénú láti rí i pé òkan soso kò tilẹ kú nínú àwọn omọ adìe náà. Nígbà tí ó sì tún ma di odún kejì, àwọn abo wònni tún ti yé, òkòòkan tún yé méjọ, àwọn omọ wọn tún dàgbà tí èyíkèyí kò kú nínú wọn. Bẹẹbẹẹ mo di aládiẹ, mo sì ní tò òdúnrún adìe, kí n tò bèrè sí tà wọn. Lójó tí mo kó ta adìe mí, mo pa pòun mewa lóko wa.

(o. i. 50 - 51)

This was how I started to work as a labourer at the man's farm. On the following day, I observed that he had a hen that had just hatched her chicken. And I beseeched to him to allow me to take care of the hen and her chicks, so that we could share her chicks, but he refused and told me that I could only buy one of the chicks, and the chicks were so young that they were not more than three-days old. I asked how much he was willing to sell the chick and he told me that he would sell it for half-a-penny and I bought it. This was how I spent the half penny that I had in my pocket. Exactly a year after, the little chick that I bought had grown up and laid eight eggs, she hatched the eight: seven hens and one cock. I was surprised to see that none of them died. In the second year, the hens also laid their eggs and each of them hatched eight chickens, their chickens also grew and none of them died. This was how I had a very big poultry and I had up to three hundred chickens before I started to sell them. The first day I sold some of them, I realized ten pounds in our farm.

These days, mechanized farming has been introduced, and large scale, animal husbandry and poultry farming are practised. This is a welcome development, as it enables farmers to farm on a large scale and also rear birds and animals using

scientific methods for better harvest and dairy production. The introduction of new technology, and mechanized farming, such as the use of fertilizer, insecticides and fungicides, soil make up, preservations and nutritional needs of farm animals improve farm yield, safety and faster growth of animals and poultry birds.

5.2.4. Pastoral farming

This is an act of breeding, feeding and managing animals or livestock, for the production of food. Goats, pigs, sheep, horses, dogs and cats are kept in the Yorùbá traditional organisation. The Yorùbá also practise pastoral farming as a profession in *Kádàrá ati Ègbòrè rẹ̀*. *Kádàrá* opts for animal husbandry as a profession; he prefers it to crop farming.

*Ní àkótán, iṣẹ̀ oko ríro kò wù mí tó bẹ̀; iṣẹ̀ tí òkàn tẹ̀mí
ńfà síjù nì iṣẹ̀ ẹ̀ran síṣìn... (o. i. 12)*

Moreover, I am not really interested in crop farming; the profession I prefer is pastoral farming...

Ọ̀dúnjọ and Ọ̀ládípúpọ̀ mention about *Ewéréndé*, a wealthy man in *Aiyédùn* town, who has a field of animals.

*Àwọ̀n ilẹ̀-oko tí ó tí jogún bá repete, owó rẹ̀ tí ó pọ̀ yamùrà;
àti àwọ̀n ohun àlùmòni lórísírísi míràn gégé bí agbo ẹ̀ran,
màlúù àti àgùtàn... (o. i. 95)*

He inherited a large expanse of land, his great wealth and his numerous valuable possessions like a field of animals, such as cows and sheep...

In the same text, we read about *Ìyábò*, who takes *Kádàrá* to her late husband's farm, where he reared different animals on a large scale:

*Lẹ̀hinnáà, ó tún mú Kádàrá lọ oko ọ̀kọ rẹ̀ níbití pápá tẹ́jú
dàradára fún ẹ̀ran síṣìn, ó sì múu mọ̀ àwọ̀n míràn tí nwón
ńṣe iṣẹ̀ ẹ̀ran síṣìn ní àdúgbò ihè hákannáà... Báyi nì Kádàrá
bẹ̀rẹ̀ iṣẹ̀ ẹ̀ran síṣìn rẹ̀, ó kọ̀ abúlẹ̀ kan tí Àlào ńgbẹ̀ nì oko, ó
sì tún gba ẹ̀nikan pẹ̀lú. (o. i. 194)*

After that, she took *Kádàrá* to her husband's farm, where there was an open field for rearing animals, she also introduced him to other pastoral farmers in the locality... This was how *Kádàrá* began his profession of animal husbandry, he built a hut on the farm, where *Àlào* lived, he also employed an additional hand.

5.2.5. Medicine and pharmacy

Among the notable professions practised by the Yorùbá are the medical and herbal practices. The medical herbal practitioners and pharmacists are called "Oníṣègùn" and "Adáhunṣe", respectively. They used medicinal herbs for both preventive and curative purposes. The profession of Ifá divination is among the most popular among the Yorùbá. The practitioners are consulted to communicate with Ọ̀rúnmilà and the divinities in order to solve problems of various kinds.

In *Igbó Olódùmarè*, Olówó-Aiyé, the narrator, asserts that hunting, herbal-profession and Ifá priesthood go together.

*Àkàrà-ògùn ni mí nitòótó, oníṣègùn ni baba tí ó bí mí í ṣe,
babaláwo sì ni pẹ̀lú, òògùn kún inú ilé wa dé enu, bẹ̀é ni
nríkan abàmì nì bẹ̀ ní kòrò iyàrà...* (o. i. 14)

Truly, I am Àkàrà-ògùn, my father is a herbalist, as well as a babaláwo, there are several kinds of charms in our house, so also dangerous materials are in the corner of our room...

5.2.7 Hunting and fishing

Hunting and fishing are also practised by the Yorùbá. Hunting, according to Banwo and Danmole (2005:284) is regarded as a respected profession because of the risks, local knowledge and wisdom involved. This is aptly described in the saying:

*B'òdẹ̀ bá rò 'sẹ̀, b'òdẹ̀ bá rò 'ya.
B'òdẹ̀ bá pẹ̀ran, kò ní í f'énìkan jẹ.*

If a hunter thinks about his tribulations, if a hunter thinks about his suffering. If a hunter kills game, he would not share it with anyone.

In all of Fágúnwà's novels, the hero is always a hunter, who is sent on an expedition in quest of solving one problem or in quest of acquiring knowledge and wisdom. In *Ìrìnkèrindò nínú Igbó Elégbèje*, Fágúnwà considers hunters as very brave and courageous:

Kò sí ògboiyà tí ó dàbí ọ̀dẹ̀ (o. i. 91)

There is none as courageous as a hunter.

An example of this is when the king of Irinkèrindò's town invites him to lead other hunters to bring back home "Èso Igi Irònú", the fruit of the tree of thought.

*Isé tí mo fé ràn ọ̀ nì yí, mo fé kí ọ̀ wá ẹ̀ a sájú àwọn ọ̀dẹ̀
miràn, kí ẹ̀ wá lọ̀ sí Òkè Irònú tí rí bẹ̀ nínú Igbó Elégbèje,
kí ẹ̀ wá lọ̀ ká èso igi irònú fún mí wá.* (o. i. 11)

This is the errand I want to send you, I want you to be the leader of other hunters, you should all go to Òkè Irònú in Igbó Elégbèje, and and pluck the fruit of Irònú tree for me.

Apart from the fact that hunters hunt for game and make available games' meat which is a good source of protein, they sell excess game after they had taken enough for their family consumption. The skins of such game are either kept for posterity or used for leather works. Examples of these leather works are waist belts, shoes, bags, suitcases, armllets, hats, leather watch, and leather furniture. Leather is also used by the Muslims as prayer mats. The skin of such games such as snakes, leopards, and crocodiles are also sold. Some animal parts are used for concoction, medicine and other purposes.

Besides these, hunters were in charge of security in major towns and villages. Olórí-ọ̀dẹ̀ (head of the hunters) and his fellow hunters kept watch against external invasion and internal marauders. In pre-colonial days, under the hunters guard, instances of robbery, stealing and burgling were not as rampant as it is these days. Hunters who double as herbalists or Ifá practitioners and practise traditional medicines are the ones who have the courage and what it takes to go on hunting expedition. The courage of hunters and the security they provide is presented in *Ogun Àwítélé*, where Fáléti describes the efforts of hunters that were called upon to safeguard and protect the citizens of a town from the menace of the armed robbers who write to inform the Baálẹ̀ of their impending plan to invade and rob the citizens.

*Nígbà tí èmi àti Ìkólàbà dé 'lé, a bẹ̀rẹ̀ sí ronú bí a ó ẹ̀ rí àwọn
ọ̀dẹ̀ tí ó nílá rí kọ̀jọ, nítórí pé ọ̀rọ̀ tí ó dé 'lé yí, ọ̀rọ̀ ìgboiyà nì,
ọ̀rọ̀ akíkanjú sì nì pẹ̀lú, kii ẹ̀ ọ̀rọ̀ ojo, Gbogbo àwọn ìjòyè-
ọ̀dẹ̀ ìyókù nì a kọ̀ ké sí ná - A sápa, Ọ̀tún Olúọ̀dẹ̀, Ọ̀sì Olúọ̀dẹ̀,
Balógun Olúọ̀dẹ̀ àti Àjànà...* (o. i. 10)

When Ìkólàbà and I got home, we began to think about how to assemble competent hunters, because the issue on ground was a matter of bravery, it was also an issue of courage: it was

not an issue of cowardice. All the titled chief hunters were the ones we initially enlisted – Asipa, Otún Olúḡḡe, Òsì Olúḡḡe, Balógun Olúḡḡe àti Àjànà...

The above thus indicates that courageous hunters provided security against night marauders and invaders in pre-colonial and post colonial Yoruba society.

5.2.7. Other professions

There are many other professions that are used to boost economic practices of the Yorùbá. To each of these practices are apprentices, who are under the tutelage of professionals in order to learn the arts. Most importantly is the fact that professions run in families. Hence, the young learn the professions of their parents from generation to generation.

In *Ògbójú Ode Nini Ighó Irinmole*, Fágúnwà speaks through Íràgbèje and chastise children thus:

Ṣá tẹramó isékísé tí ìwọ bá n sẹ: àti àgbé ni ó, àti akòwé ni ó, àti onísòwò ni ó, òkan kò yàtò, jùbẹ ọ fífi ojú sí isé eni ni baba owó nini.
(o. i. 74)

Work hard at any profession that you practise; be it farming, be it clerical work, be it trading, there is no difference among them, the most thing is concentrating on one's profession, which results in riches.

In *Olówólayémò*, Jéḡḡà depicts barbing as one of the professions practised by the Yorùbá. The practitioners are referred to as Onígbàjamò.

Ní àṣálé ojó kan, ni mo ọ sí ọdò onígbàjamò kan kí ó bá mi ge irun mi.
(o. i. 105)

One night, I went to a barber to have my hair cut.

The Yorùbá also engage in building profession, as revealed in *Olówólayémò*. Olówólayémò's father employs the services of a builder, who is to build a special house for his boss. Thus, Olówólayémò reveals:

Lẹhin tí wọn sì joko, baba mi fi Animáṣaun hàn, Gẹgẹ bí ọmọlé tí o mọ nipa isẹ ile daradara.
(o. i., 3.)

After they were seated, my father introduced Animásun to his boss.
As a professional bricklayer.

There are also professional sculptors among the Yorùbá, in *Àdiitú Olódùmarè*.
Àdiitú describes how creative, sculptors of Ifèhinti town are:

*Ní gbogbo ilú òde aiyé yí, kò sí èyí tí àwọn ènià imú rẹ̀ mọ̀
isẹ̀ àfowóṣe bí ilú Ifèhinti. Bí nwón fì amọ̀ mọ̀ ènià, ighàtí
olúwarè há sòrò síí tí kò dáhùn ni yìò tó mọ̀ pé amọ̀ ni.* (o. i. 22)

In all the towns on earth, there is none whose citizens are
as good in sculpture as those of Ifèhinti town. If they use
mud to mould someone, it is until you talk to it before
you realize that it is a statue.

All these show the Yorùbá as diligent and hard-working people, as
confirmed by the Yorùbá saying that: "A kì í mú isẹ̀ jẹ, kí a tún mú isẹ̀ jẹ" (If one
chooses not to work, one cannot escape poverty). In *Kúyẹ*, Oúnjọ presents a
bùrùkùtù (a local liquor made of millet and guinea corn) seller:

*Bí owó diẹ̀ bú wà l'owó Àdigùn, òun pàápàá á máa
mu iwón otí bùrùkùtù oni kọbọ̀ méjì tàbí mēta.* (o. i. 27)

Whenever Adigun has a little money to spend,
he too usually takes a little local liquor of about two or three kobo.

In *Ó Le Kú*, Àjàní buys palm-wine from a palm-wine tapper, who hawks with his
bicycle.

*Níbití wón ti n takùròsọ, bàbá elému ti gun kẹkẹ̀ dé. Wón
tún ra emu t'Àjàní fẹ̀ wá gbé fún àwọn ọ̀rẹ̀ rẹ̀ lógbà.* (o. i. 45)

As they were chatting, a palm-wine tapper arrived on his
bicycle. They also bought the palm-wine which Ajani
intended to take to his friends on campus.

Fágúnwà, in *Ọ̀gbójú ọ̀dẹ̀ nínú Igbó Irúnmọ̀lẹ̀*, counsels parents about child
training. He charges them with the obligation of ensuring that their children are
enrolled to learn a specific profession and be the best in such chosen profession.

*Kó ọ̀mọ̀ rẹ̀ ní isẹ̀ tí ó dára. Bí ó ẹ̀ àgbẹ̀ ni, kọ̀p dáradára, wò
bí àwọn ènià dídú ẹ̀ ni ilẹ̀ tó, Eléda ni ó fì ta baba nlá wón
l'ọ̀rẹ̀; bí ó ẹ̀ ọ̀wò sí ẹ̀ ni, kọ̀p kí ó jíná; bí ó sì ẹ̀ gbénàgbénà
ni, kọ̀p kí ó yée dáradára, máṣe jẹ́ kí ó ẹ̀ eléyí diẹ̀, kí ó ẹ̀*

tòhùn díè, kí ó máa fò tí orí òkàn dé orí èkejì. (o. i. 73)

Teach your child a particular trade. Be it farming, teach him well, look at how the black people are blessed with a large expanse of land. It is the creator that gave it to their progenitors as a gift. If it is to learn a trade, teach him to perfection. If it is carpentry work, teach him to master it well. Do not allow him to be jack of all trades, moving from one type of trade to the other.

5.3. Women and economy

Women play important roles in their different professional callings in societies and have proved their worth as women of substance. Some women have also excelled in their different areas of endeavour (Shehu, 2000:13). In *Àyànmó*, Qlábímtán comments on Jòkè and her law profession.

Nítorípé Jòkè tí ñ sísé lóyà ní ilú òyìnbó, kò nira fún un rárá láti rí isé ní Nàìjíríà. Láti ilú òyìnbó ní àwọn òyìnbó onísòwò kan tí fún òun náà ní isé tí nwón ní kí ó máa se asojú àwọn ní Èkó; owó òlá ní nwón sì gbà láti san fún un gégé bí àyè rẹ.
(o. i. 106)

Because Jòkè had been practising law abroad, it was not difficult for her to get a job in Nigeria. Some white traders from abroad had offered her a job, that she should represent them in Lagos; they agreed to pay her a fat salary that befits her status.

Fámílúsi (1998:9) also asserts that besides the domestic responsibilities of women, they tend small gardens behind the house to supplement men's income. He says:

The traditional Yorùbá women dominated the business world as they played a prominent role in the economic field. They assisted the men to plant and harvest some crops. The duty of selling of food items like yam, corn, vegetable was totally reserved for women.

Women keep and maintain *Okò Etilé* (commercial farms) and wetland farms. They usually sell the produce of such farms and keep the rest of the produce for family consumption. Though, women also inherit *Okò Egàn* (plantation farm) from their parents, the usual practise is for them to employ *Alágbàro* (labourers) to work in such farms. Such labourers are paid based on agreed rates. Women's pre-occupation is in the area of processing of farm produce in *Ebu* (cottage refinery) where they process

palm fruits into palm-oil, palm-kernel and local black soap. In *Kádàrá àti Ègbon rẹ* we read about Àgbégbémí's wife. She is industrious:

*Olurànlówó pàtàkì ní ó jẹ́ fún oko rẹ, bí ó ẹ nipa sí ẹ isé
ilé ni, tàbí nipa bibá a ta àwọn nkan oko rẹ ní ojà, kò ní
iròjù rárá fún isé-kísé láti ẹ... (o. i. 2)*

She is a notable helper to her husband, when it comes to domestic chores, or assisting him to sell his farm produce, she does not hesitate to do any kind of work...

Women also weave baskets and local brooms. Both men and women are involved in weaving. Women are also *Onídìrì* (hairdressers). In *Kékeré Èkùn*, Olábímtán describes hairdressing as a profitable profession practised by women, in a discussion between Bádéjọ and Dékúnlé:

*...Hówù, ẹbí irun ni iyàwó omo Àdìgún yẹn ndi tà, irun si
ni iyàwó tire nà ndi. Èlò ní iyàwó tire npa l'ósù? Pónùn
m'èédógún ni nwón nfun obinrin yẹn lósù... (o. i. 7)*

Is it not hairdressing that Àdìgún's daughter does, and your wife is also a hairdresser. How much does your wife earn monthly? That woman is paid twenty five pounds per month...

In *Omo Òkú Òrun*, Odúnjọ shares with the readers Àbèké's criticism of her hairdresser:

*Tàbí olóriburúkú ni iyá onídìrì yíi kẹ? E wo orí tí mo ní kí ó
dì fún mi ní kòlèsè, bí ó ti ẹ gogoro bí orí alákorí... (o. i. 1)*

Is this hairdresser an unfortunate woman? Look at the hair I asked her to plait in all-back style as it is plaited high like that of a good-for-nothing person...

In *Àyànmó*, the novelist writes about Àlàkẹ, Àlàbí's wife, and her tailoring profession thus:

*Gbogbo aṣọ àwọn iyàwó Tisà Aiyéro àti aṣọ àwọn omo wọn,
òun ni ó n rán an... Nígbatì òun náà rí bí ènià ti nwó ní òdò
òun, ó gba ìwé ọtí títà, ó sì tún n ta ọtí. Nipa báyi, nwón tún
nra ọtí ní ilé-itàjà rẹ, nwón sì n muú pèlú, kò sí irú onisé ijoba
tí kii lọ sí ilé-itàjà iya 'Gbénga. Nibè ni àwọn ọlọpàá tí n ghádùn
lẹhin isé, nibè ni woléwolé n pari isé sí, nibè ni àwọn tisà náà
n mu aṣọ tí nwón fé rán lọ... (o. i. 94)*

She sews all the clothes of Aiyéro teachers' wives and those of their children... When she sees how people patronise her, she obtained a liquor licence, and began to sell liquor. This way, they buy liquor and also takes it there, there is no kind of civil servants that does not patronise iya 'Gbénga. That is where police officers enjoy themselves after work, that is where sanitary inspectors end the day's work, that is where teachers also take their clothes for sewing...

This shows that Àláké is a well known professional tailor that is patronised by many.

Bàbá Rere, depicts Jùmòké; Dúró's wife, who trades in textile materials:

Aṣọ ni Jùmòké; iyàwó Dúró n rà tà. (o. i. 3)

Jùmòké; Dúró's wife trades in textile materials.

But iyá Àjíké is well known in Musin as a harlot:

Ilé ọtí ni ó fi n ẹ ilé, ibè ni ó sì ti n ẹ ẹ ẹ. Bì ó bá ti ri ọkọ fẹ tó lóòjọ ni owó fi n wolé. (o. i. 5)

She stays all day in beer parlours, she works there.

The more the men patronise her daily, the more money she makes.

Jùmòké establishes a restaurant, where she employs Àjíké to be in charge of her eatery and earn a salary while she and her husband will take the profit made thereof:

Ó wá pe Dúró, ó dábá pé bí Àjíké ẹ farabalẹ tí ó sì mọ oúnjẹ í sè dáadáa, k'ójẹ kí àwọn dá ibi-iṣẹ oúnjẹ sí sè-tà sílẹ kí àwọn jẹ kí ó máa se oúnjẹ tà nibẹ... Ó ní yìò máa wá sùn s'ílẹ, yìò máa gbowó oṣù, àwọn yìò sì máa kó èrè orí iṣẹ náà. (o. i. 11)

She then called Duro, and suggested that since Àjíké was cool-headed and also know how to cook well, he should let them establish a restaurant for her to manage... She said Àjíké would come home to sleep, and would also earn a monthly salary while they would share the profit made from the venture.

This is a way of preventing Àjíké from taking after her mother. In *Ìrèké Onihùdó*,

Fágúnwá tells of a woman that hawks freshly-cooked maize:

Nígbàtí ó wá di òwúrọ ojọ kẹta ní nkan bí agogo mėsán, mo pàdé obìnrin kan tí ó gbé àgbàdo tútù tí nwọn tí sè, tí ó sì gbóná yaya kan tí ó n tà á... mo ra àgbàdo nā mo sì tún ra awùsá pẹlú... (o. i. 72)

In the morning of the third day at about nine o'clock, I met a woman who hawks freshly-cooked maize, which is still very hot... I bought maize and I bought walnut also.

Similarly, in *Ìrínkèrindò Nínú Igbó Elégbèje*, *Ìrèké* and his fellow hunters meet a very beautiful spirit being in form of a lady. She hawks different ailments and people are purchasing these goods from her. Though the idea of selling this kind of goods is rather weird, the essence in it is that she sells and people buy from her:

Ará Igbó, èrò ọ̀nà, e wá bá mi rà á o, ọ̀jà mí pà, owó kẹ́kẹ́ ní; wárápá, pónùn méta; sọ̀pónná, pónùn méjì, ẹ̀tẹ̀ pónùn mérin; wèrè, pónùn méfà; orí fifó, sílẹ̀ méwá; sòbiyà, pónùn kan; otítù, tóró; làkùrègbé, pónùn kan; igbé ọ̀rìn, pónùn kan-àbò, ifòn, sílẹ̀; kúrúnà, tóró; ikó, pónùn kan; ibà, sílẹ̀ méje; òkè-ilẹ̀, pónùn méjì; aràn, sílẹ̀ mēdógún... (o. i. 26)

Residents of the forest, passers-by, come and patronize me, my wares are cheap, they cost just a little: epilepsy costs three pounds; small-pox, two pounds; leprosy, four pounds; madness, six pounds; headache, ten shillings; leg pains, six shillings; boil, one shilling; stomach-ache, ten shillings; guinea-worm, one pound; cold, two and half pence; rheumatism, one pound; dysentery, one pound ten shillings; skinny disease, six shillings; swollen body, two pounds; worms, fifteen shillings...

Bí ẹniti ó ñpolówó ọ̀jà ẹ̀mò yí tí ñ pa á ní a ñ gbó tí àwọn kan ñ pèé, tí nwón ñ rà á lówó ré. (o. i. 27)

As the one who hawks the strange wares goes on, we hear some people calling out to her, to purchase her wares.

However, the woman who hawks these wares is quick to add that:

...Ìgbàtí àwọn alatunṣe wònyí bá ra àisàn tí mo ntà, nwón á mú u lọ, nwón á lọ fii ṣe igi, ìgbàtí àisàn yí bá mú igi, nwón á mú dígí pẹ̀lẹ̀bẹ̀ tí Olódùmarè fún nwón, nwón á fi wo kòkòrò tí ó ndá àisàn nā sílẹ̀, lẹ́hin èyí, nwón á mú kòkòrò tọ̀ Olórun Oba lọ. Ìgbàtí Olórun bá rii, Olórun á kọ̀ wọn ní ọ̀nà àti fi bá kòkòrò bẹ̀jà, á sì fún wọn ní àṣẹ àti lọ kọ̀ ọ̀ sí igbá àiyà àwọn omọ̀ ènià. Ìgbàtí Dókítà pàtàkì bá sùn ní ọ̀ru tàbí babaláwo àtátà, àwọn alatunṣe wònyí á fò 'lọ, nwón á lọ kọ̀ ọ̀ sí aghári wọn. Sùghón, ó mà ṣe o, ìgbàtí àwọn oníṣẹ̀gùn pàtàkì wònni bá jí, tí nwón ronú tí nwón rí ìdí àisàn yí, nwón kò ní i mò pé isé Elédá àwọn ni... (o. i. 27)

When these mediators buy these ailments, they would inflict same on trees, when these ailments manifest on the trees, they would take lenses, which Olódūmarè has given them, to behold the virus responsible for this disease. After this, they take the virus back to God. When God sees it, He teaches them how to attack this virus and also grant the authority to impress it in the hearts of mankind.

When important Doctors sleep in the night, or an equally important Ifá priest, these mediators would fly to write it in their brains. But what a pity, when these important doctors wake up, when they think and discover the cause of these ailments, they would not know that it is the work of their creator...

This is a confirmation that doctors only care, and it is the Almighty that cures diseases. He is the divine doctor and the divine pharmacist. The knowledge and practice of medical profession emanates from him. Fádípè (1970:148) opines that the:

Sexual division of labour between husband and wife is carried over to the disposal of the farm produce. The wife is responsible for selling either in an elaborately processed form or practically as harvesting some of the farm that are in excess of the normal requirements of the farmer and his family. For this service, she usually receives a commission.

In *Kádàrá àti Ègbon Rẹ*, the patriarchal tradition of the husband playing a dominant role over the wife, even in the area of economy, is portrayed. 'Ìyá Kádàrá', Kádàrá's mother, is without any money, she depends solely on her husband for all her needs.

Ṣùgbón obìnrin náà kò dá owó kan ní fúnra rẹ, nítorípé Àgbégbémí oko rẹ ni ó m̀bá ta gbogbo òkan tí ó ǹ tà, bí ó bá sì ti ti ojà dé ni ó máa òkó owó tí ó bá pa b̀ò fún un láì mú òkankan s̀hìn. Nítòrináà, kò sí irànṣ̀wò kan tí ó lè ṣ̀ fún Kádàrá nípa ẹran rirà, àfi ońjẹ nìkan ni ó ò fún un ní ní oúnjẹ tí òun pàápàà ǹjẹ. (o. i. 16)

But the woman does not have any money of her own, because she helps Àgbégbémí to sell all the things she sells, when she returns from the market, she hands the money so realized to her husband without keeping any money back for her own use and needs. As a result, she could not render any assistance to Kádàrá in the area of procuring animals, except for food, which she shares with him from her own portion.

This situation aptly describes the predicament of the women who have no economic powers of their own. The situation renders iya Kádàrá helpless. She could not come to the assistance of her son during his trying period and period of dire needs. This shows that in traditional Yoruba society sometimes women are economically dependent on their husbands for basic as well as other needs.

Some Yorùbá traders also practise smuggling of imported banned goods and materials into the country to sell to those who are fond of buying imported textiles and liquor. This is shown in *Bàbá Rere*.

*Níghà tí ọ̀nà ọ̀jà fàyàn wó dí, aṣọ ilẹ̀ Àgùnnyìn tí Dúró ñ kó sí
sọ̀bù fún Jùmòkẹ̀ kò sí mọ́; ọ̀ sí b́áa se ọ̀nà ọ̀tí-títá l'ápòtí-
l'ápòtí láì dá isé aṣọ rírán rẹ̀ dúró. (o. i. 23)*

When smuggling became tough, the textile materials that Dúró stocked in Jùmòkẹ̀' s shop became a scarce commodity; he arranged for her to sell liquor drinks in cartons without stopping her sewing business.

5.4 White collar job

White collar job is also common today. Consequently, people who have received Western education and those who have undergone training in various professions are employed by the different levels of governments – local, state and federal governments in order to earn a decent and honest living. Available today also are different corporations, and other private-businesses in which the Yorùbá work in order to earn a living.

In *Bàbá Rere*, Qlábímtán discusses Dúró as an employer of labour and how he pays his employees.

*Qjọ kẹ̀ èdógún – kẹ̀ èdógún ni Dúró ñ sanwó fún àwọn ọ̀sìsẹ̀
rẹ̀. Bí wọn bá sí tí gbówó dé ní b́ànkì, aago irú èyí tí wọn
máa ñ lù láti pe àwọn ọ̀mọ́ Ilẹ̀ – iwé, ni ọ̀gá isé máa ñ lù láti
pe gbogbo ọ̀sìsẹ̀ láti wá gba owó wọn... (o. i. 1)*

Dúró pays his employees every fifteen days. Once they withdraw money from the bank, a bell like the one used in schools is rung to assemble all employees to come and receive their pay.

Àlábí takes up the teaching profession as a stepping stone before he goes to learn the medical profession, in *Kékeré Èkin*.

Bádéjọ ní kí Fọlárín máa ǵe Tísà ní Aiyéro, kí ó tún lẹ máa
te diùrù ní sọ̀sì wọ̀n... Nìgbà tí Àlùfáà gbó pé inú bàbá Àlàbí
àti iyá Àlàbí kò dùn sí, ó pe Bádéjọ, ó ǵe àlàyé irú ipò tí ọmọ
rẹ̀ yìò wà bí ó bá sísé Tísà. Ó fì yée pé isé Olúwa ní isé Tísà,
èrè rẹ̀ sí pọ̀ l'órùn... Àlàbí sì hẹ̀rẹ̀ isé Tísà ní Ìlòkò ní ihẹ̀rẹ̀ ọ̀dún
titun.
(o. i. 63)

Bádéjọ suggested that Fọlárín take up teaching in Aiyéro, so
that he could also double as the church organist... When the
clergyman heard that bàbá Àlàbí and iyá Àlàbí were not happy
about it, he called Bádéjọ and explained to him the kind of
position his son would occupy if he became a teacher. He told
him that teaching was God's profession, and its reward was
much in heaven... Thus Àlàbí began teaching in Ìlòkò at the
beginning of the new year.

In *Àyànmọ*, Àlàbí is a trained medical doctor:

Lẹ̀hìn ọ̀dún méjì tí Àlàbí dé ilú òyìnbó, ọ̀nà rẹ̀ tí là gààrà, ó
sì bó sí ibi ikósé dókítà tààrà... Sùgbón nìgbà tí èsì idámwò
rẹ̀ tí yìò fì bó sí ibi ikósé dókítà dé, tí ó dára, ó bẹ̀rẹ̀ sí kọ
isé dókítà...
(o. i. 93)

Two years after Àlàbí had gone abroad, his path became well
paved, he crossed over to the training of medical profession
straight away... But when the result of his examination which
will enable him to practise medicine was released and was
good, he started learning the medical profession...

The study has thus demonstrated that there are many Yorùbá traditional professions
and it behoves on each individual to choose from many and more of these
professions. The Yorùbá are very hard working and the fact that "there is dignity in
labour" is manifested in the various professions practised by them.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION

6.0 Introduction

This Chapter concludes the research. It presents the summary, findings, and implications of the study. Some recommendations are also offered.

6.1 Summary

The main concern of this work is the exploration of the culture orthodoxy of the Yorùbá. Culture is perceived as an amalgamation of knowledge, technology, language, religion, fashion, culinary, institutions, norms and values, education and general ways of doing things which need to be modified and transmitted through education. The samples for the study were selected from various Yorùbá novels.

The study highlighted various institutions in the Yorùbá society. They include family marriage, political, religious and economic institutions. These institutions are discussed as they are practised in the Yorùbá society. The totality of all the institutions is what make up the people's tradition and culture. These institutions are the unwritten laws that guide the ways of life of the people, their actions and activities which are for the benefit of the members of the society. Culture orthodoxy is likened to teachers that instruct members of the society and the government.

Since sociology is essential as the study of people in a society and their interaction; this necessitated the adoption of sociology of literature as the theoretical framework for the study. Globalization, postcolonialism and multiculturalism are reviewed in the study. In the study, orthodoxy is described as a process involving gradual deposits of ways of doing things, which forms the culture of a people; and it distinguishes the lifestyle and ways of life of the Yorùbá as reflected in the selected novels.

The study demonstrates that the culture orthodoxy of the Yorùbá is truly reflected in Yorùbá novels to a large extent. It finds that the Yorùbá culture orthodoxy depicted in the Yorùbá novels through various institutions of the Yorùbá and exhibition of such institutions as they are x-rayed in the novels are also discussed.

The institutions of family, marriage, politics, economy and religion as observed in the novels, serve the purpose of the Yorùbá as it is discovered that the ethical standards of the Yorùbá are high. The grandeur, sophistication and high intelligence the Yorùbá possess in the institutions that are in place are portrayed in the texts.

The study finds that the culture orthodoxy depicted in the Yorùbá novels are truly a reflection of Yorùbá world view vis-a-vis the contents of the selected novels. It finds that in religion, the selected novels for the study indicate that there are three popular religions practised in the Yorùbá society. The religions are: the African Traditional Religion (A.T.R.); Christianity; and Islam. Religious belief among the Yorùbá centres on God as the Supreme Being; therefore, there is no basis for religious rivalry among the practitioners of these religions, as they co-exist among the people in the society with each person having the freedom to practise a religion of his choice.

The findings of the study also reveal that the culture orthodoxy depicted in the Yorùbá novels are truly a reflection of Yorùbá worldview as the institution of family is depicted as being communal in pre-colonial era and that has since given way to individualism in the contemporary times. In the institution of marriage, the orthodox Yoruba society practised polygamy unlike monogamy that is common in contemporary society.

The investigation discovers that in politics, the traditional rulers, as custodians of culture and tradition of the people, are being exploited by politicians in their administration. The politicians do not assign any particular role to traditional rulers in the constitution. Their roles and relevance in the scheme of things are barely recognized. This is a replica of the indirect rulership style employed by the British colonialists. The issue of resilience in traditional rulership is paramount. The study finds that the institution of traditional rulership has survived despite all odds. The Yorùbá have also all along stood against mis-governance and oppressive tendencies of traditional leaders. They have always resisted this in their own way through traditional checks and balances.

The findings of the study also reveal that the culture orthodoxy depicted in the Yorùbá novels are truly a reflection of Yorùbá worldview as agriculture is depicted in the selected novels as the main source of Yorùbá economy. Traditionally,

the Yorùbá society is an agrarian one. The Agricultural practices of the Yorùbá were sufficient to maintain the traditional Yorùbá society in the past.

Finally, the study demonstrates that there are significant differences in the ways the Yorùbá culture orthodoxy were practised in the past compared to how they are practised today. These differences manifest in the various institutions studied in the novels. The differences are the outcome of modernism, globalization, post-colonialism and multiculturalism. The investigation has revealed that the Yorùbá novelists do justice to the preservation of Yorùbá culture orthodoxy as the novelists are true custodians of culture orthodoxy of the people and their society as reflected in the novels. The extent of cultural products and images contained in the novels certainly establish the Yorùbá novels as a veritable tool for cultural preservation.

6.2 Implications of the findings

This study centres on the culture orthodoxy in Yorùbá novels, with particular emphasis on Yorùbá institutions. Our findings have far-reaching implications on the Yorùbá nation. The problem being faced by the Yorùbá seems to be that of "individualism". There is need for the nation to conquer this menace in order to develop and progress. A Yorùbá maxim says "*Àgbájọ ọwó nì a fì ñ sọ àyà*" (united we stand, divided we fall). If the Yorùbá come together and speak with one voice, they will be better able to decide to operate within their culture, and promote same.

The challenge of unity is most desirable in the area of agriculture, in order to avert the impending doom of famine and hunger, the beginning of which is already staring the nation in the face. All the traditional agricultural practices already condemned by the whites should be re-visited. For instance, the white made the Yorùbá believe that there is nothing like rain-making, they refer to it as superstition. This is because it is not meaningful to them. therefore, they cannot prove it in their own scientific way. In the Western culture, they have what is referred to as "climatic weather modification" called cloud seedings, which is an equivalent of the Yorùbá's rain-making. This practice is less effective and much more expensive than the practice of the Yorùbá that is condemned by them.

The Yorùbá traditional knowledge of herbs and medicine which is condemned by the West needs to be re-visited, refined and packaged with specific prescriptions and doses. The efficacy of the Yorùbá traditional herbs and medicine is not in doubt, therefore, rather than condemn the practice totally, we only need to re-package and modernize it as it is being done by some "Herbal medicine practitioners" today.

Except the Yorùbá go back to the drawing board to demonstrate the vitality of their culture in all aspects of life, they may be heading for total extinction. This is because the Yorùbá elders who are in possession of valuable "seen" and "unseen" traditional technology and African traditional science are fast diminishing. Most of these elders have already passed on, taking along with them, these highly-valued traditional resources. The elders, who are supposed to pass these materials to the youth, have been alienated from the youth in the name of civilization.

There is nothing the West possesses which the Yorùbá do not possess. The West knows this, hence, their condemnation of all that is traditional African, in favour of foreign materials. Yorùbá culture is not inferior to any other culture. Yet, the Yorùbá culture is being swallowed by foreign cultures of the Western, developed countries. Therefore, there is a dire need to quickly arrest the situation.

6.2.1. Recommendations

The beginning of the problems being faced by the Yorùbá is the invasion of their culture by the Europeans, through exploration and evangelism. Some steps need to be taken to bring about the lost glory of the race. There should be a law that the Yorùbá language and culture should be made a compulsory subject in pre-primary, primary and secondary schools, both private and public in all Yorùbá speaking states. This is capable of preserving the language and culture, so that the Yorùbá thoughts and reasoning will be truly Yorùbá. A situation whereby a man thinks in one language and speaks in another can only retard the development of the society. The developed countries are those who preserve their languages and make their languages the language of education and government. Examples are Italy, Japan, Britain, France, Spain, Denmark, China, Switzerland, Germany, et cetera.

Developing countries are those that have resorted to make their indigenous languages their official languages. Examples of these are India, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, and so on. These countries preserve and guard their cultures jealously; they package and sell these cultures to other countries. The question is, should the Yorùbá continue to be perpetual importers of such cultures? The answer to this question is no! Such a situation is unacceptable as it is to the detriment of the development of the Yorùbá culture. There is need for the Yorùbá as a nation to wake up from their deep slumber to patronize, package and export their very rich cultural heritage to the outside world.

The future of a country depends on the children and the youth of such a country. Therefore, the rescue mission should begin with the youths on whose hands rest the future and preservation of the language and culture. There is therefore, the need to cultivate the traditional values of the Yorùbá into the school-age children and the youths.

The Yorùbá need to promote the richness of their family institution. The Yorùbá culture has moral values with its communalism, than the individualism promoted by Western family unit. The Yorùbá need to inculcate values and morals of their cultural heritage into the younger generation. There is need to further promote communal behaviour of collective discipline of all the children and chastity of all erring adult members of the society, including the query on the source of sudden wealth of family members. Courteous behaviour, in terms of showing respect to the elders in the society should also be inculcated into the younger ones. There is need to promote shared love, and affection that will further advance the general welfare and well being of all members of the society. Parents should not impose career choice on their children rather they should allow them to practise careers of their choice. Also, parents need not choose who a marriage partner of their children should be. They should leave the choice of making such a life-time decision to the parties involved. The novels generally criticize divorce and encourage spouses to work towards unity.

The Yorùbá only need to adopt Western Technology and integrate it into the existing Yorùbá cultural practices in order to modernize the Yorùbá indigenous technology, rather than westernizing the Yorùbá culture, which eventually result into the bastardization of Yorùbá culture and tradition. The Yorùbá tend to equate getting

good education to getting integrated into one foreign culture or the other. This is erroneous. They only need to modify the existing traditional technology rather than jettisoning them in favour of that of the West. The West came to study the Yorùbá culture they modified and repackaged same, only to sell back to the people at exorbitant rates, after modifying, recycling and repackaging them.

This brings about the need for reparation in order to retrieve and re-possess some of the artifacts and artistic materials of the Yorùbá progenitors that have been taken away by the Europeans. The whites acknowledge the fact that Africans and, by implication, the Yorùbá possess highly valuable material culture in their civilization. There is need for the Yorùbá to re-trace their steps and re-visit the traditional ways of life of their forefathers. They may need to adapt only those things that are positive from the Westerners in order to improve the existing structure, rather than abandoning their ways of life in preference of that of the West.

There is the need for everyone to add value to the society. The study also reveals that arms and ammunition that are used to commit heinous crimes in the society are imported from the Western countries. Corruption which has eroded and distorted the traditional Yorùbá ethical standard has been institutionalized and perfected by the members of the Yorùbá society.

The Europeans' interests in Africa and Yorùbá, are for commercial purposes. They sell their technology and culture to the people in order to further develop and maintain their status of world leading powers. Yet, Africans, and the Yorùbá are awaiting transfer of technology from the West. No civilization is going to develop another civilization. Developing own civilization will lead to liberation of the new civilization, which may reduce the domination and imposition of the already civilized nations on the developing nations.

Furthermore, there is the need to develop the Yorùbá indigenous crops in order to produce sufficient food for the Yorùbá nation. Oil is a product of conflict, wherever it is found in the world. Hence, there is the need for reduction of dependence on oil. Rather, the Yorùbá should direct their focus on agriculture. If this is done, a lot of improvement will be made in the society. It is important for the Yorùbá to have food security. As the reinvigoration of the traditional agriculture is done, there would be creation of more employment opportunities for the people, this

will lead to reduction in poverty and the resultant behaviours of kidnapping, armed robbery, murder, pornography et cetera. This will ultimately demystify the seemingly harsh security, social and economic problems, which seem to be insurmountable.

The Yorùbá need to realize the need to reduce their dependence on the West. They also need to adopt their traditional cultural approach of doing things. The Obas, as custodians of culture and tradition and as traditional rulers, have the task of promoting and preserving the tradition of their domains. They are referred to as traditional rulers and not as Christian or Muslim rulers. As a result, the Obas should be truly traditional in all their deeds, including worship of the gods and ancestors.

Unlike in the past, where the monarch was accorded the power of life and death, it is discovered that the present form of democratic governance has eroded the powers of the traditional rulers in Yorùbá and other societies. This debasing position whereby the traditional ruler is accorded the impassive role of "*Royal Father*" needs to be re-visited. Traditional rulers, like in the past, should be given specific traditional roles to perform in their various domains. As custodians of culture and tradition of their people, their roles ought to be recognised and promoted, as they have a lot to contribute to the society in the areas of preservation and promotion of traditional values and ethics.

Contemporary society has a lot to learn in terms of politics and governance as demonstrated in the Yorùbá novels. As democracy was used to secure political freedom and National independence for Nigerians, contemporary leaders need to be truly democratic in their style of governance. They need to give room for dialogue, listen to the yearnings and cries of their people: stop the act of imposing leaders on the people and allow leaders to emerge from the concept of the people, by allowing voters' vote to count.

Money politics should be reduced as too much money is spent on electioneering processes; this encourages corruption and graft in the polity. These should become things of the past, in order that the Nation and her Nationales are not further pauperized. Also, the situation whereby "the winner takes all" after electoral victory need to be re-visited. Elective posts should be shared among aspirants, to reduce the attitude of "*do-or-die affair*" in winning elective positions. The wasteful spending and looting of the nation's treasuries by those who are entrusted with the

care of such should be halted immediately, if the nation must develop and become a relevant force to reckon with in the committee of Nations.

6.3 **Limitations of the study and suggestions for future study**

The main purpose of this study is to substantiate the conception that the Yorùbá novels genuinely reflect the culture orthodoxy of the Yorùbá. This is in terms of the ways of life of the people as contained in their various institutions. The research focused on the Yorùbá culture orthodoxy as depicted in the Yorùbá novels.

The use of language, aesthetics of the language, especially proverbs are beyond the scope of this study. It is therefore suggested that further research work could also examine the aesthetics, language use, and the use of proverbs in Yorùbá novels. This is to appreciate further the Yorùbá proverbs as a common law and a great patrimony acquired from the Yorùbá progenitors.

Furthermore, the trend of westernizing the Yorùbá children, youth and adults as obtainable today is another probable topic for subsequent research. This will further show the direction of the nation.

SELECTED NOVELS

- Adeoye, C. L. (1971). *Èdà Omọ Oòd'uà* (Atunse Keji). Ibadan: Oxford University Press.
- Akínládé, K. (1985): *Şàngbá Fọ*. Ibadan: Paperback Publishers Ltd.
- Akinolá, A. (1984): *Filá L'obinrin*. Ibadan: Evans Brothers (Nigeria Publishers) Ltd.,
- Awóyelé, O. (1988): *Àjẹkú L'ayé*. Ibadan: Oníbonòjé Press and Book Industries (Nig.) Ltd.
- Délànò. I. (1955): *Aiyé D'aiyé Òyinbó*. Lagos: Thomas Nelson and SMS Ltd.
- ____ (1963): *L'ójó ojó un*. London: Thomas Nelson.
- Fágúnwà, D. O. (1982): *Igbó Olódùmarè*. Lagos: Thomas Nelson Nigeria Ltd.
- ____ (2005): *Ògbójú Ode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalé*. Ibadan: Nelson Publishers Ltd
- ____ (2005): *Ìrìnkèrindò Nínú Igbó Elégbèje*. Ibadan: Nelson Publishers Ltd.
- ____ (2005): *Àdìitù Olódùmarè*. Ibadan: Nelson Publishers Ltd.
- ____ (2005): *Ìrèké Onibùdó*. Ibadan: Nelson Publishers Ltd.
- Fálétí, A. (1970): *Omọ Olókùn Eşin*. Ibadan: Heinemann Educational Books (Nigeria) Plc.
- ____ (1965): *Ogun Áwítélé*. Ibadan: Oxford University Press.
- Ìşòlá, A. (1990): *Ogún Omódé*. Ibadan: University Press, Plc.
- ____ (1992): *Ó le kú*. Ibadan: University Press, Plc.
- Jéboḁà, F. (1964): *Olówólayémò*. Ibadan: Longman Nigeria Limited.
- Johnston, R. O. (1976): *Ìyábò I*. Ibadan: University Press.
- ____ (1985): *Ìyábò II*. Ibadan: University Press.
- Ládélé, T. A. (1971): *Jé Ng Lô 'gba Tèmi*. Lagos: Macmillan Nigeria.
- ____ T. A. (1978): *Ìgbì Ayé Nyí*. Ibadan: Longman Nigeria.
- Ògúndélé, J. O. (1956): *Ibú-Olókun*. Ibadan: Bounty Press Limited.
- Ògúndélé, J. O. (1965) *Ejìgbèdè Lónà Ísálú Òrun*. London: Longman.
- Ògúníran, T. A. (1972): *Eégún Alaré*. Ibadan, Macmillan Nigeria Plc.
- Òjó, B. (1989): *Ménumó*. Ibadan: University Press Limited.
- Òkédijí, O. (1981): *Atótó Arére*. Ibadan: University Press Plc.
- Owólabí, O. (1981): *Ìjànbá Şelú*. Ibadan: Evans Brothers (Nigeria Publishers) Ltd.

- _____ (1988): *Ọtẹ̀ N'ìbò*. Ìbàdàn: Vantage Publishers.
- Oyèdélé, A. (1970): *Kini Mo Ẹ?* Ìbàdàn: Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Ltd.
- Oyèdélé, A. (1973) *Ìwo ni*. Lagos: Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Ltd.
- Ọdúnjọ, J. F. (1964): *Kúyẹ*. Lagos: Africa University Press.
- _____ (1964): *Ọmọ Ọkú Ọrun*. Lagos: Africa University Press.
- Ọdúnjọ, J. F. and A. B. Ọládípúpọ (1967): *Kádàrá Àti Ègbon Rẹ*. Ìbàdàn: Onibonòjé Press and Book Industries (Nig.) Ltd.
- Ọlábímtán, A. (1967): *Kékeré Ekùn*. Lagos: Macmillan Nigeria Publishers. Ltd.
- _____ (1973): *Àyànmó*. Ìbàdàn: Macmillan Nigeria Publishers.
- _____ (1977): *Bàbá Rere*. Lagos: Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Ltd.
- _____ (1993): *Orílawẹ̀ Àdìgún*, Lagos: Macmillan Nigeria Publishers.
- Yémitán, Ládípọ (1980): *Orúkọ ló Yàtọ*. Ìbàdàn: University Press Limited.
- _____ (1988). *Gbọ̀baniyì*. Ìbàdàn: University Press Limited.

References

- Abimbólá, W. 2006. *Àwọn ojù-odù méréèrindínlógún*. Ìbàdàn: University Press PLC.
- _____ 2006. *Ìjìnlè ohùn enu ifà Apa keji*. Ìbàdàn: University Press PLC.
- Abrams, M. H. 1981. *A glossary of literary terms*. New York: Rine Hart and Holt.
- Acuff, G. et al. 1973. *From man to society*. Illinois: The Dryden Press.
- Achufusi 1986. "The main genres of African Traditional Literature" *Nigeria Magazine*, Vol. 54 No. 54 (Oct - Dec)
- Adébòwálé, O. 1994. *Style in Yorùbá Crime Fiction*. An unpublished PhD Thesis University of Ìbàdàn. Ìbàdàn.
- Adékólá, A. F. 2004. Modern Influences on Traditional Economy. In Nike S. Lawal, et al eds in *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Africa World Press Entrea, INC. Trenton N. J.
- Adélékè, D. A. 1995. 'Audience reception of Yorùbá films: Ìbàdàn as a case study.' An unpublished PhD. Thesis in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Adélékè, D. A. 2004. *Lessons from Yorùbá mythology*. Sage publications London: Thousand Oaks and New Delhi.
- Adémólá, O. S. 1998. *Tropical Zoology*. Ìbàdàn: University Press Ltd. Ìbàdàn.
- Adéníjì, L. A. A. 2008. *Religious conflict in Nigeria: a ravaging fire of our time*. 2nd Distinguished Lecture delivered at the Federal College of Education, Òsìlèlè, Abèòkúta.
- Adéoyè, C. L. 1980, 2005. *Àsà àti Ìṣe Yorùbá*. Ìbàdàn: University Press Ltd. Ìbàdàn.
- Adéyanjú, D. 2004. History and language functions: a case of the English Language in Nigeria. Oyéléyè L. Ed. *Language and Discourse in Society*. Ìbàdàn, Hope Publication Ltd.
- Adéyemí, L. 2005. "The ideology of multiculturalism in the works of selected American minority group's novelists: lessons for Nigerian literatures" *Ihafa: A journal of African studies*, Vol 5, No. 2.
- Afigbo, A. E. 2000. Myth, history and nation orientation. In Ayò Bámgbòsé Ed. *Humanity in context*. Occasional Publication of the Nigerian Academy of Letters.

- Afolábí, A. S. 1997. Sociology of Education. In Àjàyí, Káyòdé Ed. *Òsíṣẹ̀ Study Series*. Abèòkúta Satellite Publishers.
- Afoláyan, M.O and Afoláyan, P.O 2004. Obas in contemporary politics. In Nike S. Lawal, et al (eds) in *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press Entrea, INC.
- Agishi, E. C. 2003. *A dictionary of agriculture*. Makurdi. Agitab Publishers Ltd.
- Ajéléti, C. O. 2002. Modernity in Yorùbá novels: M. A. project, to Department of Linguistics and African Languages: Faculty of Arts University of Ìbàdàn.
- Akínjògbín, I. A. 2002. Milestones and social systems in Yorùbá history and culture: A key to understanding Yorùbá history. Ìbàdàn Olú-Akin Publishers.
- Akínyemí, A. 1996. "Ìlò oríkì nínú ipolówó ojà lówùjò Yorùbá" *Olóta Journal of African Studies*. Vol. 1 No. 2 Pgs 99 – 108.
- Alana, O. 2004. Traditional Religion. In Nike S. Lawal, et al (eds.) in *Understanding Yorùbá Life and Culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press Entrea, INC.
- Amos, B. 1976. Analytical categories and ethnic genres. *Folklore genres* – In Amos, B. D. (Ed.) Austin University of Texas Press. 215 – 241.
- Angulu 1975. *The social anthropology in Africa: an introduction*. Heinemann: London.
- Ashcraft, B. et al Eds. 2004. *The Post-colonial studies reader*. New York: Routledge.
- Aróhunmúlàṣẹ̀, L. O. 1997. *Class struggle in Yorùbá historical and protest plays*. PhD Thesis, University of Ìbàdàn.
- Awólàlu, J. O. 1981. *Yorùbá beliefs and sacrificial rites*. Ìbàdàn: Longman.
- Awónúsi, S. 2004. Globalization and hegemonic English in Nigeria. Identity conflicts and linguistic pluralism. In Òní Dúrò, et al Eds. *Nigeria politics and social conflicts*. Lagos: Centre for Black and African Arts and Civilization (CBAAC) p 85 – 102.
- Àyántáyò, J. K. 2003. *Socio-religious dimensions to chieftaincy affairs in Yorùbáland, Nigeria*. Paper presented at International Conference on Chieftaincy in Africa: Culture, Governance and Development. University of Ghana, Legon, Ghana. January 6th – 10th 2003.

- Babátúndé, E. 2004. "Traditional marriage and family." In Nike S. Lawal et al Eds. *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press, INC.
- Bámgbóṣé, A. 2007. *The novels of D. O. Fágúnwà*. Ìbàdàn: Nelson Publishers Ltd.
- . 2001. Language culture and the African renaissance. In Olúkòjù, E. O. Ed. *A golden heritage: essays in celebration of St. Andrew's College, Òyó*. Ìbàdàn: Heinemann Educational Books Nigeria PLC.
- Bámidélé, L. O. 2000. *Literature and sociology*. Ìbàdàn: Stirling – Horden Publishers (Nig) Ltd.
- Barber 1978. *Why do we need a sociology of literature?* A paper presented at the Sociology of Literature Seminar, University of Ifè, Ilé-Ifè.
- . 1979. *Marxist sociology of literature*. Paper presented at the Sociology of Literature Seminar, University of Ifè, Ilé-Ifè.
- . 1984. *Sociology of Yorùbá written literature: Fágúnwà and Òkédìjì*. Seminar paper, University of Ifè, Ilé-Ifè.
- Barthes, R. 1976. *Mythologies*. Paris: Jonathan Cape Ltd. Editions.
- Bascom, W. R. and Paul Gabauer 1943. The relationship of Yorùbá folklore to diving. *Journal of American Folklore*, Vol. 56.
- Bidney, D. 1965. Myth: symbolism and truth. In Thomas A Sebeok Ed. "Myth: A symposium." Bloomington and London: Indiana University Press.
- Brown, H. D. 1992. "Learning a second culture" in Joyce Merrill Valdes (ed) in *Culture Bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching*. Cambridge. Cambridge University Press.
- Brumbaugh, R. S. 2008. "Aristotle Microsoft Student 2008 [DVD]. Redmond W. A: Microsoft Corporation.
- Chinweizu, et. al. (1983) *Toward the Decolonization of African Literature*. Enugu: Fourth Dimension.
- Coffin, T. P. 2007. Folktale in *Microsoft Student Encarta*. Microsoft Student 2008 DVD Redmond, WA Microsoft Corporation.
- Dáramólá and Jéjé 1967. *Àwọn àṣà àti òrìṣà ilẹ̀ Yorùbá*. Ibadan. Onibonòjé Press Ltd.

- Dasylva, O. A. 1999. *Classificatory Paradigms in African oral narrative*. Ibadan: Atlantis Books.
- Dòpámú. A. and Alana E. 2004. Ethical systems. In Nike S. Lawal, et al Eds in *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press Entrea, INC.
- Dorson, R. M. 1972. Concepts of folklore and folk life studies in Dorson R.M Ed. *Folklore and folk life: An Introduction*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press Pgs 1- 8.
- Douglas, H. B. Ed. 1992. Learning a second culture, in *Culture bound: Bridging the cultural gap in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ebewo, P. 1991. Culture and literature in Thompson, Dapo Adelugba et al (eds) *Culture and Civilization*. Ibadan: Africa Link Books Ibadan.
- Egbokhare, F. O. 2007. "Globalization and the Linguistic implication". An article written in the *Sunday Tribune* of 25th November.
- Emenyonu, E. 1978. *The rise of the Ighó novel*. Ibadan: Oxford University Press.
- Encyclopedia of Religion* 1982. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Fádípè, N. A. 1970. *The sociology of the Yorùbá*. Ibadan: Ibadan University Press.
- Fájényò, S. A. 2003. *The aesthetics of verbal lore in Yorùbá jingles and advertisement discourse in the electronic media*. Ph.D Thesis University of Ibadan. XIV- 323.
- _____ 2007. *A critical examination of the impact of globalization on Yorùbá language*. A paper presented at the National Conference of the Yorùbá studies Association of Nigeria (YSAN) held at Oyo State, College of Education, Oyo, between 2nd and 6th October, 2007.
- Fámilúsi, O. 1998. *Women in the domestic setting in Yorùbá play*. M. A. Project. Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan. X-84.
- Finnegan, R. 1979. *Oral poetry: its nature, significance and social context*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Folájìn, T. 2007. *Re-engineering the nation's educational system towards global challenges: the murky waters*". 1st In-house Distinguished Lecture" held on 13th December 2007, by the Federal College of Education, Abéokúta.

- Francois, J. F. and Paule, M. 1997. Introduction: the History of an Idea. *Research in African Literatures*. p 1 – 7.
- Franz, B. 1992. Language and thought. In Joyce M. Valdes Ed. *Culture bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Galadima, S. 1991. Ethnic and religious conflicts: a threat to the survival of Nigeria democracy. in S. Bello and Y. Nasidi Eds. *Economy and national development*. Lagos: National Council for Arts and Culture.
- Gregor, L. and Nickolas, B. 1962. *The moral and the story*. London: Faber and Faber.
- Hambling, C. and Mathews, P. 1974. *Human society*. Hampshire: Macmillian Education Ltd.
- Hastings, J. 1917. *Encyclopedia of Religion and Ethics*. Vol. IX, New York: Charles Scribner's Sons.
- Henslin, James M. Ed. 1980. *Marriage and family in a changing society*. New York: Free Press.
- Herskovits, M. J. 1962. *The human face in changing Africa*. New York: Alfred A. Knoff.
- _____ 1965. *The human factor in changing Africa*. New York: Routledge and Kegan Paul Ltd. Published by Alfred A. Knoff.
- Hornby, A. S. 1984. *Oxford advanced learner's dictionary of current English*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Ìdòwú, B. 1996. *Olodumare: God in Yorùbá belief*. Ìbàdàn: Longman Nigeria Ltd.
- Ilésanmí, T.M. 2001. Educulture for the third millennium. In *Yorùbá*. Vol. 12 No.1.
- Irele, A. 1990. The African Imagination. *Research in African Literatures (RAL)*. Vol. 21. No 3 (summer) Pgs 49 – 67.
- Ìsòlá, A. 1978. *The writer's art in the modern Yorùbá novel*. Ph.D Thesis, University of Ìbàdàn, Ìbàdàn.
- _____ 1998. *The modern Yorùbá novel: an analysis of the writers' art*. Ìbàdàn: Heinemann Educational Books Nigeria Plc.
- John, B. 1964. *Other cultures: aims, methods and achievement in Social Anthropology*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.

- Johnson, S. 1921. *The history of the Yorùbás from the earliest times to the beginning of the British protectorate*. London: Routledge.
- Joyce, M. V. (Ed.). 1992. Culture in literature, in *Culture bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Jusdanis, G. 1996. Can multiculturalism disunite America? in *Thesis Eleven* 44, p 100 – 110.
- Kaplan, R. B. 1992. Culture and the written language” in Joyce M. Valdes Ed. *Culture bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kroehler, H. and Zarden, V. 1996. *Sociology: the core*. New York: McGraw – Hill \ College, U.S.A.
- Kuper and Kuper 1996. *The Social Science Encyclopedia*. 2nd Edition, Routledge. London, and New York.
- Laurenson D. and Swingewood A. 1971. *The sociology of literature*. Paladin, London Leach Mace.
- Lawal, N. S. et al Eds. 2004. *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press. INC.
- Leech and Coffin 1972. *The critics and the ballad*. Illinois: Southern Illinois Carbondale.
- Lucas, J. O. 1948. *The religion of the Yorùbá*. Lagos: CMS Bookshop.
- Margaret, L. 1953. Nunivak Eskimo personality as revealed in the mythology. *Anthropological Papers of the University of Alaska*. Vol II No I. 165 – 168.
- Mazrui, A. 2001. Unpublished public lecture given at the center for African studies, Livingstone campus, Rutgers University, New Jersey.
- McLaren, P. 1994. White terror and oppositional agency: towards a critical multiculturalism. In D. T. Goldberg Ed. *multiculturalism: a critical reader*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers.
- Moloye, 2004. “Tradition high fashion in transition” in Nike S. Lawal et al Eds in *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press Entrea, INC.
- Moore, Ed. 1965. *African literature and the universities*. Ìbàdàn: Ìbàdàn University Press.

- Morrish, I. 1972. *The sociology of education: an Introduction*. London: George Allen and Unwin.
- Na'Allah and Ògúnjímí B. 1991. *Introduction to African oral literature*. Ilorin: Unilorin Press.
- New Gem Dictionary* 1975. London and Glasgow: Collins.
- Newman, James L. et al. *Africa Microsoft® Student 2008 [DVD]* Redmond, W.A: Microsoft Corporation.
- Nkrumah, K. 1965. *Neo-colonialism: the last stage of imperialism*. London: Heinemann.
- Obiechina, E. 1975. *Culture tradition and society in the West African novel*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Offiong, D. A. 1980. *Imperialism and Dependency: obstacles to African development*. Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishers.
- Ògúnfólábí 2004. *From oral prose to written fiction: the contemporary African novel in Isala: Ifè Studies in African Literature and the Arts*. Vol II. Pg 94 – 102.
- Ògúnpòlú, O. 1986. *Classification of Yorùbá prose narrative*. A seminar paper presented at the Faculty of Arts Seminar on Yorùbá Folklore. Ógùn State University, Nigeria. Pgs 213 – 221.
- Ògúnṣínà, J.A. 1987. *The sociology of the Yorùbá novel: A study of Isaac Thomas, D.O. Fágúnwà and Òládèjò Òkédìjì*. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis. University of Ìbàdàn.
- _____ 1992. *The development of the Yorùbá novel*, Ìbàdàn: Gospel Faith Mission.
- Ògúntómíṣín, G. O. 1993. *The Yorùbá*. In Bassey W. Andah, et al Eds. *Some Nigerian people*. Ibadan. Rex Charles Publication.
- Òjò, E. D. 2004. "Women and the family" in Nike S. Lawal et al Eds in *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press Entrea, INC.
- Okpewho, I. 1992. *African oral literature: background, character and continuity*. Bloomington and London: Indiana University Press.
- Olúkòjù, E. O. 1978. *The place of chants in Yorùbá traditional oral literature*. PhD

- Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- _____ (1999). LIY 751 (Prose lecture notes) taught by him in the Linguistics and African Languages Department, Faculty of Arts, University of Ibadan (1999).
- Osborne in Microsoft Encarta® Student 2008 (DVD) Redmond, W. A.; Microsoft Corporation.
- Owólabí, K 2007. *Ó tó géé, omọ Odúduwà: ogun isàmúlò èdè Yorùbá ní ibikíbi, ní ipòkípò àti ní àyèkayè dí jǐjǎ wáyí*. Ibadan: Universal Akada Books (Nig) Ltd.
- _____ 2008. *Àwọn olùkópa àti ojúṣe wọn nínú idàghàsókè àti igbèga èdè Yorùbá*. Ibadan: Universal Akada Books (Nig) Ltd.
- Oyèdielè, A. 1984. *Ki ni mo se?* Lagos: Macmillian Publishers.
- Oyèdípe, F.P.A. 2004. Changes in the traditional family system. In Nike S. Lawal et al Eds. *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press INC.
- Oyètádé, A. 2004. *The enemy in the belief system*. In Nike S. Lawal et al Eds. in *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press INC.
- _____ 2004: Body beautification in Nike S. Lawal et al Eds. *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press. INC.
- Ọlábímtán 1982. *Validity in the interpretation of Ifá literary corpus*. A conference paper presented at 2nd Annual Congress of the Nigerian Folklore Society, Ilorin, August.
- Ọlájúbú Olúdàre 1978. *Ìwé àṣà ibilẹ Yorùbá*. Ibadan: Longman Nig. Ltd.
- Ọlálówò, M. O. 1998. *Gender issues in Yorùbá witten plays*. Unpublished M.A project. University of Ibadan.
- Ọlátúnjì, O. O. 1984. *Features of Yorùbá oral poetry*. Ibadan: Ibadan University Press Ltd.
- _____ 1993. *Beyond the spoken word. Inaugural Lecture*. University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

- Pacten, 2008. Microsoft Encarta® 2008 © 1993 – 2007 Microsoft Corporation.
- Rájí and Danmole, H. O. 2004. Traditional government in Nike S. Lawal, et al Eds. In *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press Entrea, INC.
- Robert. Lato Ed. 1992. How to compare two Cultures in *Culture bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Roget's II 1995. *The new thesaurus*: Third Edition. New York: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Scholte, J.A. 1993-2003. *Globalization*. In Microsoft Encarta® 2006 [CD]. Redmond, W. A. Microsoft Corporation, 2005.
- Sills, D. L. (Ed.) 1972. *International Encyclopedia of the Social Sciences*. Vol.1 New York and London: The Macmillan Company and Press and Coillier Macmillan Publishers.
- Smith, W. C. 1964. *The meaning and end of religion*. New York: Mention Books.
- Sodiq, Y. 2004. The practice of Islam in Nike S. Lawal et al Eds in *Understanding Yorùbá life and culture*. Trenton N. J: Africa World Press Entrea, INC.
- Strauss, L. 1968. *Structural anthropology* translated by C. Jackson and B.G. Schoept: Penguin Books Harmond Sworth.
- Şekoní, R. 1979. *The structure and significance of Yorùbá trickster narrative, Confluence 1*.
- _____ 1982. *The trickster and anti-society narrative tradition among the Yorùbá*. A conference paper. 2nd Annual Congress of Nigerian Folklore Society. Aug. 23 – 27 Ilorin, Nigeria.
- _____ 1983. *Towards a new taxonomy of Yorùbá oral prose fiction*. A Seminar paper presented at Literature in English Dept., University of Ifè (now Obáfémí Awólówò University, Ifè), Nigeria (April).
- Shehu, F.S. 2000. *Female on female: a critical examination of four female Yorùbá writers*. An unpublished M. A. project submitted to the Department of Linguistics and African Languages University of Ibádán. XI-113.
- _____ 1983. *Towards the decolonization of African literature*: Enugu: Fourth Dimension.

- Sódipè, N. O. 1991. *Ègè chants in Ègbá land*. An unpublished M. A. project submitted to the Department of Linguistics and African Languages University of Ìbàdàn.
- Táíwò, O. 2004. *Globalization, society and culture: whither Nigerian youths*. In Òní Dúró, et al Eds. *Nigeria politics and social conflicts*. Lagos: Centre for Black and African Arts and Civilization (CBAAC) p 241 – 256.
- The Chambers Universal Learners Dictionary*. 1993. Edinburgh: Chambers Harrap Publishers.
- The Holy Bible*. 1999. Authorised King James Version. Printed in Japan.
- The Holy Qur'an*. 1998. Beirut-Lebanon: Published by Al-Biruni.
- The International Encyclopedia of the Social Sciences* 1968. Crowell Collier and Macmillian, Inc. United State of America.
- The World Book Encyclopedia* 1992. World Book International USA, Vol. 18.
- The World Book Encyclopedia* 1996. World Book International. A Scott Fetzer Company. London, Sydney, Tunbridge Wells, Chicago, Vol. 4.
- Thompson, S. 1979. *Myth and folktales*. In Thomas A. Ed. *Myth: a symposium*. Bloomington and London: Indiana University Press.
- Thomas A. S. (Ed.) *Myth: a symposium*. Bloomington and London: Indiana University Press.
- Thompson, et al Ed. 1991. *Culture and civilization*. Ìbàdàn: Africa Link Books.
- Thomson, D. 1974. *Introduction to Gaelic Poetry*. London: Gollanz.
- Tradition "Lectic Law Library" at <http://www.Lect Law> (Browsed on 18-03-02).
- Ukpokolo, I. E. 2004. Globalization and the search for cultural philosophy for contemporary Africa in Òní Dúró, et al Eds. *Nigeria politics and Social Conflicts*. Lagos: Centre for Black and African Arts and Civilization (CBAAC) p 275 – 285.
- Wallace, M. 1995. The search for the Good Enough mammy: multiculturalism, popular culture and psychoanalysis in David, Theo, Goldberg Eds. *Multiculturalism: A critical reader*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers Inc.
- Weber, M. 1964. *The theory of social and economic organization*. New York.

Wheelwright, P 1979. The semantic approach to myth in Thomas A. Ed. *Myth: a symposium*. Bloomington and London: Indiana University Press.

William, F. 1958. *Culture and society*. New York: Penguin.

William, R. Acton and Judith Walker de Felix 1992. Acculturation and mind. In Joyce Merrill Valdes Ed. *Culture in literature*. In *culture bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

William, R. 1977. *Marxism and literature*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Williams, R. 1976. *Keywords*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Yai, O. B. 1972. *Deviation and intertextuality in Yorùbá oral poetry*. A conference paper presented at 10th West African Language Conference. Legon University, Ghana.

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Names for males

Akòwé:	The literate one
Awoṣomáròde:	One who loves to dress up, even without going out
Bòdá Ilèèwé:	The School boy
Èniáfě:	One that is loved
Eyínáfě:	One with admirable set of teeth
Fààrípò:	The fashionable one
Máníjà:	Borrowed from the English word: Manager
Oriólówó:	One that is destined to be rich
Ọkọ Ìyàwó:	The husband of the bride (little husband of the new bride)

Names of females

Ayalóyà:	Wife of a lawyer
Ayílukọ:	One who clings to her husband
Èjiniwúrà:	One whose gap-tooth is likened to gold
Èjìwùmí:	One whose gap-tooth is admired
Gèlèòdùn:	The beauty of the head-tie is in tying it
Ìbàdí àrán:	One whose waist is like velvet
Ìdíìlẹ̀kẹ̀:	One whose buttock is likened to beads
Olójúarédè:	One whose eyes are seductive
Òwúrúbútú:	The plump one
Sisí Ilèèwé:	The School girl